

**SCIENTIFIC SERVICES
AND
FACILITIES**

ANNUAL REPORT

EXECUTIVE SUMMARIES 2002/03

SERVICES AND FACILITIES

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NERC Services & Facilities Management Team - Annual Report 2002/03

1. Introduction

NERC Science Programmes Directorate (SPD; but no longer an entity) provided financial support during 2002/03 for 26 Scientific Services and Facilities (S&F) that were operated by or on behalf of NERC, and to which the NERC community had access (Table 1). Research Ships and High Performance Computing facilities are separately accountable from the S&F and are not covered in this report.

Each S&F produces an annual report to a prescribed format with a number of mandatory and optional annexes. The self-contained summary report sections on the performance measures, activities and highlights of each S&F are now posted on the respective Facility web sites. Collated hard copies of the set are distributed to Service Review Group Members, internally within NERC and among the S&F (Service Heads and Steering Committee Chairs), and more widely on demand. It is not intended that there should be a hard-copy distribution to Science and Innovation Strategy Board members, nor Expert/Board Advisory and Working groups, nor to Peer Review College membership, although they may be asked to refer to Web-copies for information and comment. The respective overseeing Scientific Services Steering Committees have considered complete S&F reports, and accompanying annexes can be made available to readers on request.

2. Scientific Services and Facilities Management Group (S&FMG)

In the course of the year, S&FMG staff at Swindon working on S&F management comprised:

- Dr R L F Kay - Head of Group;
- Mr P W Purcell (also Head of ARSF¹), Dr A D Kaye - scientific administrators;
- Mrs J Sutton (Executive officer) who joined us in June 03, and Mrs V Smallridge (part-time administrative officer).

Financial, contract and procurement administrative support was provided by Financial and Information Systems Directorate (FISD).

The S&FMG Head of Group and scientific administrators each acted as Contact Point for a number of individual S&F, being responsible for:

- Facility management, direct or indirect line-management of NERC staff in the cases of ARSF, NERC RCL, GEP, MSTRF and SGF, RSDAS and ¹⁵NSIF;
- Oversight of contracts and/or service level agreements and financial control;
- Steering committee secretariatship and peer-review procedures;
- Programme management - notably the development of the Integrated Data System for ARSF and introduction to service of the new ARSF research aircraft;
- Prioritisation within, and allocation of, capital budget;
- Secretariat of the annual Services Review Group;
- Publicity; interface with the Science and Innovation Strategy Board (SISB) and the erstwhile sectoral Peer Review Committees (PRCs) and Grant Assessment Panels etc.

S&FMG staff were also involved in negotiations for commissioned research (mostly via NERC Thematic Programmes) and commercial contracts from which almost 10% of the total Services and Facilities budget derived.

¹ For key to S&F abbreviations see Table 1.

TABLE 1: SCIENTIFIC SERVICES AND FACILITIES, RECURRENT ALLOCATIONS AND RECEIPTS DUE TO SPD 2002/2003, (excluding capital)

	Macronic	Service and Location	Managing Institution(s)	S&F SB Allocation £k	Other NERC SB £k	Other Receipts £k	Total Recurrent Allocation
1	ISNSIF	15N Stable Isotope Facility, Merlewood	CEH Merlewood	61.60	7.00		68.60
2	AIF	Argon Isotope Facility, East Kilbride	SUERC	160.96			160.96
3	ARSF	Airborne Remote Sensing Facility	NERC SO	533.00		71.00	604.00
4	BIGF	British Isles GPS Facility		30.00			30.00
5	BOSCOR	British Oceanographic Sediment Core Research Facility, Southampton	SOC	65.59			65.59
6	CLRC SRS	Synchrotron Radiation Source, DL	CCLRC	80.00			80.00
7	CMRF	Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological Radar Facility, Chilbolton and RAL	CCLRC	0.00	80.00		80.00
8	DSRS	Dundee Satellite Receiving Station	Dundee University	249.22		28.00	277.22
9	EPFS	Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy, Southampton	Southampton University	89.15			89.15
10	GEP	NERC Geophysical Equipment Pool, Edinburgh	Edinburgh University and NERC SO	212.50			212.50
11	ICPAES	Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy Facility, Egham	RHUL	29.83			29.83
12	ICPMS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry Facility, Kingston (Service hiatus March - September)	Kingston University	122.05			122.05
13	ICSF	Isotope Community Support Facility, East Kilbride	SUERC	92.68			92.68
14	IMF	Ion Microprobe Facility, Edinburgh	Edinburgh University	117.69			117.69
15	LSCSIF	Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility, East Kilbride	SUERC	95.47			95.47
16	MEMF	Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility	Manchester University	40.00			40.00
17	MSF	Molecular Spectroscopy Facility, RAL	CCLRC	154.60			154.60
18	MSTRF	Mesosphere, Stratosphere, Troposphere Radar Facility, Aberystwyth and RAL	CCLRC	125.17			125.17
19	NIGL	NERC Isotope Geosciences Laboratory, Keyworth	BGS	698.00			698.00
20	OMSF	Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility, Bristol	Bristol University	55.83			55.83
21	ORADS	Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service	Oxford University	91.26			91.26
22	OUUSF	Open University U-Series Facility	Open University	82.66			82.66
23	RCL	NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory, East Kilbride	SUERC and NERC SO	400.75		50.00	450.75
24	RSDAS	Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service, Plymouth	PML	104.89	31.00		135.89
25	SGF	NERC Space Geodesy Facility, Herstmonceux	NERC SO	130.00		206.00	336.00
26	SMGF	Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility	Sheffield University	100.66			100.66
				00.00			0.00
	Steering Committees etc			30.00			30.00
	S&F Management			243.28			243.28
	TOTAL			4196.84	118.00	355.00	4669.84

3. Steering Committees

S&FMG is assisted in its management task by the Scientific Services Steering Committees (listed in Table 2), which advise on operational matters and provide peer-review of user applications. The SGF Steering Committee adopted BIGF, while the NERC Steering Committee for SRS and ISIS is no longer needed because of CCLRC, s facilities reverting to free-at-the-point-of-delivery service, and to which there are no longer NERC contributions.

TABLE 2: SCIENTIFIC SERVICES AND FACILITIES STEERING COMMITTEES 2002/03

Steering Committee	Facilities overseen	Chair 2002/03, affiliation	No Meetings
Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Steering Committee	ARSF, RSDAS*	Prof P Cross, UCL, now replaced by Dr R Bewley, English Heritage	2
British Ocean Sediment Core Research Facility Steering Committee	BOSCOR	Prof J Dowdeswell, Bristol, now replaced by Prof J Jones, UCL	1
Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Steering Committee	DSRS, RSDAS*	Dr T Guymer, SOC	1
Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy Steering Committee	EPFS	Mr A Lamb, NRSCL, now replaced by Dr S Mackin, Surrey	2
Geophysical Equipment Facility Steering Committee	GEP	Prof M Forde, Edinburgh, now replaced by Dr T Murray, Leeds	2
Inductively Coupled Plasma Spectrometry Facilities Steering Committee	ICPMS, ICPAES	Prof M Pollard, Bradford	2
Ion Microprobe Facility Steering Committee	IMF including tephrochronology + MEMF	Prof B W Yardley, Leeds	1
Molecular Spectroscopy Facility Steering Committee	MSF	Dr J Barnett, Oxford, since replaced by Prof G Duxbury, Glasgow	2
NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee	MSTRF, CMRF	Prof C Collier, Salford	2
NERC ISIS and SRS Steering Committee (from 2000)	SRS, ISIS	Prof A Putnis, Muenster, Germany	0
NERC Isotope Geosciences Facilities Steering Committee	NIGL, AIF, ICSF, OUUSF	Prof N Harris, OU	2
NERC Isotope Life Sciences Steering Committee/Organic Mass Spectrometry Facility	¹⁵ NSIF, LSCSIF, OMSF	Professor D S Powison, IACR-Rothamsted, now replaced by Prof J Laybourn-Parry, Nottingham	1
NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory Steering Committee	RCL	Prof D Keen, Coventry, now replaced by Prof C Caseldine, Exeter	4 (1 joint meeting plus 1 or 2 separate meetings each)
Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service Advisory Panel	ORADS	Mr A Saville, National Museum of Scotland	
NERC Space Geodesy Steering Committee	SGF, BIGF	Prof P Moore, Newcastle, now replaced by Dr S Laxon, UCL	1
Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility Steering Committee	SMGF	Prof M Macnair, Exeter, to be replaced by Dr J M Pemberton, Edinburgh	1
Total NERC-supported	16		25
Other SCs not supported by NERC except by SPD representation			
SRS Assessment Panels	SRS		2
ISIS Panels (see SRS above)	ISIS		2

*Jointly overseen

4. Management and Staff Arrangements

Most of the S&F were managed via contracts or Service Level Agreements (SLA). Only ARSF and SGF operated under direct line-management from Swindon. Approximately 65 staff are involved with operation of the S&F and employed by NERC, directly or through its Research at Centres, by other Research Councils or by HEIs. A summary of the current management and staff arrangements is given at Annex 1.

5. Contractual Information

Current contract/SLA information, lead-science area, review dates, and Swindon Office contacts relating to each of the S&F budget lines are also summarised at Annex 1. Most S&F are block-funded via contract/SLA, with contributions to staff and recurrent infrastructure costs paid in return for agreed proportions of capacity (usually not the total) being made available to the NERC community following peer-review.

NEODC transferred to management via the EO programme at the beginning of the reporting year.

It should be noted that where the unit cost of service delivery is relatively high, and/or NERC is a minor customer of an externally managed operation, funding is either fully or partially on a 'pay-as-you-go' (PAYG) basis (eg for CMRF, MEMF). Access to ISIS and SRS reverts to block funding (by CCLRC) from April 2003.

6. Financial Data

The 2002/03 NERC cash-spend on 26 services was approximately £5.13M, including capital refurbishment. Table 1 summarises the facilities' allocations, together with contributions from other NERC Science Budget sources such as the Thematic and Non-Thematic Mode grants, as well as from external funds.

With one exception (SGF, which has no direct users), the S&F are required to provide cost-allocation data attributing the real and/or notional costs of providing services to users. The data on individual usages, as tabulated in the Annual Summary of Scientific Services 2002/03 Cost-allocations, are available on request.

Council's decision in 2001 that the Services & Facilities, as part of a wider NERC requirement, should find a total of 10% savings in its baseline funding over the next two years precipitated STB-delegated management action, during this FY. Support for MEMF is still being phased out, funding for CMRF comes from the Atmospheric Science Programme, and although the previous year's moratorium on funding new facilities had in principle been lifted, no new facilities were established.

Joint Infrastructure Fund (JIF)

Over the last five years the national funding schemes JREI and JIF and SRIF have provided opportunities for HEI-based facilities to renew and/or expand their equipment capital base. These and several others have impacted significantly on S&F in terms of increased capabilities, and there is evidence of greater calls for recurrent support and on the capital maintenance budget, possibly at the level of 5% or more of the initial JIF investment. (Notable examples of these are the two AMS instruments, an additional ion microprobe and a 10-fold increase in seismic monitoring equipment.) SISB will inevitably be faced with a bid to enable NERC to sustain the enlarged portfolio during the coming financial year.

Capital Budget

The Services and Facilities Capital Budget, amounting on average to 10% of the Services and Facilities Science Budget allocation, is intended to ensure that regular investment in, and replacement of, equipment maintains S&F capabilities at a high level. Bids against this fund are normally received from S&F each January and allocations are made even before the recurrent allocations to S&F are finalised. Although there are indications that there will be further national schemes to invest in scientific capital, following the end of JIF, JREI and SRIF, there was only the S&F capital budget to support maintenance of the capital base during the reporting year.

The allocations made from the budget in 2002/2003 are listed in Table 3. Major calls on the funds included: a high-precision GPS/inertial position and attitude system for the ARSF research aircraft; a contribution to the replacement of a NIGL stable isotope mass spectrometer; replacement detectors and software upgrades at DSRS; high temperature GCMS components for OMSF; a leak-detector and probe upgrades at IMF; and a modest top-up to the funding for the extensive BOSCOR core-store extension which was mostly funded by SOC/University of Southampton.

TABLE 3: SCIENTIFIC SERVICES AND FACILITIES CAPITAL ALLOCATIONS 2002/2003 AND PROPOSED FORWARD COMMITMENTS 2003/04 AND BEYOND

Service	Items Bid 2002/2003	2002/03 Allocation £k	Forward Look Items	2002/03 Forward Commitment £k
15NSIF				
AIF	Minor capital	5.90		
ARSF	PAS system	75.00		
BOSCOR				
BIGF				
CLRC SRS				
CMRF	Replacement 94 GHz radar tube	93.00		
DSRS	Replacement detectors + software upgrade phase 2	45.30		
EPFS	Spectro-goniometer for DRDF measurements	23.00		
GEP				
ICPAES				
ICPMS	Emergency laser replacement	11.00		
ICSF				
IMF				
LSCSIF	Elemental analyzer (collaborative & SUERC)	17.70		
MEMF				
MSF	Upgrade temperature control system and pressure gauges	76.15		
MSTRF				
NIGL	Water mass spec 30% contribution	59.00		
OMSF	Agilent 6890 G/C and FID detector	21.74		
ORADS	2 freeze-drier pumps	6.52		
OUUSF				
RCL	Cosmogenic isotope analysis lab set-up loan – turbo-molecular vacuum pumps + RCL refurbishment	106.40		
RSDAS				
SGF				
SMGF	PC workstations and Software	10.00		
Total		550.71		

7. Output and Performance Measures

Applications:

In the course of FY2002/03, 25 of the Services & Facilities (SGF has no direct users) assessed project applications according to the following distribution:

	Applications	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1/β	R* or Pilot Project	Reject
Total	459	18	206	141	14	5	57	24

The total number of applications apparently declined by about 10% of the previous year but this reflects removal of NEODC, ISIS and SRS users from the compilation, together with the ramp-down of MEMF support. All following compilation data are similarly affected.

In most facilities an α4 grading, exceptionally a high α3, is necessary for an academic project, and it is generally the case that α3 projects are only supported if a student is involved; no support was approved for any sub-α3 proposal unless a resubmission achieved a fundable grade. Every effort is made to accommodate demands of NERC research grant-holders and eligible fellows and to support NERC-funded research students. Projects graded R*, particularly those involving students and first-time applicants, are typically improved following facility and/or steering committee advice and upgraded on re-submission.

Facility Usage:

The recorded user-profile was as follows:

HEI Academic	NERC Research Centre	NERC Fellow	NERC PhD	Other PhD	Commercial	Total
349	75	9	119	156	93	801

The recorded in-year distribution of projects by science areas was:

SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Total
61	250	98	69	190	49	22	739

Usage of S&F and distribution of projects by science area varies from the number of projects peer-reviewed due to factors such as multiple applicants, multi-phase projects, projects extending across two or more financial years etc.

Publications:

During Calendar Year 2002, the Services & Facilities contributed, by means of collaboration, service and/or data provision, to the following publication output by science area and nature of output:

SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Total
46	276	129	52	149	75	9	736

Refereed Publications	Non-Refereed Conference Proceedings	PhD Theses	Grand Total
344	325	67	736

8. Services Review

General

The Services Review Group (SRG) is convened annually in January with an *ad hoc* membership normally drawn from Peer Review Committees (PRCs) and the Science and Innovation Strategy Board (SISB), to assess and prioritise applications for new services, and audit and review those existing services which have contract/SLA end-dates 15 months later. The SRG recommendations are presented for approval by the SISB and (in the reporting year) the PRCs are advised of the outcome. This constitutes an 'Exit Strategy' aimed at continually refreshing the services portfolio to reflect scientific priorities and user-needs.

This mechanism is open to any potential new service with running costs below £150kpa (not including capital; initial capitalisation can only exceptionally be supported from the services budget). Where it seems likely that more than one institution could offer a given service, a prior options exercise is conducted, possibly leading to extra bids being submitted in competition with the original bid. Applications for services where the costs exceed £150 kpa are not normally supported from the services Infrastructure baseline and funds must be sought from SISB.

Services Review Group 2003

The 2003 SRG met on 27-28 January 2003 and was again chaired by Professor T A Brown, UMIST, who had recently retired from SISB. SRG membership was drawn exclusively from the PRCs: the Chair or an alternate and one other nominated member, respectively, from each.

In addition to the chairman the membership comprised: Dr Julian Andrews, UEA (ESPRC), Dr John Ballard, RAL (ASPRC), Prof M Cresser, York (TSPRC), Professor Lyn Jones, Dundee (TSPRC), Prof Roger Jones, Jyväskylä (FSPRC), Dr Seymour Laxon, UCL (MSPRC), Dr Gillian Malin, East Anglia (MSPRC), Dr Andrew Orr-Ewing, Bristol (ASPRC), Prof Steven Sparks, Bristol (ESPRC), Professor Paul Younger, Newcastle upon Tyne. Participating Swindon Office staff comprised Mr D A Brown (Director, Science Programmes), Dr R L F Kay (Head S&FMG), Mr P Purcell and Dr A Kaye (Secretary).

Items of business considered were:

- the consultation for, and review of, the current NERC Services & Facilities (S&F) portfolio;
- applications for renewal of current S&F;
- new applications for support as S&F.

Proposals for Renewal of Existing Services & Facilities

SRG2003 considered bids for renewal from seven existing S&F, plus one new bid. The prospective renewals had been advertised on the NERC Website, and made known to other potential bidders in order to stimulate expressions of interest for alternative services provision. In the event, no competitive bids were received.

Using the averaged scores (out of five) against the standard criteria of Need, Uniqueness, Quality of Service, and Quality of Science and Training, all renewal bids scored well above the perceived pass-mark of 4.0 (above which members had accepted that money was probably better spent on facilities rather than e.g. on equivalent grants). All were thus sufficiently highly rated to merit strong recommendation for renewed service provision at the end of their current contract/SLA. The prioritised list of bids is shown below.

Facility	Average Score
Renewals	
SGF, Herstmonceux	5.00
LSMSF, Merlewood, Bristol, East Kilbride	5.00
EPFS, Southampton,	4.88
GEF, Edinburgh	4.50
ICSF, East Kilbride	4.38
OUUSF, OU	4.38
NIGL, BGS Keyworth	4.25

New Bids

Facility	Average Score
New bids	
Cosmogenic Isotope Analysis Facility, East Kilbride	4.83
Micromorphology, St Andrews	3.63

The bid to establish the NERC Cosmogenic Isotope Analysis Facility at the Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre, from Professor Fallick at SUERC and Prof Mike Summerfield of Edinburgh University, was rated highly and recommended for funding, subject to some additional evidence being presented to SISB of the scientific need in the UK and global contexts; this requirement was subsequently met.

The need to block-fund a micromorphology facility was not felt to be pressing, in view of the currently small NERC-funded user-base.

Completion of the Review of the Whole S&F Portfolio

SISB subsequently approved all the SRG recommendations at its February meeting and pronounced itself satisfied that the S&F portfolio cover all facilities with scores at 4.0 or above is effective, good value for money and as flexible and responsive to changing demands as can reasonably be expected.

The financial Forward Look for the whole Services and Facilities portfolio including the SRG2003 recommendations was therefore presented to the Board. SISB approved full funding of the amount needed to cover the now fully reviewed portfolio. The S&F baseline requested, and subsequently confirmed, was £5.473M.

In addition, S&FMG was tasked to explore establishing the Ecotron part of the renewal bid of the Centre for Population Biology as a S&F, and this is expected to result in a new contract from April 2004 for block-funded infrastructure to support grant-funded projects of 18-24 months duration.

9. Publicity

The S&F brochure is now a “virtual document” published via the NERC Website as a hub for sites maintained by each funded S&F, with details of access, peer-review and charging arrangements for each (and also for those recognised but not funded). This is continually updated and the linkages to individual S&F websites are being revised and improved.

Articles appearing in *NERC Planet Earth*, relating to S&F were as follows:

Articles:

1. New Light on Earth and Environmental Sciences (Summer 2002). Two page article on Synchrotron Radiation Source.
2. Clouds - Do they Obscure the Forecast? (Summer 2002). Two-page item about clouds and the forecasting of global warming, focusing on measurements taken by the Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological Radar Facility.
3. Oral History (Summer 2002). Two page article on the use of the NERC Isotope Geoscience Laboratory to look at Strontium isotopes in ancient bones and teeth.

10. Acknowledgements and Staff Changes.

S&FMG acknowledges the unstinting contributions to the effective running of the S&F made by all staff and managements involved; honorary efforts, some involving considerable workloads, by Chairs and members of the S&F Steering Committees and SRG are particularly appreciated. Credit is due to personnel in other departments for administrative and financial assistance, and to the management of each S&F for timely provision of data pertinent to Output & Performance Measures, Steering Committee and peer-review business.

Dr Roger Wood retired from being joint Head of SGF in March 2003 after a distinguished 39-year career wholly spent in Government/Research Council science.

Dr Sarah James handed back the reins of ICPAES to Nick Walsh, temporarily, in August 2003.

Finally, it is with great sadness that we record the untimely death of Dr John Ballard in September 2003. John made an immense contribution to NERC science in the broad, but especially as head of MSF, as ASPRC and SRG2003 member, as well as being the RAL manager of the head of MSTRF (and NEODC).

R L F Kay, P W Purcell and A D Kaye

Scientific Services Management Team

Science and Innovation Funding

September 2003

ANNEX 1: S&F CONTRACT/SLA, TERMS, STAFF NUMBERS AND STATUS, REVIEW DATES, AND SWINDON OFFICE CONTACT AT NOVEMBER 2003

	Mnemonic	Service Name	Location	Lead Area	Type	Term (yr)	Staff	Contract Reference	Contract end-date (31 March)	Service Review Date (Jan)	Service contact
1	AIF	Argon Isotope Facility	SUERC, East Kilbride	ES	C	5	2PD + 0.5T	F14/G6/35/01	2007	2006	RLFK
2	ARSF	Airborne Remote Sensing Facility	Swindon/Kidlington	TFS/E O	D	5	0.3B4, 2B4, B6	SPG direct	2008	2007	PWP
3	BIGF	British Isles GPS Facility	Nottingham	ES	C	2	1 Misc	F14/G6/108	2005	2004	ADK
4	BOSCOR	British Oceanographic Sediment Core Research Facility	SOC	ES	C part	5	0.5B4, B6	Non-Capital element part of SOC contract	2007	2006	RLFK
5	CMRF							SLA			
6	DSRS	Dundee Satellite Receiving Station	Dundee University	MS/EO	C	5	7 misc.	F14/G6/4/01	2008	2007	PWP
7	EPFS	Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy	Southampton University	TFS/E O	C	5	0.6 Pool Man., 0.2 PD, 0.5 PG, 0.4T	F14/G6/06/01 DST/26/70/04	2009	2008	PWP
8a	GEF	Geophysical Equipment Facility - Edinburgh Node - formerly Geophysical Equipment Pool	Edinburgh University	ES	C/D staff	3	1 B5, 1 B6, 1 T, 1 misc.	F14/G6/24/01	2007+	2006?	RLFK
8b		Geophysical Equipment Facility Leicester Node (ex SEIS-UK)	Leicester University		C	3	1 T, 1 Misc, 0.4 Misc, 0.2 Misc	TBA	2007+	2006?	
9	ICPF	Inductively Coupled Plasma Facility - Atomic Emission Spectrometry Node	Royal Holloway, London University	ES	C	3	0.6 PG	F14/G6/38	2006	2005	ADK
		Inductively Coupled Plasma Facility - Mass Spectrometry Node	Kingston University	ES	C		1 PD, 1 PG, 0.6 Misc	F14/G6/91			
10	ICSF	Isotope Community Support Facility	SUERC, East Kilbride	ES	C	3	1 RA	F14/G6/11/01 DST/26/70/08	2007+	2006?	RLFK

	Mnemonic	Service Name	Location	Lead Area	Type	Term (yr)	Staff	Contract Reference	Contract end-date (31 March)	Service Review Date (Jan)	Service contact
11	IMF	Ion Microprobe Facility	Edinburgh University	ES	C	5	3 Misc	F14/G6/40 DST/26/70/09	2008	2007	RLFK
12a	LSMSF	Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility – CEH Node (formerly 15N Stable Isotope Facility)	CEH Merlewood	TFS	SLA	5	1 B5 1 B6 1 B7	SLA CEH Merlewood	2007+	2006?	RLFK
12b		Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility – Bristol Node – formerly OMSF	Bristol University	TFS	C	3	1 PG(?) Dr I Bull	F14/G6/13/01			
12c		Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility – East Kilbride Node - formerly LSCSIF	SUERC, East Kilbride	TFS	C	3	1 RA 0.5 T 0.5 T	F14/G6/20/01 DST26/70/01			
13	MEMF	Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility	Manchester University	ES	C	3	1.5 misc.	F14/G6/32/01 DST26/70/17	Ends 2004 to PAYG?	N/A	RLFK
14	MSF	Molecular Spectroscopy Facility	CLRC RAL	AS	SLA	5	1.785 misc.	SLA CLRC	2005	2004	RLFK/ ADK
15	MSTRF	Mesosphere, Stratosphere, Troposphere Radar Facility	Aberystwyth University CLRC RAL	AS	SLA	5	0.5B5, 1.9 misc.	SLA CLRC	2005	2004	ADK
16	NIGL	NERC Isotope Geosciences Laboratory	BGS Keyworth	ES	SLA	5	c70% of 18 misc	SLA	2007+	2006?	RLFK
17	ORADS	Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerating Dating Service	Oxford University	ES	C	3	6 T 1 C 1 Misc	F14/G6/25/02	2005	2004	RLFK
18	OUUSF	OU U-series Facility	Open University	ES	C	3	1 T 0.2 Misc 0.5 Misc	F14/G6/47 DST26/70/20	2007	2006	RLFK
19	CIVF	Prince Madog Coastal & Inshore Vessel Facility	Bangor University	MS	PAYG – C?	3	N/A	TBA	2005	2004	ADK
20	RCL	NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory	SUERC, East Kilbride	ES	C	5	0.5B5, 2.5PD,4 T, AO	F14/G6/46	2008	2007	RLFK

	Mnemonic	Service Name	Location	Lead Area	Type	Term (yr)	Staff	Contract Reference	Contract end-date (31 March)	Service Review Date (Jan)	Service contact
21	RSDAS	Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service	CCMS Plymouth	MS/EO	SLA with CCMS	5	0.3B5, 2.4 misc B7-8.	SLA with CCMS	2005	2004	RLFK/PWP
22	NSDF	NERC Facility for Scientific Diving	SAMS Dunstaffnage	MS	In prep	2		SLA with SAMS	2005	2004	RLFK
23	SGF	Space Geodesy Facility	Herstmonceux and CEH Monks Wood	ES/EO	D from 1999	5	2B5, 3B6,3B7	Two-thirds of the funding from MOD and DTI (BNSC)	2009	2008	RLFK
24	SMGF	Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility	Sheffield University	TFS	C	3	PD	F14/6/48/01 DST26/70/66	2005	2004	ADK
25	SRS	Synchrotron Radiation Source	CLRC DL	ES	SLA + PAYG	1	N/A	SLA CLRC	2003	N/A	RLFK

Key: NERC staff by Band: B4/UG7/pilot/instrument specialist; B5/SSO/SPTO, B6/HSO/HPTO, B7/SO/PTO; Post-Doctoral Research Assistant PD; Post-Graduate Research Assistant, PG; Technician, T; Clerical, C; other miscellaneous non-NERC staff, misc.

Service Contacts at NERC Swindon Office (SPG staff) by initials: Dr R L F Kay; Mr. P W Purcell; Dr A D Kaye.

SSPMG-managed NERC staffs associated with services were:

- Dr C L Bryant (Head RCL, East Kilbride).
- Dr S J White (Head MSTRF, RAL, and NEODC now under EOP);
- Mr. P Kearney (Head) and Mr. A Ball (GEP, Edinburgh University);
- Mr. P W Purcell (ARSF, based at Swindon); Capt C Joseph, Mr. D Davies; and Mr. A Edgar, Mr. F Tadina, (ARSF, based at Kidlington),
- Dr G Appleby (SGF, based at CEH Monks Wood); and Dr R Wood (retired March 2003), Mr. P Standen, Mr. P Gibbs, Mr. D Benham, Mr. D Walters, Mr. R Sherwood and Miss V Smith (SGF, based at Herstmonceux).

Other abbreviations: PAYG, 'Pay-As-You-Go' (SPG maintains single accounts on behalf of all NERC funding modes). D, Direct management; C, Contract; AS, ES, MS, TFS: Atmospheric, Earth, Marine, Terrestrial and Freshwater Sciences; EO, Earth Observation; SBA, Science-based Archaeology (ES/TFS).

Our reference

Your reference

Direct line/e-mail

J.Laybourn-Parry@nottingham.ac.uk

**School of Life and
Environmental Sciences**

3rd July 2003

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Dr D. Lin,
Natural Environmental Research Council,
Polaris House,
North Star Avenue,
Swindon,
SN2 1EU

NERC LIFE SCIENCES MASS SPECTROMETRY FACILITY

Dear Dr Lin,

The annual reports of the three nodes of the Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility are testament to the continuing success of the Facility. Each of the nodes received consistent highest scores for need, uniqueness, quality of service and quality of science and training in the review for the financial year 2002-2003. The combined nodes of LSMSF supported 38 projects during 2002/2003. A significant number of these projects contributed the NERC thematic programmes (GANE, Soil Biodiversity), as well as to responsive mode funded projects and Ph.D. projects. During 2002 the Facility achieved an excellent output of 35 peer reviewed publications, many of which included facility staff as authors. The training of graduate students is an important activity undertaken by the staff of LSMSF, resulting in a number of Ph.D theses, most supported by NERC studentships.

During 2002/2003 the Organic Mass Spectrometry node of LSMSF received a significant level of refurbishment and additional instrumentation that was supported by funds secured from SRIF. While this will strengthen the excellent reputation and capability of the node, it did cause very considerable disruption during the year, with equipment 'down time'. Nonetheless the node sustained a good performance for which the staff must be congratulated. The ¹⁵N SIF node is preparing for its imminent move to Lancaster University, which is likely to impose some disruption during 2003/2004.

While the three elements of LSMSF have operated in a complementary fashion for many years, we are always seeking ways to maximise operational efficiency and to deliver a more streamlined service to NERC users. Together the three nodes provide

Head of School: Professor J Laybourn-Parry

Professor D Archer, Professor C J Barnard, Professor J M Behnke, Professor J Bradley,

Professor J F Peberdy.

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2000

support for virtually all applications of organic and light stable isotope mass spectrometry, however, there are potential problems with respect to new applicants and their understanding of the services available from each node. Applicants may make a number of applications to the different nodes, which results in confusion and an inefficient use of Facility staff time. In future the LSMSF will operate a single entity. Not only will this increase the efficiency of service, it will enable synergistic operation of the three nodes by facilitating sharing of knowledge, expertise and analytical capabilities. Moreover, it provides a level of insurance in the event of serious instrument failure. In future applicants will make a single electronic application – effectively a one-stop-shop. The advantage of this is that it enables LSMSF to direct an application to the appropriate node(s). The current Directors of each node will undertake the role of LSMSF Director in rotation.

In summary the LSMSF has sustained a strong performance during 2002/2003 and has implemented measures to enhance the quality of its service to the NERC community.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads "Johanna Laybourn-Parry". The signature is written in black ink and has a long, sweeping underline that extends to the right.

Johanna Laybourn-Parry
Chairman NERC LSMSF

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE ¹⁵N STABLE ISOTOPE FACILITY (¹⁵N SIF)	FUNDING BLOCK	AGREEMENT SLA	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1984	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The ¹⁵N stable isotope facility (¹⁵N SIF) (now an integral part of the NERC Life Science Mass Spectrometry Facility (LSMSF) along with the formerly named OMSF and LSCSIF) is recognised as a facility, providing light stable isotope analysis of ¹⁵N and ¹³C for ecological research workers in NERC institutes, or in university departments receiving NERC funding. In order to achieve this the Facility houses a number of state-of-the-art instrumental capabilities, namely gas chromatography, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, elemental analyser-isotope ratio mass spectrometry, trace gas-IRMS and compound specific IRMS. The Facility undertakes research and development, covering all aspects of ¹⁵N and ¹³C analysis technology and applications, which is of direct benefit to, or to meet the future needs of terrestrial and freshwater life sciences research. The ¹⁵N SIF aims to promote the awareness, application and technology of ¹⁵N and ¹³C analysis techniques and to disseminate to the wider scientific community, in addition to provide training and promote good practice in the use of ¹⁵N and ¹³C analysis techniques. We aim to provide specialist support for those user communities identified in the NERC mission whose needs can be served by the Facility. Peer review of the quality and relevance of the applications ensures that only the best science is supported.

Key advantages of the Facility:

- It provides a focal point for external/internal researchers to discuss aspects of their research during all stages of an isotope related project. It also provides a source of collaboration for users unable to access sophisticated instrumentation or lacking in the expertise. We pride ourselves with our close customer/researcher relationship.
- Highly efficient sample management, sample preparation and processing, careful quality control to ensure that only superior sets of analytical results are produced, data interpretation, detailed collation of output data contribute greatly to the high quality service offered by the Facility to the NERC TFS user community.
- Underpinning active training for NERC students and post-doctoral researchers in the science of stable isotope mass spectrometry. All users working on NILSSC graded projects are actively encouraged to visit the ¹⁵N stable isotope facility and become fully involved in sample analyses, therefore maximising the training aspects of the service.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review:		28/01/03
Need 5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 5	Quality of Science & Training 5	Average 5	

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 50%	Staff & Status SSO Manager (B5) 50% established HSO (B6) 50% established SO (B7) 100% established	Next Review (January) 2008	Contract Ends (31 March) 2008
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY

Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k						Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	Bulk C	Bulk N	Gases (CO ₂ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O)	Extended analyses	Individual compounds	Grinding /nitrogen gas			
18K	0.017	0.017	0.017-0.025	0.075	0.025-0.075	0.005	0	14	124.34k

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)

2002-03	18k	2003-04	18.5k	2004-05	19k	2004-06	19.5k	2006-07	20k
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STEERING COMMITTEE NILSSC	Independent Members 12	Meetings per annum 2	Other S&F Overseen LSCIF and OMSF
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APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)

	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	3	10	1	0	0	0	0	0
Other academic			1					
Students		3	4				2	
Pilot							2	
TOTAL	3	13	6	0	0	0	2	0

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years —1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	0.33	4	2	0	0	0	0	0
Other Academic								
Students		2	1.33				1.33	
Pilot							1.33	
TOTAL	0.33	6	3.33	0	0	0	0	0

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects	1	3	2	0	0	0	0	
Other Academic			1					
Students								
Pilot								2

USER PROFILE (current FY)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other			
	Total	NERC	Total				NERC						
29	13	9	8	6	1	0	0	0	0	0			
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other			
	Total	NERC	Total				NERC						
22	12	6	6	4	1	0	0	0	0	0			

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic 14	Centre/Survey 6	NERC Fellows 0	PhD 9	Commercial 0
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic 12	Centre/Survey 6	NERC Fellows 0	PhD 6.33	Commercial 0.66

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS 43	EO	Polar	Grand Total 43	Refereed 16	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc 24	PhD Theses 3
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS 6.3%	AS	TFS 93.7%	EO	Polar				
OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS 36	EO	Polar	Grand Total 36	Refereed 12.66	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc 20.66	PhD Theses 2.66
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS 9.1%	AS	TFS 90.9%	EO	Polar				

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

General

From April 2002 to March 2003 the ^{15}N SIF has given support to, and been involved in the development of twenty two different NILSSC approved projects with UK universities, institutions and centres. In addition, six CEH projects and one BIRE contract has been supported. Three of the NERC projects are collaborative with the ^{15}N SIF and utilise our recently commissioned instrumentation. Support has been given to six Soil Biodiversity and four GANE thematic research grants. A total of nine Ph.D / M. Res. students/post-doctoral researchers from all sources have received hands on training within the facility in the use and applications of stable isotope mass spectrometry throughout the year.

Operation

2002/2003 has seen very heavy utilisation of the analytical instrumentation by the NERC research community. All analytical instruments have been in continuous use with minimal downtime. The EA IRMS instruments have seen a 3 fold increase in usage this year. Micromass UK replaced a rotary vane pump within one day on the new EA-IRMS after its catastrophic failure. A service contract funded by CEH was purchased covering the GC-MS instrument. It has been the most productive year in the history of the facility in terms of the number and variety of samples processed. The year has seen in excess of 13,000 analyses carried out by the Facility, nearly double the annual amount analysed in previous years. The Head of Facility expresses gratitude to Mr Sleep and Miss Grant (^{15}N SIF) for their dedication and commitment to ensuring the efficient throughput of QC samples. Staff have co-authored five manuscripts this FY. Both staff have now received full training in gas chromatography methodologies (Agilent Technologies courses) and both are capable of operating both EA and trace gas IRMS systems. The SO training programme is continuing to ensure that all three staff have the capability to troubleshoot within the ion source and high vacuum systems of all facility instruments. Mr. Sleep has received in house training on GC/MS and GC-C-IRMS operation and maintenance.

Commercial exploitation

In mid-2002, the NERC research and collaborative centres innovation fund awarded the ^{15}N SIF £5k funds to carry out a marketing survey for an 'in-house' designed N_2 gas preparative unit which has already been used extensively on two NERC peer-reviewed projects. The unit proved to be very cheap to construct and is highly cost effective allowing greater sensitivity of analysis and over a much shorter time-scale. The facility has recently received information from the NERC marketing scouts and patent lawyers that a leading isotope analytical company wishes to purchase marketing rights for the instrument and to develop it further to perform rapid CO_2 analyses.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Examination of all peer-reviewed applications to the ^{15}N SIF during the last 5 years has shown that 93.6 % are categorised under the terrestrial and freshwater life sciences cost category; with the remainder being allocated under marine sciences and technology. The key NERC ENRI's supported by the ^{15}N SIF are Biodiversity, Natural Resources and Global Change. It is predicted that Pollution and Environmental Risks and Hazards will become more important within the next 5 years. It is expected that the facility will continue to perform a dynamic role in addressing issues important to the NERC 2002-2007 strategic plan specifically with respect to the 'Earths Life Support systems' and 'Climate change'. There has been an overall increase in the tendency of research groups to exploit several of techniques within one particular application. Below is a 'snapshot' of the very diverse range of NILSSC peer-reviewed research undertaken by the facility, that serve to highlight the broad range of a) applied technical methodologies and b) underlying expertise the NERC ^{15}N SIF.

Natural abundance of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ plotted against $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ natural abundance for fruit bodies of fungi characteristic of waxcap grasslands. All samples were collected from the Southcote site. The 'Waxcap fungi' included *H. pratensis*, *H. laeta*, *H. conica*, *H. splendidissima* and *H. virgata*. 'Saprotrophic fungi' included *Cystoderma amianthinum*, *Panaeolus rickenii*, *Mycena* spp. *Entoloma confreudum*; 'Clavarioid' fungi included members of the genera *Clavulina*, *Clavulinopsis*, *Clavaria* and *Clavulinopsis*, as well as the earth tongues *Trichoglossum* and *Geoglossum*.

1) Autecology of *Hygrocybe* spp. in temperate grasslands (University of Aberystwyth). Members of the genus *Hygrocybe* are ubiquitous and colourful components of many undisturbed and nutrient-poor grasslands in Northern Europe. Through surveys of the distribution of *Hygrocybe* spp. and of other macrofungal genera showing similar patterns of occurrence, a picture is gradually emerging of the more important waxcap grassland sites, and of those species in greatest need of protection. As part of a UK-based Soil Biodiversity Programme, the researchers have monitored the effect of various management regimes on fruiting of *Hygrocybe* spp. Fine-scale mapping combined with genetic analysis (AFLP/ISSR) is being used to measure the extent of individual genets, with species-specific PCR probes being used to establish the vertical location of mycelia. Analysis of the natural abundance of the stable isotopes

in fruit bodies showed that grassland *Hygrocybe* spp. show significant depletion for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (-28 to -30‰) and enrichment for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (+12 to +18‰), a pattern that sets them apart from most macrofungi previously examined (see Figure above left). Furthermore, the other macrofungi associated with these undisturbed grasslands (e.g. *Clavariaceae*, *Geoglossaceae*) have very similar isotope

signatures despite being taxonomically unrelated. Experiments using plant litter enriched in ^{15}N are currently underway and will further clarify our understanding of the role of these fungi in nutrient cycling and explain why they are so adversely affected by many agricultural practices.

2) Development and application of novel methods that determine the functional phylogeny of microbial communities. 'Cutting edge' alpha 5 molecular DNA/RNA science, from the University of York and CEH-Oxford, aims to understand the role of prokaryotic communities in ecosystem function by pinpointing the actual specific component populations involved. Advances have been made over the last decade through the application of molecular methods that provide community diversity signatures based on 16S and 23S ribosomal RNA analysis. However, whilst useful, these techniques have been restrictive as they are unable to determine the functionally active component groups. ^{13}C isotopically labelled substrates (^{13}C phenol) have therefore been utilised in this project to specifically identify organisms responsible for phenol degradation in an industrial bioreactor. The specific objectives of SIF were to confirm that the high density RNA contained enhanced levels of ^{13}C , thus unambiguously linking the anabolism of phenol to the community members identified. Using EA-IRMS analyses the objectives of the research project were fulfilled and that the utility of the isotope probing technique has great potential to provide previously unknown access to information between micro-organisms and their role in biogeochemical/biodegradative processes. (Rapid Comm. Mass Spec., 16, Issue 23, 2179-2183, 2002). The success of this work has instigated a Second Round Soil Biodiversity grant due for completion in 2004.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Aims

The ^{15}N SI facility provides a cost-effective, high quality resource for the provision of light stable isotope analyses to researchers in the terrestrial, ecological and environmental sciences. Under NERC policy, only the best science is supported by subjecting applications to peer-review by the NERC isotope life sciences steering committee. Since the level of demand for the facility has increased since the last Service Review, only applications of α 3 and above will be supported. Sections 4 & 7, in Appendix 1 explicitly demonstrate the facility advancements, in terms of quality and contribution to NERC science. The demand reflects the increased status of the facility, the introduction of new technologies and the higher quality of science now undertaken. Samples have been traditionally analysed as part of the NERC scientific service, however the facility has become more recognised as providing a wealth of other essential support for researchers, not just a result producing service. Researchers are frequently requesting collaborative proposals with the facility, particularly when new methodologies or techniques require the expertise of facility personnel. The ^{15}N SIF emphasises its strong policy for maintaining high quality control procedures for all isotopic determinations carried out within the Facility. This includes regular calibration of working standards with NIST standards, 'round robin' tests with other internationally recognised stable isotope laboratories and bi-monthly 'blind' comparisons terrestrial samples as part of the Wageningen International Soil & Plant exchange programme. The facility aims to carry out research and development in any aspect of ^{13}C and ^{15}N analysis which would be of benefit to the terrestrial life-sciences research and promotes the use of stable isotope techniques in the resolution of environmental and ecological problems. The facility provides training for, and promotes good practice among the user community in the use of ^{13}C and ^{15}N analytical techniques. It provides essential support to the user, before the analytical stage is reached, in planning the project, and afterwards, in interpreting the results. We strongly encourage students and post-doctoral staff, to undertake analytical work within the ^{15}N SIF as part of their PhD and/or research agenda. Since the SRG in January 2003, the ^{15}N SIF has amalgamated with the OMSF and LSCSIF to form the Life Sciences Isotope Facility to yield a single point of contact, one-stop-shop, facility. The combined facility will:- increase the efficiency of service co-ordination, facilitate access by potential users to more than one service by approaching a single node, ensure a synergistic operation of the three facilities and provide a level of insurance/cover in the event of catastrophic instrument failure.

Future developments:-

1. During the past three years, the ^{15}N SIF staff have designed the plans for the new laboratories that will ultimately accommodate the ^{15}N SIF at CEH-Lancaster, as part of the relocation to an overall Centre of Excellence in Environmental Sciences in the North West. In fact Prof. J. Lawton stated that "the amalgamation will create one of the biggest environmental science groups in Europe with great potential and an exciting future". The relocation will undoubtedly benefit the facility profile and its NERC user group. Advantages include a new purpose built main instrumentation laboratory, 3 sample preparation areas (one enriched, one natural abundance laboratory and one large sample grinding facility), direct access to a wealth of CEH and University scientific expertise in areas of related science, the CEH soil ecology section molecular preparation laboratories, access to the Lancaster Environmental Chemistry instrumentation & support staff (transferable gas chromatography/mass spectrometric techniques in atmospheric/pollution) and the Dept. of Biological sciences with which strong alliances have been maintained for the last 6-8 years. Building work for the forthcoming Lancaster relocation has is well underway and a completion date of 26th September 2003 has been targeted. The move should prove highly beneficial to the NERC facility and to its user community specifically with respect to the construction of the new purpose new laboratories and the potential to forge close working relations with the existing University departments. 2. The ^{15}N SIF have recently recognised that there is no facility in the UK providing isotopic analyses of $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ in nitrous oxide trace gas. Several environmental research groups in the UK have recently highlighted the urgent need for $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ isotopic measurements of N_2O as a means of sourcing nitrous oxide. The ^{15}N SIF has the capability of carrying out this determination on its trace gas pre-concentrator IRMS. The head of facility has recently formed a liaison with the worlds leading expert on nitrous oxide analysis; Dr. Tadashi Yoshinari at Wadsworth Centre, State University of New York. Dr. Yoshinari is currently calibrating our reference N_2O gas for $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$. 3. Rapid and improved sensitivity of CO_2 measurements. The predicted future increase in the number of CO_2 gas analyses entering the facility is cause for capacity concern. Current operating conditions allow one sample to be processed every 10 minutes. Future R & D is therefore required to modify the 'in-house' designed N_2 interface to allow improved specification and sample throughput for CO_2 analyses. R & D has revealed that it may be possible to analyse CO_2 using this technique provided that the N_2O and O_2 is completely removed from the system and dead space is reduced to prevent CO_2 peak broadening. R & D aims to focus on much narrower bore tubing and investigate chemical means of N_2O removal e.g. molecular sieves.

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Dr. N.B.W. Harris

8 July 2003

Mr David Lin
Science Programmes Directorate
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wilts SN2 1EU

Dear David,

NERC Isotope Geoscience Facilities: Annual Reports

On behalf of the Steering Committee I write to approve the annual reports from the facility managers of:

NERC Isotope Geoscience Laboratory (NIGL) at BGS;
NERC Isotope Community support Facility (ICSF) at SUERC;
NERC Argon Isotope Facility (AIF) SUERC; and
NERC Uranium Series Facility at the Open University (OUUSF)

Over the past 12 months all four facilities have continued to respond positively to the increasingly competitive scientific criteria imposed by the committee and we endorse the progress made in both the range and quality of science that they have undertaken. For 3 of the facilities, recent months have been dominated by the Review, the results of which, relative to previous reviews, I enclose. The committee was pleased to see upward movement by all 3 facilities, virtually across the board. It is interesting to note that the Review identified a marked increase in 'uniqueness', emphasizing that the skills and resources that are offered cannot be found elsewhere in the U.K. The most outstanding progress however, was made by NERC Isotope Geochemistry Laboratory increasing its average grade from 3.8 to 4.25. In my view this success reflects the sustained high level of work approved by the committee, the innovative science now being undertaken, the strong publication record and the effective management of the Facility by Prof. Parrish.

Yours sincerely,

Prof. N.B.W. Harris
Encl:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Niall Harris', written over the typed name and 'Encl:'.

**SRG 2003 Facility Review Scoring
(previous review in parentheses)**

	NEED	Uniqueness	Quality of service	Quality of science and training	Average
ICSF	4.0 (4.0)	5.0 (4.5)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
OU USF	4.0 (4.0)	4.5 (3.0)	4.5 (4.5)	4.5 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
NERC IGL	4.5 (4.4)	4.0 (3.4)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (3.6)	4.25 (3.8)
AIF	(4.5)	(5.0)	(4.0)	(5.0)	(4.63)

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE ARGON ISOTOPE FACILITY	FUNDING BLOCK	AGREEMENT F14/6/14	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1994	TERM 2002-2007
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The age of geological materials and the rates of geological processes are amongst the most fundamental questions in the Earth Sciences. The K-Ar clock is the *most widely applied radiometric-dating scheme*, and has been successfully applied to rocks less than 2 thousand years old to meteorites older than the age of the Earth. The Argon Isotope Facility (AIF), located at the Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre (SUERC), East Kilbride, Scotland, provides access for UK Earth Scientists to the one of the world's most comprehensive suite of geochronological argon and sample preparation facilities.

The AIF was *established in response to community demand*, and over the last 5 years has created and assembled a world class analytical facility capable of meeting this existing and projected future demand. The objectives have been *flexibility* (e.g., responding to active volcanic hazards) and *versatility* (offering the comprehensive suite of argon extraction methods). Earth Science problems throughout the entire NERC remit can be addressed; recent use has seen support for *Global Change* (c. 40%), *Natural Resource* (c. 25%), and *Environmental Risk* (c. 10%) ENRI's, along with other generic geochronological applications.

Training and Development

NERC proudly proclaims to "train the next generation of independent environmental scientists" (Annual Report 1999-2000). The AIF is in turn proud of its contribution to this process, and considers such training an important output of the facility. We believe that we also play a role in training and educating the supervisors of students and post-doctoral fellows, as well as other facility applicants, and in this way promulgate the immense potential and benefits, and emphasise the subtle restrictions, of dating with the ⁴⁰K-⁴⁰Ar decay scheme. Training starts at project inception and planning, is most concentrated during laboratory residence, extends to manuscript redaction and beyond, and is certainly more a cultural inculcation than a mere transfer of mechanical skill.

Scientific Focus

Whilst necessarily responsive to the user-base, both the demand and highest-rated science has focused on

- Quaternary and Holocene volcanic rocks (*climate change* and *natural hazards* applications)
- Tectonic provenance, especially those orogens with significant *climate change* implications
- Quantifying the volume flux and *climate* implications of the world's largest volcanic provinces
- High-precision time scale and other stratigraphic studies (applications throughout the Earth Sciences)
- Other generic, user-demanded geochronological studies

Scientific Review

A principal tenet of the AIF's mission is to ensure that *only the highest possible quality science is supported*. All projects requiring more than 1 week of facility resources are reviewed by the NERC Isotope Geosciences Facilities Steering Committee (NIGFSC); the current cut off for support is above $\alpha 3$. This review process includes all work for NERC-allocated PhD students and studies approved by NERC Standard Grants or other funding committees, and ensures that almost all projects have been through at least 2 stages of review. Small pilot projects requiring less than one week are conducted at the discretion of the facility Head and Manager. At least 50% of past pilot studies have led to later, *successful* full proposals, a robust verification of the Facility's pre-project assessment process.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review:		
Need 4.5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 4	Quality of Science & Training 5	Average 4.63

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 50%	Staff & Status	Next Review	Contract Ends
	Dr Malcolm S Pringle, Manager (RIII), 100%, FTC Dr Dan Barfod, PDRA, (RIA), 100% FTC Mr Andrew Tate, Senior Technician (E), 50% FTC	(January) 2006	(31 March) 02-07

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k 191	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k 5.1	Income £k n/a	Full cash cost £k 238.2			
	Unit 1 0.215 / half day unit	Unit 2	Unit 3						
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)									
2002-03	191	2003-04	196	2004-05	202	2005-06	208	2006-07	214

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NIGFSC	8	2	NIGL, ICSF, OUSF

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APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other academic								
Students								
Pilot								
TOTAL								

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years —1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic								
Students								
Pilot								
TOTAL								

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic								
Students								
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other
22	4	10	6	4	4					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other
22	4	10	6	4	4					

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
6	4	2	10	not applicable

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
6	4	2	10	not applicable

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
							10	7		3
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	100%									

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
							10	6		4
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	100%									

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

2002/2003 was an active year in terms of both personnel and laboratory development. Dr Dan Barfod, formerly of Imperial College and the SUERC U-Th/He laboratory, brought a wealth of noble gas analytical experience to his new position as the Facility PDRA (actually starting in Dec 2001). Dr Dirk Marheine, formerly of the Universities of Goettingen and Montpellier, brought a solid foundation in clay K-Ar and metamorphic Ar/Ar geochronology and finished a 6-month internship designed to significantly broaden his experience in the full range in modern Ar/Ar techniques. Unfortunately, the technician who had been an integral part of the AIF since the beginning of the 2nd funding cycle, Mr Brian Davidson, had to resign for personal reasons. For fiscal years 2002/2003 and 2003/2004, he has been replaced by Mr Andrew Tait, one of SURRC's most experienced technicians, especially well versed in mass

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spectrometer maintenance, computer hardware, and software development. The AIF is incredibly fortunate to be able to utilize Mr Tait's particular skills during what we view as a unique period of mass spectrometer development and extraction line automation. See the comments in the Forward Look below!

We have been tried to more systematically continue our goal of increasing the number of finished manuscripts from completed analytical projects while maintaining a healthy analytical effort on approved projects. A key purpose of this goal was to reduce the total number of projects active at any one time and thus increase the flexibility and responsiveness of the Facility towards future projects. During 2002/2003, this has evolved to about a 60/40 split between laboratory and manuscript/project development work, which seems a sustainable target. The laboratory effort is also split about 60/40 between mass spectrometer time and sample preparation.

With respect to getting manuscripts into the refereed literature, 7 papers were published in 2002, 6 manuscripts are in press (or already published in 2003), and 10 manuscripts are in review. Additionally, 3 PhD dissertations were successfully defended in 2002/2003.

With respect to the analytical program, work proceeded on 12 approved (average grade, $\alpha 3.6$), 4 pilot, and 5 infrastructure projects. This involved about 3200 analyses or about 200 analytical days on the 2 active SUERC argon mass spectrometers, about 76% of the total analytical capacity of the SUERC argon geochronology laboratory. We are maintaining a Facility analytical commitment of about 16 weeks, which we consider appropriate considering sample preparation requirements, reactor turn-around time, and mass spectrometer scheduling.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

- **Quaternary and Holocene volcanic rocks**

Over the last 10 years, advances in the application of Ar/Ar techniques to young volcanic rocks have led to a revolution in constraining when volcanoes have erupted, how fast magmas move through the crust, and the time scales of magma generation. This has practical applications in the assessment of *volcanic hazards* and the *climatic effects* of volcanic eruptions, as well as more theoretical applications to the rates and fluctuations of magma generation in the crust and mantle.

During 2001/02, we studied lavas from the Magadi region of southwestern Kenya, which lies within the centre of the East African Rift valley. This work has been undertaken in order to understand the growth rates of small, kilometre scale, normal faults over short geological timescales (~0.1-3.0 Ma), in an area where the faults can be examined directly by relatively inexpensive fieldwork rather than remotely with significantly more expensive seismic studies. The field area is dissected by a network of kilometre scale normal faults (some still microseismically active) that cut through volcanic trachyte and basalt flows. Lava flows that were erupted contemporaneously with fault movement were dated using Ar/Ar techniques, which achieved a precision of better than 2 k.y. (e.g., a stratigraphically important trachyte flow yielded an age of 359.1 ± 1.6 ka). This compares with, where such data even exist, 10-20 k.y. Precision available from previously published regional conventional K/Ar dates. Achieving such precision on these lavas has ensured a detailed understanding of fault growth, linkage and fault-tip propagation rates for six faults that have been very accurately surveyed in the field using differential GPS. For example, the above mentioned trachyte has an onlapping relationship to a number of preexisting fault blocks, but is cut into ledges 'attached' to the face of reactivated scarps representing a minimum 40 m of fault displacement, leading to a minimum fault displacement rate of 0.11 mm/yr.

- **Tectonic provenance, especially those orogens with significant *climate change* implications**

The use of single-grain age determinations from sedimentary sequences has developed into a powerful tool used to document major orogenic exhumation events and their timing relative to periods of major climate change. The approach builds on the stratigraphic research of teams of co-workers, and requires relatively large numbers of analyses, often on only very small grains.

Detrital minerals ages from the foreland sediments shed from a mountain belt can be used to constrain source region provenance, indicate the maximum age of sedimentation, and, when chronostratigraphic constraints are available, allow quantitative estimates of exhumation rates using simple thermal models. Single-crystal Ar/Ar ages of white mica are among the most cost-effective and robust chronometers of such processes. "Zero-age" micas (i.e., mica age = stratigraphic age) indicate periods of rapid exhumation (up to 5 mm/yr); longer lag times of 5 to 10 m.y. (i.e., mica age > stratigraphic age) imply exhumation rates ≤ 1 mm/yr. or sediment storage prior to final deposition. Much of the current effort has focussed, and will continue to focus, on Himalayan evolution, our effort to date are summarized in Figure 1 below.

The Balakot and overlying Murree Formations in Pakistan, and the Dagshai and overlying Kasauli Formations in India, represent the first significant clastic sediments from the Himalayan orogen preserved in the foreland basin. Limited paleontologic constraints and poor stratigraphic control restricts our ability to make quantitative estimates of exhumation rates during the deposition of these formations. From the 37 Ma (possibly 28 or even 24 Ma) micas in the Pakistan sediments (Najman et al., Nature, 2001) and the 28 Ma micas in the Indian sediments (Najman et al, Geology, 1997) we can only conclude that either 1) rapid exhumation was occurring by that time if the mica ages were to equal the respective stratigraphic age, or 2) the stratigraphic age of the sediments -- and the first arrival of significant clastic sedimentation to the foreland basin-- is significantly younger than the Ar/Ar ages.

We now have an extensive Ar/Ar data set for 3 sections for which good stratigraphic control is available: the Kamli Formation in Pakistan (c. 18 to 14 Ma), the Dharamsala and Siwalik Formations in NW India (c. 20 to 5 Ma), and the Siwalik in west Nepal (c. 10 to 1 Ma). A majority of the Kamli samples show lag times ≤ 1 m.y. from at least 17.4 to 14 Ma, implying exhumation rates of ca 4.5 mm/yr for some section of that part of the orogen (Najman et al., GSA Bull, in press). In contrast, the NW Indian sections studied show zero lag times from 20 to 17 Ma, but no evidence of such a signature thereafter (White et al., EPSL, 2002; Najman et al., Fall 2002 AGU abstract and this volume). A lack of zero-aged micas and increasing lag time up-section is also observed in the Nepalese Siwalik section.

Our results on the continental foreland are in contrast with previous studies on distal sediments in the Bengal Fan, which found

zero-age mica and K-feldspar throughout the recovered record. These studies were interpreted to imply a significant component of rapid exhumation somewhere in the portion of the orogen sampled by the Bengal Fan. The lack of granulite facies present in the Himalayas indicated that this rapid exhumation was both spatially and temporally variable. Our work highlights the use of proximal basin studies to identify such regions. However, neither our work nor other recent studies of modern day sediments have identified a zero-age component in the younger sediments. This suggests either that we have not yet identified such regions, or that the acknowledged analytical problems in the Bengal Fan studies were more significant than previously thought.

[Summary mica figure, mica age vs depositional age for each of the Pakistan, Indian, and Nepalese sections, will appear here??]

- **Quantifying the volume flux and *climate* implications of the world's largest volcanic provinces**

Studies of large igneous provinces (LIPS) range from *climatic* and oceanographic effects of continental and oceanic flood basalts, to evolution of mantle dynamics, to models of outer core convection driving the earth's magnetic dynamo. Using Ar/Ar geochronology to quantify absolute age and volume flux is arguably the most important advance in their study in the last 25 years. Our studies during 2002/2003 focused on the normally magnetized Ontong Java and Manihiki Plateaux, which represent the largest igneous province on Earth erupted over at least the last 250 m.y. Previously, the best Ar/Ar age for Ontong Java and Manihiki Plateaux was 122.4 $\pm$ 0.8 Ma (Mahoney et al, 1993). Recent work documents essentially synchronous, early Aptian global events just younger than Chron M0r, including significant changes in seawater Sr and C isotopic compositions, Ocean Anoxic Event 1a (a.k.a. the Selli black shale), and major plate reorganizations in the Pacific. Current time scales are tied to our Ar/Ar age for a reversal in the basement sequence at ODP Site 878 (MIT Guyot, western Pacific) and bio- and cyclo-stratigraphic arguments identifying this reversal as the top of Chron M1r. Based on these constraints, volcanism on the plateaux was complete at least 2 m.y. before the early Aptian events, thus could not have had a causal relationship.

However, our re-examination of C-isotope stratigraphy in the basalt limestones shows conclusively the biostratigraphic constraints were in error and that the dated reversal at MIT Guyot is actually the top of M0r. Thus, the base of the Aptian is now 125 rather than 121 Ma. Besides allowing synchronicity of the Ontong Java Plateau volcanism and global oceanographic events, such a revision would require important changes to the Cretaceous time scale (i.e.,).

Furthermore, our new Ar/Ar ages on basalt recovered at 4 new sites on the Ontong Java Plateau during ODP Leg 192, combined with new biostratigraphic constraints and a re-interpretation of the exiting Ar/Ar data, shows that the plateau was built over at least 10 m.y., from about 123 to 110 Ma. Combined with our previous results showing that the southern Kergulen Plateau in the Indian Ocean was built over at least 10 m.y., 119 to 109 Ma, the two largest flood basalt provinces of the last 250 Ma are now essentially synchronous with the major global oceanographic events observed in the Aptian. Also, as these two provinces were obviously not erupted in the relatively short periods predicted by either the classic plume head and incubating plume models, a significant revision in our understanding of the mantle dynamics of these extreme volcanic systems is now required.

- **Other generic, user-demanded geochronological studies**

U/Th-He promises to develop into an important low-temperature geochronometer. For example, U/Th-He ages of detrital zircon would provide an ideal lower-temperature chronometer to the Himalayan white mica Ar/Ar studies described above. The new AIF PDRA, Dr Dan Barford, has been instrumental in setting up the new U/Th-He dating laboratory at SURRC. In one of the first studies to come from this facility, Barford and Stuart (submitted) show that apatite (U-Th)/He data from vertical profiles near Ballachulish in the Scottish Highlands, constrain the age, magnitude and mechanisms of denudation associated with impingement of the Paleocene ancestral Icelandic plume beneath NW Britain. Helium ages of low elevation samples are coeval with emplacement of basaltic rocks of the British Tertiary igneous province providing a direct link between crustal denudation and plume-related magmatism. Modeling of the He age data indicates a relatively high early Tertiary paleogeothermal gradient (45-50°C/km), which translates to regional exhumation of ~1 km. This estimate is similar to the lowest estimates derived from other techniques and provides the best available estimate for onshore NW Britain. Significant age differences at given elevations across a pre-Tertiary fault suggest that reactivation of this and similar structures may have at least partially accommodated early Tertiary denudation.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

The AIF has been presented a time-limited, unique opportunity to make a significant advancement in an area which has long been a focus of AIF development: a simultaneous argon isotope multiple collection mass spectrometer (MCMS). Combining (1) Dr Pringle's previous experience with the world's only last generation MCMS at the USGS in Menlo Park, California (USA) and (2) a patent-pending improvement in very small signal amplification, a new British mass spectrometer company has designed a next generation, small volume and low blank MCMS. Such a new system promises at least a 3 to 5 times improvement in analytical precision for Quaternary applications, making Ar/Ar geochronology more precise than even ¹⁴C techniques down to 10,000 and perhaps even 1000 years old. Because of Dr. Pringle's assistance during the development process, SUERC was been offered the opportunity to purchase the first such mass spectrometer at a heavily discounted price, approximately half of the anticipated commercial cost. Funded by 50/50 contributions from internal SUERC resources and the NERC Scientific Service 2003/2004 Small Capital Program, the order for the mass spectrometer has been placed, construction is well underway, and we anticipate delivery in July 2003. Thus, 2003/2004 promised to be an exciting year of technique development.

ENGLISH HERITAGE

26 August 2003

Dr David Lynn
Director, Science and Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
SWINDON
Wiltshire SN2 1EU

Dear Dr Lynn

Re: Annual Report of the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARSF) FY 2002/2003.

As Chairman of the ARSF Steering Committee I have pleasure in enclosing the Annual Report for the financial year 2002/2003. The Committee reviewed the draft report at its last meeting on 14 May 2003 and the results of the discussions have been incorporated in this final draft.

During the year there have been a number of challenges and opportunities to which the Facility and its staff have responded well. A few of these are highlighted here:

1. User-demand increased by 19% as new users were attracted by developments in ARSF capabilities and renewed confidence in the improved data delivery timescales. This is an ongoing process and investigation of new data processing methodologies is being undertaken in collaboration with the Environment Agency. In particular looking at the use of their processing facility (using industry-standard commercial software on selected datasets), which would relieve the work-load on the CEH Data Processing staff and improve delivery time for appropriate data.
2. Increasing contribution to environmental science at a strategic level. This is illustrated by the demonstrated ability to support atmospheric research through better exploitation of the aircraft's capabilities and flexibility – for example, the deployments to the west coast of Ireland (NAMBLEX) and the commissioned campaign in the Netherlands (Baltic Bridge Cloud-II).

3. The SWIR campaign also exploited aircraft flexibility, supporting a collaborative ARSF /Belgian Science & Technology Research Institute/ITRES Research Ltd project. This was to test a demonstration prototype Short Wave Infra Red (SWIR) instrument, by acquiring comparative datasets over established BNSC Community Sites (SHAC 2000 Campaign).

4. There has been an increased interest by the archaeological community in evaluation and exploitation of spectrographic data for the discovery and monitoring of buried sites, two of which formed part of the SWIR campaign.

5. Interaction between ARSF and other S&F such as the Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (EPFS) has continued, which provides excellent support via ground instrumentation used by ARSF applicants and calibration of the ARSF's CASI instrument. There is further collaboration with both Section for Earth Observation at CEH and RSDAS in development of atmospheric correction algorithms for use with the ARSF data processing software, as well as improved, automated data processing and delivery.

Although there have been these positive developments there are still challenges ahead; in particular to obtain recognition by the Earth Observation Expert Group (EOEG) of the contribution that ARSF (and the other EO-related S&F) can make to the strategic aims of the EO Programme. The SWIR campaign is an example which would have benefited by EO support – the ARSF operational budget will probably not be able to support such opportunistic instrument demonstrations in the future.

Yours sincerely

Dr Robert H Bewley

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SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Airborne Remote Sensing Facility - ARSF	FUNDING /AGREEMENT Direct/via Swindon Office	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1982	TERM 5 yrs
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<p>TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:</p> <p>Airborne remote sensing and research is a key component of the quantitative remote sensing of the earth and is an essential contributor to the development and validation of Earth-system models, providing data in support of a wide range of interdisciplinary environmental research across the spectrum of the NERC remit and ENRIs. Such data are increasingly important for fundamental research into the natural environment and its inherent physical, biological and chemical processes. The ARSF offers a high-quality, cost-effective means of monitoring terrestrial, freshwater, marine and atmospheric environments at high temporal, spatial and spectral resolution.</p> <p>The flexibility and responsiveness of the current Facility is underpinned by its highly capable Dornier 228 research aircraft, with exceptional range, endurance and payload permitting the support of a wide range of science areas and applications.</p> <p>ARSF participation in the European Community research infrastructure programme "European Fleet for Airborne Research (EUFAR)" provides the potential for UK researchers to gain access to other European airborne research platforms and experimental instrumentation.</p> <p>Key advantages are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexibility and quick deployment on an opportunistic basis; - Provision of a fixed set of primary optical and digital remote sensing instruments; - Repeatability of observations at user-specified spatial, temporal and spectral resolutions; - Ability to mount additional new instruments on an opportunistic or thematic basis (eg SWIR Campaign, Sept 2002). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prime elements of the ARSF Mission are to underpin training, to promote good practice in the use of remotely sensed and other airborne data by the user community, and to promote the awareness, application and technology of airborne research techniques among the wider user-community. Lower α-grade projects, associated with training support, can be supported at minimal cost by acquiring data whilst en-route to higher-grade projects - In the optical remote sensing role, the ARSF provides the UK environmental research community with synoptic analogue and digital imagery of high spatial and spectral resolution on a repetitive basis at almost any desired temporal frequency. Data are acquired via a suite of reliable and well-characterised instruments. The ground-based data processing system is capable of delivering to users a variety of products ranging from radiometrically-calibrated data to fully geometrically-rectified images that allow direct comparison of multi-temporal surveys. - Additional roles include support for: marine remote sensing applications (as far as the continental shelf), atmospheric research (the aircraft is configured and certified to deploy a range of basic gas sampling equipment, particle measurement systems and scatterometers), and earth sciences (the aircraft is also capable of deploying geophysical instrumentation). Support for polar science is increasing (Svalbard Campaign 2003).
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SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)				(Date: January 2002)
Need 5	Uniqueness 4.5	Quality of Service 4.5	Quality of Science & Training 3	Average 4.25
(Low publication rates due to data delivery problems 1995-99)				

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 100%	Staff & Status	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March)
	Superintending Officer/Manager (B5) 70% established IDS/Processing Manager (B5) 30% established Systems Operator (B6)) Pilot (B5)) all 100% established Co-pilot (B6)) Science/Operations Co-ordinator (B6))	2007	2008

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY							
Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k @ 220 flight hrs pa				Capital Expend £k	Revenue £k	Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1 - Flight Hour						
558	3.802				15	70.99	836.44
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)							
2002/03	2003/04	2004/05	2005/06	2006/07	2007/08	TOTAL	
558	£558	£558	£558	£558	£558	£3348k	

STEERING COMMITTEE Airborne Remote Sensing Facility	Independent Members 7 (Chair Prof P Cross, UCL to Dec2002, succeeded by Dr R Bewley, EH)	Meetings per annum 2	Other S&F Overseen
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APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY – 2002/03)							<i>R* regraded as α 3 & 4</i>		
	α 5	α 4	α 3	α 2	α 1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject	Commercial
NERC Grant projects	0	3	3	0		0			
Other academic		6	9		1		7*	1	
Students		3	5				1*		
Pilot/Commercial									3
% Distribution		36%	51.5%		3%				9.5%

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average last 3 years – 99/00 to 01/02)									
	α 5	α 4	α 3	α 2	α 1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject	Commercial
NERC Grant projects	0.7	2.3	3.0	0.7	0.3	0	1.3	0.3	0
Other Academic	1	3.7	3.7	0.3	0	0	1.0	2.0	0
Students	0	1	1	1.3	0.7	0	0	0.7	0
Pilot/Commercial	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.0

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY – 2002/03)								
	α 5	α 4	α 3	α 2	α 1	β	Pilot/Comm	
NERC Grant projects		2						
Other Academic		4	7					
Students		2	2					
Pilot/Commercial							5	

USER PROFILE (current FY)					<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>					
Grand Total	Infrastructure				PAYG					
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
33	8	7	2	10	12					3

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)					<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>					
Grand Total	Infrastructure				PAYG					
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
27.7	6.7	5	4.3	12.7	6	0	0	0	0	0.7

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
20	10	0	7	3

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
15	9	0	5.3	0.7

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY – 2002/03)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
2	5	3	0	5	11	0	26	7	15	4

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
1	4	7	3	16	1	0

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
4.3	2.7	3.7	0	7	5.3	0	23.3	8.3	12.7	2.3

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
1.3	6.7	3.7	0	9	4	0

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR:

Demand for Support: 33 applications for ARSF support were received, α-graded and scheduled for flight in 2002/03. 87.5% of the applications were >α-3, compared with the 51% average for the previous 3 years. Six projects supported 7 PhD students. The Equipment Pool For Field Spectroscopy (EPFS) supported ARSF projects and 7 SWIR UK projects. Commissioned projects were those for VITO, BGS (Glasgow thermal survey), and a BBSRC agricultural project.

ARSF Workshop: The Biannual ARSF User Workshop was held at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory in December 2002, attended by an average of 60 people per day. Useful feedback from users was collected and implementation is in progress.

Publications: A total of 26 user publications for 2002 reflect the wide range of supported environmental science.

In-House Research: IHR concentrated on refinement of the Integrated Data System: improved data-processing techniques optimised throughput and product delivery. In partnership with CEH's Section for Earth Observation and the Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service (RSDAS), marine atmospheric correction algorithms are in the testing stage for CASE1 water. RSDAS also investigated potential techniques for streamlining data handling and processing. ARSF worked with EPFS staff during a flight over Thorney Island, Chichester Harbour to test SWIR stability and develop capability for in-flight calibration of the CASI using simultaneous spectral measurements on the ground. The EPFS also performed four laboratory calibrations of the CASI system.

The IDS is now complemented by an Applanix Airborne Position and Attitude system, delivered to the ARSF in March 2003. The system is operating in parallel with the IDS and experienced ARSF users have positively evaluated outputs. The Applanix will facilitate the integration of other instruments deployed by ARSF in the future.

Basic pressure/temperature/humidity sensors have been installed, and an arrangement with the School of the Environment, University of Leeds will provide access to basic particle-measurement equipment. Testing of a small probe particle counter is planned with UMIST.

Preliminary arrangements have been undertaken for the installation of the ULM LiDAR in the Do228, and evaluation is underway of resourcing required for data processing.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/ STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

New science areas that can be supported are:

- Atmospheric: provision of atmospheric measurements over urban areas and other smaller targets, and continuous aerosol sampling/profiling thus complementing the capabilities of larger atmospheric science platforms;
- Marine: extension of existing remote sensing applications to the continental shelf environment;
- Polar: deployment in support of glaciology and tundra/arctic vegetation studies.

The ARSF aims to achieve this in three ways by:

- Continuing improvement in data delivery, stimulating rising demand in such applications as: detection of environmental risks/hazards; seepage/pollution detection and mitigation; low-altitude atmospheric and pollution research over urban areas and routine collection of basic atmospheric parameters during transits; monitoring sea-surface temperatures and algal and suspended particulate matter; and detection and estimation of methane flux from wetlands.
- Providing tailored and integrated data packages to support 3D/4D modelling to address specific science issues on the regional and site-specific scale in the atmospheric, marine, terrestrial and freshwater sciences through deployment of specific instruments such as LIDAR, SAR, hyperspectral and geophysical sensors.
- Providing detailed, scientific validation of the broad-scale, satellite-based measurements used in global change research. Potential applications are in validation of sea-surface temperatures produced by the Advanced Along-Track Scanning Radiometer (AATSR), where the presumed high-accuracy is currently only partly supported via limited ship-borne validation data; and contribution to modelling of albedo as a function of illumination through characterisation of the Bi-directional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF).
- Supporting the development of new sensors to measure additional parameters that science now demands, in collaboration with instrument manufacturers and by contributing to the NERC EO Programme's "New Observing Techniques" and the BNSC "NEWTON" initiatives through development flying of prototype air- and space-borne instruments. European capability in multispectral thermal remote sensing is currently not highly-developed and there is potential for development of current or new instrumentation which would have research applications in the earth sciences, archaeology, vegetation studies and resources management; downstream commercial applications are in the fields of urban architecture, heat-loss studies and water management.

Hardware developments for support of the above aims include:

- Installing routine gas-sampling capabilities (inlets and storage bottles), and basic temperature/pressure/humidity sensors.
- Access to internal and external Particle-Measurement Systems (PMS) with DLR and Univ. Leeds.
- Access to LiDAR and development of capabilities in collaboration with the Unit for Landscape Modelling, Univ. Cambridge.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

TARGETS & MILESTONES: From 1-4 -2002 to 31-3-2003, aircraft & crew were on standby 119 days for 57 operational flying days and 191 operational flying hours. An additional 22 hrs was incurred in crew training, maintenance and transit flying.

Aircraft & crew utilisation (days):

Research HEI/Institute	Commercial	Standby	Standdown	Scheduled Maintenance. & Avionic Upgrades	Unsched Maint.	Total
52	5	119	78	111	0	365

Allocation of Capacity (nominally 220 hrs pa):

Science/Commissioned Research	Instrument Test/Development	Applications Development	Training/Maint/Transit	Total Hrs Flown/ % utilisation	Under-utilisation (weather)
137 hrs 62 %	29 hrs 13%	25hrs 12%	22 hrs 10 %	213 hrs 97%	7.0 3%

Allocation of Flying Effort by Sector

Science	Research & Development	Flight Crew Training/ Maint/Transits	Commission
112 hrs 51 %	54 hrs 25%	22 hrs 10 %	25 hrs 11%

Allocation of Effort by Project:

α Grading	5	4	3	2	1	Commission
Average Flight Time Hrs:min	0	4:45	2:20	2:00 (one project)	0	4:05

Integrated Data System: The AZ16 IDS flight hardware is ageing and deteriorating. ATM sensor performance during the latter part of the 2002 season was poor due to a displaced Pfund mirror, but this was repaired by Sensytech during the winter stand down. An update was commissioned in the IDS A/D boards in order to eliminate dropped scanlines and system noise.

SNAP Atmospheric campaign, Ireland: In August 2002, deployment to the west of Ireland totalled 16 flight hours including 6 sorties and transit. Leeds University researchers made ozone and CO₂ measurements and collected air samples for analysis between flights as well as deploying a particle measurement device. Simultaneous samples and measurements were made at Mace Head International Atmospheric Research Station, by 40 UK scientists from various Universities.

Short Wave Infra Red (SWIR) UK Campaign: The campaign was a collaborative project between ITRES Canada, NERC ARSF and VITO (Flemish Institute for Technology). The Facility deployed the new SWIR sensor in September 2002 for 10 days in the UK, in support of 15 UK projects, for a total of 14 hours flying – the primary sites being those flown in BNSC's 2000 SHAC Campaign, with the intention of providing a range of comparative datasets. Data delivery from ITRES is expected during the Spring 2003.

Svalbard Campaign. 10 applicants proposed projects following the AO in July 2002 for a deployment to Svalbard during the 2003 season. Campaign organisation is well under way, including the integration and operation of the ULM LiDAR, upon which most of the proposals hinge.

Web Pages: 60+ ARSF WebPages were designed and implemented on the Swindon web server. The new web site went live in July 2002 providing information and announcements to ARSF users and the wider public. Updates and additions are scheduled in the coming summer.

Operations: The Do228 aircraft has proved extremely reliable, with no unplanned maintenance in the course of the season. However, planned downtime was higher than usual due to the need for an 18-Year Inspection and the mandatory avionics upgrade detailed below.

- To meet mandatory EU airworthiness and safety requirements a new transponder, emergency locator beacon, and Traffic and Collision Avoidance System (TCAS) were installed.
- In October 2002, the ARSF Manager and Head Services & Facilities visited DLR in for exploratory discussions on future access to the Do228. An interim 2-year extension of the lease (to October 2005) was secured.
- In April 2002, Mr. Adam Edgar joined the ARSF as Co-pilot. In September 2002, Mr. Gary Osborn (Systems Operator) resigned and was replaced by Mr. David Davies on 4 November 2002.

Remote Sensing and Photogrammetry Society Conference: In order to increase the visibility of the Facility within the UK remote sensing scientific community, the ARSF provided leaflets and information at the Remote Sensing and Photogrammetry annual conference at DTI, London, 22 October 2002

International Airborne Remote Sensing Conference, Miami, 20-25/5/02: The Facility presented 1 poster on ARSF operational aspects and 2 posters were presented by Mr. Andrew Wilson on IDS and atmospheric correction algorithms derived from ARSF data.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED BY ARSF IN FY 2002/03 (Examples of key a4/5 projects):

(Right) Detecting and monitoring ground movement in the Durham and Northumberland coalfields using remote sensing. Richard Eyers and Jon Mills University of Newcastle upon Tyne Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) and Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) imagery acquired by the ARSF in 2002 and 2003 is being processed at the University of Newcastle to investigate surface disturbance above abandoned coalmines in the North East of England. This surface disturbance, which causes damage to roads and property in the region, has been linked to known geological faults. Spectral indicators of subsidence and fissuring include vegetation stress and soil moisture variations. Spectrographic data is complemented by multi-date digital photogrammetry, producing digital terrain models (DTM) from archive and recently acquired ARSF photography. These DTMs are used to investigate the topographic expression of subsidence and fissuring.

RGB 432 ATM data, acquired in July 2002 by the ARSF, draped over Ordnance Survey DEM. Fault lines from British Geological Survey mapping are overlaid.

(Left) Collection and Primary analysis of Data Obtained by Thermal Imaging (BGS Report CR/02/248)

In March 2002, the ARSF flew an airborne thermal survey over the Govan area of Glasgow for the Building Research Establishment and their client, the Scottish Energy Efficiency Office within the Scottish Executive. Using a corporate NERC approach, the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology processed the basic data to produce apparent radiant temperature images in the correct geographic position and the British Geological Survey analysed the data to extract an apparent heat loss value over each building using algorithms they have developed in previous thermal studies. After passing the results on to the client, the BGS then used the same thermal data to analyse the area's ground stability for an internal BGS project. Finally, the heat loss results from these collaborative studies were presented by the BGS at the Scottish Energy and Environment Conference in Glasgow on February 27th 2003. The organisations involved are now in discussions as to how to use the information that has been extracted from the data (see the attached image of evening temperatures over buildings in Govan).

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE BIGF	FUNDING	AGREEMENT	ESTABLISHED as S&F October 2002	TERM 2 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

BIGF serves as a single central collector and repository for UK GPS data and as the interface between the scientific community and the archive in qualifying and satisfying their demands for archive data to carry out research. In this role BIGF has links to over £1 million worth of infield data collection and communications hardware.

The fundamental value of BIGF is encapsulated in a secure archive of GPS RINEX data supplied to it by various methods from over 50 continuously observing GPS receivers (COGRs) sited throughout the United Kingdom, owned or co-owned by 11 organisations including Government agencies and others. Since being awarded the status of a NERC Facility, a further 3 COGRs have been established by existing suppliers to BIGF: 2 by the Ordnance Survey of Great Britain and 2 by the Met Office.

The archive currently comprises close to 190 site years of data, with some stations reaching back as far as 1996. The security of these irreplaceable data is guaranteed by NERC's continued funding enabling both hard disk storage and systematic back-ups made to CD and tape.

Demands on the archive are made by an online data request form. If the request is verified as non-commercial for scientific use, then the data are made available for secure transfer by ftp to the clients facilities.

Through BIGF the Institute has also offered advice on network design, observation and data processing strategies, based on our many years experience of GPS data processing.

These features are summarised by way of a four-part Facility remit:

- In the improvement of prior or current research.
- To provide an assured repository of resources when users bid for funding for new research, in which the costs of setting up and manning an ad hoc observation network are thereby eliminated, reducing the costs to NERC.
- To enable the time window of investigations to reach back in time as far as the extent of the archive, possibly reducing the forward time span of new data collection.
- To stimulate research across the spectrum of science by way of information and suggestion.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: N/A		
Need	Uniqueness	Quality of Service	Quality of Science & Training	Average

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 100 %	Staff & Status (* funding) Professor Alan Dodson : Director (*IESSG) Dr Richard Bingley : Deputy director (*IESSG) Dr David Baker : Manager (*NERC) Mr T Veneboer : Operator (*IESSG)	Next Review (January) 2004	Contract Ends (31 March) 2004
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k 33.0	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k 0	Income £k 0	Full cash cost £k 33.0
	Unit 1 £2.68 NERC £2.14 all users	Unit 2	Unit 3			
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2004-06	2006-07		

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
	7	1	1

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other academic								
Students								
Pilot								
TOTAL								
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		1 (NCL)						
Other Academic								
Students								
Pilot								
TOTAL								

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic								
Students								
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY) N/A										*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other			
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) N/A										*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other			

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
8 (inc. 1 NERC)	2	0	8 (inc. 1 NERC)	6 (including 4 BIGF collaborators)
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) N/A				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
			5		2		7	2	5	0
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
0	10	2	10	0	9	0				
OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years) N/A										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Archival

Continued to archive daily data from 54 COGRs. Static data holdings also exist for a further 4 COGRs. Ordnance Survey of Great Britain data up to 22/3/03 delivered to the archive on CD, and procedures established to transfer daily data files on a daily basis using ftp for data from 23/3/03.

Archive access

Online request form installed at the website to formalise and standardise applications for data, and to collect supporting information required by NERC. Access to hourly data established for Geodetic Observatory Pecny, from 14 stations.

Information

These data related information are provided to the potential and actual user:

1. Station log files.
2. Data listings by year and station.
3. Data QC summaries.

(2) and (3) are currently static extractions from the archive, scripts will be developed to automatically and frequently update this information.

Website development

The development of a dedicated website, templates and stylesheet, and BIGF logo, with a level of automation appropriate to the volume of usage expected. Access provided to an online data request form, station log files and data listings by year by station.

Start of investigations into the development of database driven indicators of the archives worth in terms of multiple usage and hence increasing value of each site day of data. This database to be responsible for all record keeping and reporting related to data existence and usage of the archive, including by-product reporting.

Marketing

Active marketing of the Facility, by way of informing the scientific community on the long term funding basis negotiated and developments enabled for BIGF, in order to reinforce awareness of the archive amongst prior and existing users. Furthermore to widen the potential user base across the complete spectrum of science. This initiative was enabled through the Institute's own and BIGF's website, press releases, announcements in journals, magazines and web forums, targeted mailing and display of materials at exhibitions. To reinforce the demonstrated utility of BIGF, information on projects and by-products related to BIGF data usage were sought for use and linkage on the website.

User activities

See the next section on science supported in FY (2002/3)

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Projects

- o ARSF calibration survey.
- o DML offshore survey
- o GPS / GIS integration.
- o Ionospheric scintillation effects on GPS measurements. (See Figure 1).
- o Near real-time tropospheric water vapour estimation.
- o Ocean tide loading (NERC alpha grade 4).
- o Photogrammetry versus LiDAR.
- o Post-glacial rebound and sea level.
- o Post-processed tropospheric zenith total delay and water vapour estimation (inc. PhD). (See Figure 2).
- o Vertical land movements and sea level. (See Figure 3).

PhDs

- o University of Leeds, Ionospheric Correction Models, current.
- o University of Newcastle, Ocean Tide Loading, current.
- o University of Newcastle, Ground movement in relation to mine water, current.
- o University of Newcastle, Vegetation monitoring through the use of satellite imagery, current.
- o University of Nottingham, Strategies for Long-term Tide Gauge Monitoring with GPS, current.
- o University of Nottingham, Near real-time tropospheric zenith total delay water vapour estimation, current.
- o University of Nottingham, Active station processing, current.
- o Hong Kong Polytechnic, Ionospheric studies, current.

Sample results from the use of BIGF data

Fig 1. Plot showing the correlation of observed phase scintillation recorded by a Novatel GSV400 scintillation monitor at Bergen (60°N), Norway, the change in total electron content for the Lerwick BIGF station (60°N) and the hourly standard deviation of the geomagnetic field at the British Geological Survey's Lerwick Observatory in November 2001. The increased ionospheric activity seen on the 5th and 6th was caused by a large geomagnetic storm. This research is aimed at gaining a better understanding of the effect of ionospheric scintillation on GPS. Results based on data for Lerwick BIGF station from November 2001 and provided by M Aquino, IESSG, University of Nottingham.

Fig 2. Map of integrated water vapour, computed using a network of BIGF stations in south-west Britain on a day of organised thunderstorm activity in July 2001. Maps are produced at different times of the day to form a series in which the evolution of IWV correlates with the development of the thunderstorm, demonstrating the utility of GPS in aiding weather forecasting. Results based on data from all BIGF stations and provided by S J Waugh, IESSG, University of Nottingham.

Fig 3. 3-D coordinate time series showing the north, east and vertical component movements of the Nottingham (IESSG) BIGF station. The horizontal components clearly show the north-east movement of the British Isles due to continental plate motion, while the vertical component shows both small long-term changes and seasonal variations in ground level. Results based on data for Nottingham (IESSG) BIGF station from 1997 to 2002 and provided by F N Teferle, IESSG, University of Nottingham.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

1. To continue to archive data from 54 plus any new stations, for example Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory have 6 planned.
2. To investigate the potential for archival links with Ordnance Survey of Ireland and Ordnance Survey of Northern Ireland, who together have 16 active stations.
3. The creation of automatically daily updated files at the website showing up-to-date information on data logged and data quality for each station in the network.
4. To disseminate comprehensive information as widely as possible at zero cost to the Facility, capitalising on any free marketing opportunities.
5. To develop a new client base by raising awareness of collaborative type research with the Institute providing products from data processing to third parties for further processing in either a common or their own specialist fields.
6. There is a University of Nottingham initiative to work with GRID technology, we need to consider how BIGF might fit in, perhaps as a test-bed.
7. Data are archived at data rates of 15 or 30 seconds depending on the source. It is foreseen that some clients may need higher data rates. We will research the use of interpolation software and provide advice on whether users can create 1Hz data from that archived at BIGF.
8. Organise a workshop for past, current and potential users of BIGF data. This would be aimed at gaining constructive feedback on experience of using the archive, discussing general and specific user needs and networking users to broaden the range of science.
9. To increase the general utility of the website by inclusion of useful utilities, for example GPS and geodesy tutorials/information packages, a guide to coordinate systems in Great Britain, and so on.

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15 July 2003

Dr David Lin
Director: Science & Innovation
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU

Dear David

I enclose the 6th BOSCOR Annual Report, which was first considered at the Steering Committee meeting on 12 June. A strong recommendation from our meeting is that BOSCOR should now be considered as a research facility (the British Ocean Sediment Core Research Facility) rather than simply a core repository. Over the past five years, and particularly over the last year, BOSCOR has acquired expertise and state-of-the-art logging equipment that greatly extends the range of studies of environmental change in the deep ocean. A fine example of recent results from the new XRF ITRAX corescanner can be seen on p 5 of the annual report. The high resolving power of this equipment opens up many new avenues in core research. The excellence of the work carried out on BOSCOR material is clear from recent papers in high-impact journals such as *Paleoceanography*, *Marine Geology*, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* and *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, which are listed on pp15, 16.

The work of the Southampton unit has received the enthusiastic endorsement of the Steering Committee.

Yours sincerely

EJW Jones

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE British Ocean Sediment Core Repository (BOSCOR)	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT SOC SLA	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1997	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

BOSCOR is the UK's national deep-sea core research facility and provides a unique and strategic service to the UK scientific community. It provides an advanced state-of-the-art non-destructive core logging and analysis capability that is unique in the UK. BOSCOR also provides specialised long-term core storage facilities, so that sediment cores collected by NERC ships, and NERC-funded researchers, can be kept under optimum conditions to ensure long-term preservation, and availability to the scientific community. BOSCOR promotes secondary multiple usage of the core material in its care ensuring cost-effective exploitation of an important national scientific resource. It is also responsible for long-term curation of core-based data relating to its holdings and from core-based national marine programmes in compliance with NERC data management policy.

The BOSCOR facility provides an essential service vital to the UK's contribution to the global science effort because:

- Sediment cores and samples are the fundamental data source for information on seabed character and global environmental change.
- Cores are very expensive to collect and the cores held by BOSCOR represent a considerable investment of many millions of pounds already spent by the UK in Earth Science research.
- Unless cores are stored under optimum conditions they can dry out and fracture within months, limiting their value for further research.
- As new measurement techniques become available and new concepts evolve, existing cores can be re-sampled to add to the knowledge base. Major developments in our understanding of recent environmental change (e.g. the North Atlantic Heinrich Layers, indicating repeated collapse of the North American ice-sheet during the late Quaternary glaciations) have come from material stored effectively in long-term core repositories.
- No other facility offers community use of equivalent advanced logging tools or sophisticated x-ray analytical facilities. There is no other national repository for storing deep-sea cores in the UK.

The BOSCOR core collection currently consists of 920 sediment cores, although data are held on 1428 sample stations. During the reporting period 106 cores (totalling 670 metres) were added to the collection (see Annex 12). BOSCOR's core holdings cover all the major world oceans and are recognised internationally as being of global importance. Currently the facility holds 5 km of core in total.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: January 2001		
Need 5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 5	Quality of Science & Training 4	Average 4.75

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 100%	Staff & Status Curator (B4) 40% established Assistant Curator (HSO) 50% established	Next Review (January) 2006	Contract Ends (31 March) 2007
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY

Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1 - Samples	Unit 2 - Metres logged	Unit 3			
65.59	0.077	0.063		174.62*	0	81.45

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)

2003-04	£ 99.50 k	2004-05	£ 102.5 k	2005-06	£ 105.6 k	2006-07	£ 108.8 k	2007-08	No alloc.
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* 154.62 k - non NERC Scientific Services funding, 20 k NERC Capital funding

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
BOSCOR SC	4 (Chair: Dr. John Jones, University College London)	1-2	None

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	International Users	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		1						
Other academic		6				1	3	
Students		2	6					
Pilot								
TOTAL		9	6			1	3	

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Average 2000/02 – user applications to BOSCOR not graded prior to FY 2000-01)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	International Users	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		3						
Other Academic		5						
Students		4	4					1
Pilot						4	2	
TOTAL		12	4			4	2	1

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)							
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot
NERC Grant projects	All BOSCOR sampling/logging requests made during the year were completed. Information on NERC Grant/academic project completion is not collected.						
Other Academic							
Students							
Pilot							

USER PROFILE (current FY)										*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
	Total	NERC	Total				NERC			
19	1	9	2	3	6					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
	Total	NERC	Total				NERC			
23	4	8	5	4	7					

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
8	3	0	8	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
11	4	0	8	0

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SB A	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
	34						34	21	11	2
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	85%									15%

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SB A	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
	31						31	14	13	4
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	90%									10%

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

During the reporting period, the BOSCOP facility has continued to be well used by internal and external users. During the year there has been extensive liaison with Cox Analytical Systems of Gothenburg, Sweden, on the specification, design and build of the new micro-XRF ITRAX corescanner being built by Cox. This has also involved liaison and consultation with XRF specialists in SOES, University of Southampton. This unique, innovative machine promises to provide BOSCOP users with access to state-of-the-art facilities for high-resolution downcore geochemical analysis and to unlock a wealth of new scientific information from the cores stored in the BOSCOP repository. The factory tests were carried out in the 1st week of March 2003 and were attended by the BOSCOP Curator and Dr I. Croudace of SOES, University of Southampton. Modifications requested by the Curator and Dr Croudace are to be carried out in March-April 2003 and delivery and installation is anticipated in May 2003. The purpose-built X-ray laboratory in the facility, originally built in anticipation of acquiring a CAT-SCAN system for three-dimensional core x-radiography, was fitted out during the year to accommodate the ITRAX corescanner. Core Store 2 of the extended core store has also been fitted out with racking and is now in use. Some building flaws were resolved during the year and others are currently being resolved. Funds are being sought for a second scanner capable of 2-D element mapping.

During the reporting period, 10 researchers from 5 institutions (including 1 researcher from overseas) sampled BOSCOP cores taking a total of 2596 individual samples (a record number of samples distributed). Some of these individuals were multiple users during the reporting period and in total, 32 separate sampling sessions were recorded. In addition, 5 users used BOSCOP's multi-sensor core logger (MSCL) to log cores with a combined length of 62 m. Four other researchers from three UK universities moved cores, recently collected through their own research programmes, to the BOSCOP core store for long-term storage (under BOSCOP's conditions for ultimate community access) and in anticipation of sampling in the Spring of 2003. BOSCOP staff were also consulted by a number of other scientists (including researchers based overseas) on a number of core-related issues and for data requests.

A comparison of BOSCOP usage with previous reporting years is provided below:

Although the EUROCORE Concerted Action (an EU-funded project to set up a central-access searchable Internet database of cores held by European institutions co-ordinated by BOSCOP) came to an end in October 2001, an extension was granted for preparation and submission of the Final Report due to other partner's seagoing commitments. The Final Report was submitted during the Reporting Year (May 2002) and accepted by the European Commission. A successor proposal was submitted as an Accompanying Measure in April 2002. This proposal, called MARSEDEX, proposed data management assistance by BOSCOP to core repositories in the EU New Accession States of Eastern Europe and the Newly Independent States of the former Soviet Union, and promote access to their substantial seafloor sample archives through adding metadata on their holdings to the Eu-SEASED database. This proposal was positively evaluated and placed top of the 'reserve list'. It will be resubmitted in 2003 as an Accompanying Measure under a Framework Programme 6 call expected in July 2003.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

During the year 2002, 34 publications (including 21 in refereed literature) were either wholly or partly engendered by the BOSCOR facility (these papers are listed in Annex 6). This figure is likely to be a minimum figure as under-reporting is likely. All these publications were in the Earth Science area (assuming that marine geology is included in the Earth Science field) and included papers related to environmental and natural resource issues encompassed in the NERC mission, specifically environmental risks and hazards, global change, natural resource management, and pollution and waste. A number of other publications are currently "in press".

Some scientific highlights of research using BOSCOR cores and/or facilities are:

- Researchers have used a BOSCOR core (LC21) to study long-term variability in deep water ventilation during the late glacial and Holocene in the eastern Mediterranean. This study suggests that isolation of intermediate/deep water preceded the start of sapropel formation by up to 1.5 kyr. This research has provided a possible explanation for the previously major unresolved problem in sapropel studies, namely the source of nutrient supply required for export productivity to reach levels needed for sustained sapropel deposition. This study suggests that nutrients accumulating in stagnant Aegean Sea basins for 1-1.5 kyr were utilised in the deposition of the S1 sapropel. Pelagic long piston cores in the Mediterranean taken during *Marion Dufresne* Cruise 81 held in BOSCOR now form internationally-recognised reference cores for the Mediterranean Late Quaternary and Holocene succession. A number of studies of core LC21 have now been published (Cashford, J.S.L., et al., *Paleoceanography*, 17, 14.1-14.12).
- Researchers have used BOSCOR cores to study in detail the turbidite depositional architecture of the Moroccan turbidite system on the north-west African margin. This sedimentary system, covering three interconnected deep-sea basins, forms one of the longest turbidite systems in the world. Excellent control provided by BOSCOR cores has allowed individual turbidites to be correlated in all three basins and confirmed that the three largest turbidites on the most distal basin (the Madeira Abyssal Plain) were deposited during major fluctuations in sealevel, suggesting a link between volume of sediment input and magnitude of sea-level change (Wynn R.B., et al., *Sedimentology*, 49, 669-695).
- Researchers have used a BOSCOR core from the Sicily Strait in the Mediterranean Sea (LC07) to improve the presently restricted global geomagnetic palaeointensity dataset for the late Matuyama Chron which is essential for evaluating the long-term behaviour of the Earth's geomagnetic field. The data provided by core LC07 are unprecedented from the Mediterranean basin where only a palaeointensity record for the last 80 kyr was available previously. This research demonstrates the global importance of some of the cores held in the BOSCOR repository (Dinares-Turell, J., et al., *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 194, 327-341).

Above: Fe, Ca, Sr profiles downcore through interbedded turbidites and pelagites from the Balearic Abyssal Plain showing high Fe and low Ca in the turbidites and low Fe and high Ca and Sr in the pelagic intervals. Effects of bioturbation in the upper parts of turbidites are clearly seen. These data obtained using the new BOSCOR ITRAX Corescanner shows that it can be a powerful stratigraphic tool for determining genetic units. The line of measurement is shown in red on the core picture.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Recent expansion of the core store provides sufficient refrigerated storage for future core acquisition for at least 10 years. Funds previously secured to acquire a digital x-radiography system for community use have been used to recently acquire an innovative high-resolution XRF analyser, specifically designed for logging of split sediment cores. This machine is a unique instrument and has been built in collaboration between BOSCOR and Cox Analytical Systems of Gothenburg, Sweden. Funds are being sought to acquire a second machine specifically developed for high-resolution 2-D elemental mapping for community use and it is planned to replace the currently 10 year old GEOTEK multi-sensor core logger in the medium term.

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Synchrotron Radiation Source	FUNDING SLA	AGREEMENT PAYG	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1996	TERM Annual
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The Synchrotron Radiation Source (SRS) at the Daresbury Laboratory (DL) is part of the Council for the Central Laboratory of the Research Councils (CCLRC). Users from UK universities carry out a wide diversity of projects covering all of the scientific and technological disciplines. Synchrotron radiation, because of its 'unique' properties (intensity, continuous energy profile ('white radiation'), tunability, low divergence, polarization, ability to be focussed) is ideal for carrying out element-specific X-ray absorption spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, fluorescence lifetime, VUV, and infrared spectroscopy experiments. All types of natural materials (biological and abiological), both crystalline and amorphous (inorganic, organic, biogenic), as well as solutions and gases, can be studied and their long and/or short range structural relations, or biological properties, can be analyzed and/or imaged.

NERC users have access to the experimental beamlines and support/infrastructure facilities *via* grant funding ('tickets' awarded by PRCs) and direct access (*via* a 'Service Level Agreement'). Direct access provides a fast and efficient way for researchers to undertake innovative or small-scale studies prior to submitting normal grant proposals; history shows that many of the world-class projects became established *via* this route. This access mode is particularly important for research student training. DL is a centre for multi-technique and interdisciplinary research and this interactive working environment has benefited the wide range of research programmes being carried out by all NERC-supported users.

At the SRS, natural environment researchers are provided with facilities to study a range of fundamental and applied problems which fall in two main areas: Molecular Environmental Science (MES); and Mineral Physics and High Pressure Petrology. In the first, the aim is to study the fundamental processes controlling the geochemical and biological influences on element cycling between the crust, hydrosphere, biosphere and atmosphere at a molecular level. In the second, the aim is to obtain a better fundamental understanding of the relationships between physical properties and atomic structure, and of the mineral stabilities and equations of state for minerals in the deep crust and mantle.

NERC community users receive the full support of DL including advice on experiment design, and training on experimental stations and data reduction. Formal training courses are recommended for all new users. Hostel/hotel and subsistence are provided for the periods of experiments, and travel expenses are also covered for the research team. A two-day annual user meeting is held in September and a specialist user meeting in the spring. Two-page user research papers are published in the DL annual report which is circulated to all SRS users and to government agencies, libraries, and synchrotron laboratories worldwide (4000 copies circulated).

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review:		
Need 5.0	Uniqueness 4.5	Quality of Service 5.0	Quality of Science & Training 5.0	Average 4.88

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F < 1.5 %	Staff & Status Dr F. Bahrami, Environmental Science Liaison Officer (ESLO)	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March)
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY								
Recurrent Allocation £k 80	Unit Cost £ 10090k			Capital Expend £k N/A	Income £k N/A	Full cash cost £k		
	Unit 1 √	Unit 2	Unit 3					
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)								
2002-03	£58k Beamtime £22k ESLO	2003-04	£37k minifocus £26.56k ESLO	2004-05	£26.56k ESLO	2004-06	£26.56k ESLO	2006-07
STEERING COMMITTEE NISSC	Independent Members SEVEN environmental scientists including Chairman Prof. A. Putnis, Univ of Munster, Germany.			Meetings per annum TWO		Other S&F Overseen ISIS Neutron Allocation		

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4+$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		2						
Other academic		9	3				1	1
Students		6						
Pilot								
TOTAL								

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4+$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		4						
Other Academic		7.6	4				0.3	2
Students		6	1					0.3
Pilot								
TOTAL								

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4+$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects		1						
Other Academic		14	4					
Students		10	1					
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other			
25						16	6	5	2	1			

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other			
33						18.5	7.66	5.83	4.67	0.33			

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
10	6		6	1

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
16.5	7.3		8	

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
1	18	5					28	13	11	4

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
8.3%	66.6%	8.3%		16.6%		

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
1.2	17.4	3.10		0.86			23.93	15.2	5.6	2.52

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
3.7%	73.2%	10.76%		12.2%		

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Despite many changes occurring throughout the year (SRS being shutdown for upgrading 55% of the FY, restructuring of the lab and changing over to a new access/funding mechanism), NERC research has continued to diversify and flourish within Daresbury Laboratory.

May 15-16th, 2002 an interdisciplinary meeting on 'Understanding Microbial/Mineralogical Soil Interactions on a Molecular Scale' was held at Daresbury Laboratory. This meeting was co-sponsored by CCLRC and NERC whereby 25 biological, mineralogical and geochemical researchers from 10 university departments, 2 NERC research institutes, and Daresbury Laboratory came together to explore cross-disciplinary research in soil systems. Interactions in soil systems was chosen as a theme as it is highly diverse and falls strongly within NERC's remit. A particular aim was to assess the possible application of synchrotron radiation techniques in this research area. It came to our attention that establishing a soils molecular research theme at this point may be too ambitious due to the extreme heterogeneity of the 'real' system. It was proposed to first establish how the different components of soils interact within the extremes of composition, pH, temperature etc., followed by fundamental cross-disciplinary bio-geochemical studies of mixed mineral/biological systems under controlled conditions. Whilst NERC is the obvious lead research council, we concluded that the work is undoubtedly cross-research-council and the theme seems ideal for wider consideration by the newly established RCUK.

September 17-22nd, 2003 a workshop was held at Daresbury Laboratory entitled: Arsenic speciation in environmental samples. Three NERC research groups (Arsenic speciation in earthworms from contaminated soils. Dr Caroline Langdon, Soil Science, Univ. of Reading; Arsenic in mine tailings and weathering products. Dr Karen Hudson-Edwards, Birkbeck College; Arsenic speciation in Fe-rich environmental samples. Drs M. Cave, B. Klinck, B. Palumbo, British Geological Survey, NERC.), were targeted and offered 2 days of beamtime on station 16.5 to collect and analyse their own EXAFS data. This was a unique opportunity to provide hands-on experience to new users and to raise the scientific profile of the SRS.

The number of NERC related applications received in November 2002 was 3 times higher than the previous year. This most likely resulted from the activities the ESLO arranged throughout the year, in particular the Soil Sciences workshop in May 2002, as well as the Arsenic Workshop held on station 16.5 in September.

ENVIROSYNC. This programme, supported by NERC and Daresbury Laboratory, was aimed at assessing the types of facilities for the new synchrotron DIAMOND which would be of optimum use in environmental research. Forty-three scientists including 12 CCLRC staff members directly participated in experiments that were part sponsored by the Envirosynch project. They have all learned lessons relevant to experimental design and provision on Diamond. It is hoped that the knowledge base acquired will enable the environmental science community to fully benefit from the possibilities offered by the new source.

The knowledge gained has been important in preparing supporting cases for environmental science research or beamlines proposed for diamond. Thus the community provided key input to the case for the approved beamlines BL1 (extreme conditions), BL13 (microfocus spectroscopy), BL14 (X-PEEM), BLC (core XAFS) and to those considered for year 3 BL 027 (ultra-dilute XAFS), BL032 (IR microspectroscopy) and BL03 (JEEP).

Overall the project has been extremely cost effective and successful.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03): (See Annex 1 for more detail).

1. Characterisation of the biochemically mediated silicification: SR-FTIR chemical imaging of cyanobacteria from birth to necrosis. Liane Benning, University of Leeds, Earth Sciences.
2. of Ba (as an Ra analogue) with oxide and carbonate surfaces. Francis Livens, University of Manchester, Chemistry.
3. Rescheduled from 8.1 to 7.1, formerly 36095: The structural environment of rare earth elements in garnet solid solutions: An XAFS study. J.D. Blundy, Bristol University, Earth Sciences.
4. Volumes of hydrous phases measured at elevated pressures and temperatures using energy-dispersive and angle-dispersive multi-anvil techniques. Alison Pawley, University of Manchester, Earth Sciences.
5. An ED-XRD study of the formation of secondary minerals during the sulphation and reoxidation of iron (hydr)oxides. Liane Benning, University of Leeds, Earth Sciences.
6. Pigment identification of the contents of a 19th century paint box. G. Martin, Victoria and Albert Museum.
7. Crystal Chemistry of Vanadium Associated with Iron Oxide Hydroxides and Clay Minerals. D.M. Sherman, Bristol University, Earth Sciences.
8. Microbially mediated release of arsenic from Bengali Sediments: EXAFS Determination of Active Solid Phase Arsenic Speciation. Dave Polya, University of Manchester, Earth Sciences.
9. Equation of state of serpentine minerals measured using energy-dispersive and angle-dispersive multi-anvil techniques. Alison Pawley, University of Manchester, Earth Sciences.
10. Cadmium mobility in the soil environment. E.H. Bailey, Nottingham University, Environmental Sciences.
11. Sea Surface Temperatures from Coral Skeletons: Developing Mg/Ca as a Geochemical Proxy. A. Finch, St Andrews University, Geography and GeoSciences.
12. Arsenic Speciation in Environmental Samples. Daresbury Laboratory workshop.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Over the next few years DI will continue to provide research facilities to service two main areas of natural environment research: Molecular Environmental Science (MES) and Mineral Physics and High Pressure Petrology. Recent high-profile, NERC-supported work has included Earth, environmental and biological sciences research

As well as using the well established beamlines NERC-researchers will take increasing advantage of ongoing new developments:

- monochromatic beam for 'on-line', multi-anvil 'Walker cell' (16.4) (NERC JREI grant). User facility. 2003.
- time-resolved studies using energy dispersive XAFS (ED-XAFS) (station 9.3),
- dynamic powder diffraction station on 6W.2 for rapid kinetic measurements (1 sec) with high *d*-spacing resolution at controlled T and P. Building underway, user facility 2003.

- further new facilities being planned for the SRS include development of miniprobes for XAS and XRD, and an upgrade to the soft X-ray facilities (new helical undulator on beamline 5U).
- Mini-Focus XAS on station 9.2 partly funded by grant from NERC: 30 μm probe which will enhance studies of toxic metal distribution in heterogeneous environmental samples.
- Mini-Focus XRD on station 9.1: for high pressure mineral physics and geophysical studies in diamond anvil cells.
- mid-IR microprobe (spot size 5 microns), beamline 11.1, available end 2003. We plan to provide opportunities and training for the use of synchrotron radiation FTIR microscopy in the study of organic soil contaminants.
- Circular Dichroism on station 12, protein crystallography on the new station 10 and SAXS on station 2.1 will provide NERC protein biologists an array of complementary techniques to investigate the structure and function of their particular proteins.
- New helical undulator on station 5U.1 will enhance studies of magnetic minerals with the potential of developing X-PEEM imaging of valency states in environmental materials.

The new synchrotron DIAMOND is currently being designed and will be built at RAL. The first set of beamlines will be available in early 2007 and will include several of importance to the NERC remit: high P/T facilities with hydrothermal and diamond anvil cells; micro-XAS and X-PEEM (chemical state imaging in heterogeneous samples); SAXS/WAXS (colloid formation and ageing studies). The NERC community is playing an important role in recommending priorities for DIAMOND and via the NERC/DL ENVIROSYNC initiative has visited leading 3rd generation sources to assess the types of facilities which would be of optimum use in environmental (*sensu lato*) research. The NERC-supported SR research programme and the new initiatives both depend on some baseline support from NSS. Central facilities will continue to play a crucial role in supporting inter-research-council, state-of-the-art interdisciplinary research. NERC research students, in particular, benefit from working in this interdisciplinary environment during which they undergo a unique training experience.

A major aim is to encourage expansion and evolution of the NERC-supported SR programme at DL so that an active and mature community will be able to transfer their forefront research work to DIAMOND with as little hiatus as possible.

The bid to finance the design and development studies for the Fourth Generation Light Source (4GLS) prototype (£11.5M awarded) was successful and work has already begun. One of the key scientific areas that would greatly benefit from this technology is the Environmental Life Sciences therefore it is essential for NERC to be involved in the development of 4GLS early on.

Following the recent Quinquennial Review (<http://www.qgr.cclrc.ac.uk/Activity/ACTIVITY=Facilities>), the CCLRC is responsible for the peer review and scheduling of proposals requesting access to the ISIS, SRS and CLF large scale facilities. The CCLRC has developed the QQR recommendation of a common facility access scheme for the facilities, which are "free at the point of access" to the NERC academic research community.

For future allocation periods, new SRS peer review panels (Facility Access Panels FAPs) are being set up which reflect the internal organisation within SR Department of the portfolio of 30 SRS stations. For SRS there will be 4 FAPs, each dealing with all of the applications for a given SRS station:

FAP name	Stations
Biology & Medicine	2.1, (9.5), 9.6, 10.1, 11.1, 12.1, 13.1, 14.1, 14.2
Physics	1.1, 3.1, 3.2, (3.3), 4.1, 4.2, 5U.1, 5D, 6.1, 9.4
Materials & Engineering	2.3, 6.2, (7.6), 16.1, (16.2), 16.3, 16.4
Structural and Environmental Chemistry	3.4, 7.1, 9.1, 9.2, 9.3, 9.8, 13.3, 16.5

Note that stations in brackets are unsupported.

Under the common access arrangements there are 4 modes of access – Direct, Programme, Rapid & Service.

- **Direct Access** – all Direct Access proposals will be peer reviewed by the Facility Access Panels (FAP) and will be scheduled subject to ranking and station availability. Proposals demonstrating funding support from other Research Councils will be flagged to the panel and grant abstracts made available.
- **Programme Access** – in recognition of the needs of those users with funded major research programmes, CCLRC facilities will operate programme mode access where appropriate and where recommended by the panels. Those who wish to apply under this access are required to prepare a detailed scientific case of up to 6 pages including an indication of their beam time requirements over the duration of the programme (up to a maximum of 3 years, in 6 monthly blocks) and indicating the resources they have available to complete the programme.

The Facility Access Panels will peer review applications for Programme Access and will assess the appropriateness of this type of access for the proposed scientific programme. In future proposal rounds, successful programme access applicants are required to submit a proposal of up to 1½ pages including a summary of their progress so far and outlining the experimental programme to be carried out in the new allocation round. This will enable the FAP to recommend a balanced scientific programme for each station.

It is envisaged that programme mode time on the CCLRC facilities will be capped, but this is likely to vary depending on facility and research programme area.

- **Rapid Access** – for those applications which are urgent (e.g. sample dependent, high priority science) a rapid access mechanism will be made available. Applications will be received by the facility and considered by appropriate members of the Facility Access Panel for peer review via e-mail. If the proposal is deemed appropriate for rapid access, it will be scheduled as soon as feasible by the facility. There are no deadlines for applying under Rapid Access mode. At SRS not more than 5% of the overall beam time will be made available for Rapid Access.
- **Service Access** – Currently SRS operates Service Mode Access for Protein Crystallography only. Please contact Pierre Rizkallah p.i.rizkallah@dl.ac.uk for further information.

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Dr Andrew Kaye,
Secretary SRG,
Natural Environment Research Council,
Polaris House,
North Star Avenue,
Swindon SN2 1EU

Our reference: T/CGC/NARSCS

9 January 2004

Dear Dr Kaye,

Re: Annual Report of the Chilbolton Radar Facility

Please find the Annual Report for the Chilbolton Radar Facility. This report has been reviewed and approved by the NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee.

Yours sincerely,

Professor C. G. Collier
Chair, NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Chilbolton Meteorological Radar Facility (CMRF)	FUNDING Pay-As-You-Go	AGREEMENT CLRC SLA	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1996	TERM None
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The Chilbolton Facility is the UK's premier ground-based atmospheric remote sensing facility. It is also a leading radio science research laboratory. The combination of measurement capabilities required to address these two disciplines has established Chilbolton as a centre of expertise that is internationally respected. The facility is owned by the Council for the Central Laboratory of the Research Councils (CCLRC) and is operated by the Radio Communications Research Unit (RCRU). The Facility includes a fully steerable 25 metre antenna usable at frequencies up to 30 GHz, a 500 metre range, and a comprehensively instrumented satellite ground station 8km SE at Sparsholt.

Most of the instruments have been designed and built by CCLRC staff. Many of these instruments are only available because of the synergy between the needs of researchers in the radiowave propagation and atmospheric science/climate research communities, and the facility is also a nucleus around which instruments are brought together from other sources. The major instruments are:

- 3 GHz Chilbolton Advanced Meteorological Radar (CAMRa)
- UV Raman lidar
- Micro and millimetre wave radiometers
- Meteorological Instrumentation
- Distrometers
- 94 GHz cloud radar (Galileo) (on long term loan from ESTEC)
- IR lidar cellometer (on long term loan from ESTEC)
- Visible & IR Radiometers
- Millimetre wave terrestrial radio links
- Specialised rain gauges

Recognising the multi-disciplinary attributes of the facility, it is now operated under the umbrella of the Chilbolton Facility Consortium (CFC), which includes NERC, EPSRC and the Radiocommunications Agency (RA), as well as CCLRC. NERC does not fund the activity through Services and Facilities but it has been kept within the S and F grouping to give access to the capital fund. The terrestrial radio links are the only instrument NERC users would not have a primary interest in.

The NERC atmospheric science, hydrology and Earth Observation communities use Chilbolton to conduct research in weather, flooding and climate. Weather science often involves observations of phenomena operating below the current resolution of models and work on their effective parameterisation in models. Climate science may involve use of continuous cloud radar observations to evaluate climate model cloud climatologies.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: Jan 2001	
Need 3.5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 3	Quality of Science & Training 4.5	Average 4

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 0 %	Staff & Status 9 person years drawn from approximately 16 CCLRC staff. All permanent.	Next Review (January) Not applicable	Contract Ends (31 March) Not applicable
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k 0	Unit Cost £k/day			Capital Expend £k 93.7	Income £k 600	Full cash cost £k 86.7
	3 GHz Radar 2.88	94 GHz Radar 0.096				

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2003-04	756*	2004-05	839*	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08

*This is funded by the NERC, EPSRC, Radiocommunications Agency consortium and is not finalised.

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NARFSC	4	1	MSTRF

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03) ESTIMATE FOR DRAFT								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		3					1	
Other academic	1	1					1	
Students	1	6	3				3	
Pilot								
TOTAL	2	10	3				5	
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	0.67	2.00	0.33					
Other Academic	0.33	1.33	0.33					
Students		0.66						
Pilot								
TOTAL	1.00	4.00	0.66					

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		3					1	
Other Academic	1	3					1	
Students	1	6	3				3	
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
22						4	11	3	1	6

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
10.33						2.67	4.67	4.00		3.00

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic 10	Centre/Survey 1	NERC Fellows	PhD 11	Commercial
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic 4.33	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD 3.66	Commercial

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS 10	TFS	EO 3	Polar	Grand Total 1515	Refereed 57	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc 6	PhD Theses 2
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	19		2	1
OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS 12.3	TFS	EO 2.00	Polar	Grand Total 14.33	Refereed 5.33	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc 8.00	PhD Theses
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	5.67		2.00	

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Instruments

- A major refurbishment of the focus cabin on the 25 metre antenna (funded by NERC JIF) took place between July and November 2003. The entire framework and cladding was replaced, providing a suitably waterproof environment for the 3 GHz radar front-end electronic equipment.
- The 94 GHz radar did not operate during the year. The original 6 month period for the delivery of a new klystron amplifier was extended a further 5 months due to an additional fault with the associated modulator. The amplifier and modulator were shipped back to the UK, from the US, on 12 March 2003. (The instrument is now working well).
- The UV Raman lidar has been developed to the point where water vapour profiles can be reliably retrieved during daylight hours, as well as at night. Profiling has taken place on an event basis throughout the year.
- The IR Lidar has performed reliably and there has been continuous monitoring of cloud structure throughout the year.
- Monitoring of integrated water vapour and liquid water using radiometers during the past year has been subject to interruptions caused by temperature related radiometer instability.
- A figure summarising the performance of each instrument over the year is available in the appendix.

Users

- There has been a major emphasis on data quality and dissemination. A data strategy was completed in December 2002 which set a policy for quality control of all the data streams. Quality control on over 50 % of the data streams was completed by the end of the year.
- Four Users meetings have been held at Chilbolton during the year. These allowed detailed discussion of instrument-related issues, while updates on research were presented through short talks.
- A new user of the facility from Birmingham University has had a small NERC grant funded to use the Chilbolton 3 GHz radar.
- Colleagues in Space Science RAL had a NERC grant funded for spectrometer observations at Chilbolton and this instrument is now at the site.

Management

Significant changes in organisation and management of the facility were made during the year with the signing of the Chilbolton Consortium agreement in October. The Consortium has met twice and impacted on all parts of the operation including staffing, finance, monitoring of outputs and data quality.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Characterizing drizzle in stratocumulus (E. O'Connor, A. Illingworth (Reading))

It is difficult to forecast the formation and break-up of stratocumulus decks and improvements in model parameterisations would be welcome. New observations at Chilbolton are contributing to research on the problem. Two years of continuous radar and lidar observations indicate that stratocumulus is present 26% of the time and that about 30% contain drizzle. A technique that uses a combination of Doppler radar and lidar observations to estimate the microphysical properties of drizzle has been developed. The algorithm estimates drizzle parameters such as liquid water content, liquid water flux and vertical air velocity, and fits the drizzle size spectrum to a gamma function. The recycling time of liquid water through the drizzle process can also be estimated.

Observations of coherent boundary layer motions (W. Tian, D. Parker, S. Mobbs, M. Hill (Leeds), C. Kilburn, D. Ladd (RAL))

Fine pressure variations in the atmosphere have been observed with 3 microbarographs installed at the Chilbolton Observatory to complement the radar observations. The resulting high frequency, high resolution pressure time series have been used to extract roll information and to infer roll emergence. Although pressure time series only are not enough to describe roll circulations, they provide supplementary information on roll characteristics such as phase speed and drifting direction. A new approach using a beamsteering diagram to discriminate rolls from gravity waves and turbulent eddies has been tested with a numerical model and an observational case and proved to be useful.

Numerical model parametrization of ice microphysics and the impact of evaporative cooling on frontal dynamics (R Forbes (Reading))

The parametrization of microphysical processes in the atmosphere is a vital part of Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models at mesoscale resolution, not only for the prediction of cloud and precipitation but also for the impact on the dynamics through diabatic heating and cooling. One aspect that has had relatively little attention is the role of evaporative cooling in the development of mid-latitude fronts. Evaporation of ice particles falling into sub-saturated air beneath a layer of frontal cloud drives a narrow slantwise downdraught of similar magnitude to the frontal updraught. Deficiencies in the representation of the evaporation zone in an NWP model were identified by comparison with a one year time series of vertically pointing cloud radar data. These deficiencies can lead to a bias in the dynamics of fronts affecting the spatial distribution of wind, cloud and surface precipitation. Errors in the model representation of the frontal evaporation zone are reduced by modifying parameters in the microphysical parametrization, potentially leading to improved model forecasts of mid-latitude frontal cyclones.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Instruments

Two new radars will come on stream this year as construction is nearing completion and the radars work in test mode. The radars are a 1275 MHz radar for clear air and turbulence measurements and a 35 GHz radar for cloud measurements. The 35 GHz system will be named Copernicus and the 1275 MHz ACROBAT (Advanced Clear-air Radar for Observing the Boundary-layer and Troposphere). A further development nearing completion is a cradle to allow tilting of the 94 GHz radar.

The second main area of emphasis over the year will be routine delivery of quality controlled data to the British Atmospheric Data Centre in NetCDF, a common data format. This will involve completion of the introduction of data quality control procedures detailed in the data strategy for all the Chilbolton data streams. At the same time, development is required of the BADC web entry point for BADC users to reflect the increase from the original 3 data streams to around 10 times that number. Consolidation of RCRU web services are planned for both new users and UK colleagues closely involved in day-to-day development work at Chilbolton. The various RCRU web sites, the real-time data showcase website and the BADC web site all need to be integrated from the viewpoint of data users.

Funding and Management

Attention should continue to be placed upon efforts to unify the activities of the 4 different committees covering NERC activities at Chilbolton into a coherent whole. For reference these are the Chilbolton Consortium, the NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee, the UFAM* Utilization Committee and the NERC - CCLRC Service Level Agreement meeting. There are two areas which will affect the arrangements: firstly a decision will need to be made this year about the funding from 2005 and whether funding should continue from NCAS (NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science) or whether an application should be made NERC Services and Facilities.

Secondly, with the two new UFAM radars on stream in 2003/4, project management and peer review activities between UFAM staff and Chilbolton staff need to be properly co-ordinated.

A major review of staff at the Chilbolton Observatory is to be carried out in 2003/4 by the Chilbolton Consortium. Three senior figures from the NERC, EPSRC and Radiocommunications communities will be asked to carry out a skills and expertise audit to establish the realistic staff numbers required to deliver the agreed programme. The baseline for comparison will be the year 2002-2003. Staff costs and the extent and depth of the programme of work are issues for the Chilbolton Facility Consortium and are not covered by this review.

A name change is also planned this year to the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFAAR). This better represents the function of the site.

*University Facilities for Atmospheric Measurement

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

INTER-AGENCY COMMITTEE ON MARINE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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THG/1.1

1 December 2003

Dr David Lynn
Director, Science & Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
SWINDON SN2 1EU

Dear David

Annual Report of Dundee Satellite Receiving Station 2002/2003

Please find enclosed the report for 2002/2003 which was considered at the meeting of the Steering Committee held in London on 9 June 2003. The Committee continues to be very pleased with the sustained high quality of the service provided.

I would like to draw attention to a couple of aspects of the Annual Report and Forward Look.

- 1) There has been an increase in the number of peer-reviewed papers for the year which is mainly due to the greater number of SeaWiFS-related papers which have been published.

The Steering Committee noted with considerable concern the issue of access to SeaWiFS data. Until now this has been provided through a NASA contract with ORBIMAGE, but the contract ends in December 2003 and is unlikely to be renewed. NASA had advised users to contact ORBIMAGE directly regarding access beyond December 2003.

There was general agreement on the need for continued access to SeaWiFS, at least until there is an established MODIS ocean colour service. The Committee agreed that DSRS/RSDAS should continue negotiations with ORBIMAGE to establish the terms for future access. As a member of the UK Delegation I also raised this issue at the IOC (Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission) Assembly in June 2003 and found wide support from other Member States. As a result, the IOC Executive Secretary has been instructed to raise this matter with NASA.

- 2) All old data archived on magnetic tape has now been successfully copied to CD-ROM, ensuring long-term security of the archive.

David Lynn

1 December 2003

Page 2

Annual Report of Dundee Satellite Receiving Station

- 3) Agreement in principal has been reached with DLR, Germany regarding exchange of MODIS data to effectively extend the coverage of each facility. This was discussed at length by the Committee. On the suggestion that users could obtain data from the appropriate site rather than archive the same data at both sites, the feeling was that it would be preferable to have all data available to NERC users archived at DSRS. We are satisfied that the agreement only applies to MODIS data, so there are no issues in relation to SeaWiFS licensing.

The Committee was in favour of the arrangement, but agreed it should be checked against NERC data policy. Given the potential for UK and other users to access DSRS acquired data via DLR, the situation should be monitored to ensure DSRS is not disadvantaged, eg when demonstrating value for money in terms of scientific output in future reviews. These points were to be checked by Swindon Office, Dr Parkes and Mr Lonie.

With regards

Trevor Guymer
Chair DSRS Steering Committee

enclosure

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS)	FUNDING BLOCK	AGREEMENT F14/G6/04/01	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1981	TERM 5 Yrs
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

DSRS provides UK researchers and other potential users with access to remotely sensed data from several polar orbiting, Earth observation satellites and advice and support in the use of data. The data are used in most areas of environmental science - marine, atmospheric and terrestrial scientists comprise the majority of the user base. Information derived from the data is used to provide a greater understanding of Earth's environmental processes. The facility supports NERC strategy by providing infrastructure to make important environmental observations, which support research and training in various component areas of Earth system science.

Data are collected from the NOAA satellite series carrying AVHRR instruments (1978-present) and OrbView-2 satellite carrying the SeaWiFS ocean colour instrument (1997-present). These satellites transmit direct broadcast data in the S-band frequency range.

Following a major NERC funded upgrade to receive transmissions in the X-band frequency range, DSRS has also been routinely receiving MODIS data from the Terra satellite (April 2000-present). Terra is the first of NASA's Earth Observing System satellite series and MODIS extends upon the capabilities of AVHRR and SeaWiFS by providing many more spectral channels, increased radiometric resolution and improved spatial resolution for some channels. DSRS was the first facility in the UK and one of the first in Europe to receive direct broadcast MODIS data.

The Station's primary function is to support the NERC community, although data are also available to anyone on a commercial basis. Non-NERC users include overseas researchers, government agencies, commercial companies and private individuals. Data distribution is mainly via the Internet and occasionally on computer media or in the form of hard copy imagery. Users have access to recent data sets in near real-time, while requests for archive data are generally processed within 1-2 days.

A key activity is provision of data to the NERC Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service (RSDAS) at PML, which provides value added products for the scientific community (marine scientists in particular), without the need for further processing. These products are mainly derived from DSRS data. An important feature of the partnership with RSDAS is rapid turn round of data from reception at Dundee to delivery of processed imagery to environmental scientists in the field, particularly those onboard NERC research vessels. All new AVHRR, SeaWiFS and MODIS data received at Dundee is immediately transferred to RSDAS, where processed products are generated and made available to users in near-real time. This is important in the planning of research cruises and crucial during a cruise, when imagery is used to guide vessels to maximise success and cost effectiveness. Older archive data are delivered to RSDAS in response to specific user requests.

The DSRS archive is a valuable resource for environmental research and currently comprises over 62,000 recordings extending back almost 25 years. Many of these are unique and long-term management and maintenance of the archive is therefore important. Data acquired between 1978-97 were originally recorded on magnetic tape and vulnerable because of tape degradation. A major task over the past few years has been to secure these data by copying to CD-ROM. Two copies of all data sets were made for added security, with one held at Dundee to support user requests and the other stored at the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre in fireproof safes - this policy continues for all new data.

Part of NERC's mission is engaging society in the environmental sciences. DSRS contributes by providing the general public with Web-based open access to satellite image archives and information. User registrations and access statistics clearly demonstrate extensive worldwide interest in the site and feedback indicates that public and educational facilities are highly regarded.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: January 2002	
Need 5.0	Uniqueness 4.5	Quality of Service 5.0	Quality of Science & Training 5.0	Average 4.88

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F (Balance funded by UO Dundee through DSRS Director's post and reduced overheads costs from 46% to 25% of salaries.) 78%	Staff & Status		Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March)
	Director (UO Dundee funded)	30%		
	Manager (Other Related Grade 3)	100%		
	2 Software Specialists (ALC Grade 2)	100%		
	Clerical Assistant (Clerical Grade D)	100%		
	4 Technicians (Technical Grade C)	100%	2007	2008

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k £ 277.22k	Unit Cost £k Per Station Operator Hour (Annual capacity 5333 hours) £ 0.071k		Capital Expend £k £ 80.09k	Income £k £ 6.76k	Full cash cost £k £ 377.01k				
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement) * Figs. agreed in principal for renewed agreement									
2002-03	£277.22k	2003-04	£288.53	2004-05	*£284.02	2004-06	*£288.72	2006-07	*£291.99

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
DSRSSC	6	1	RSDAS, NEODC

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	-	7	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other academic	1	14	8	-	-	-	-	-
Students	-	1	3	-	-	-	-	-
Pilot	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	1	22	11	-	-	-	-	-

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years - 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	2.00	5.33	2.33	-	-	-	-	-
Other Academic	-	11.33	9.67	-	-	-	-	-
Students	1.00	3.00	5.00	-	-	-	-	-
Pilot	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	3.00	19.67	17.00	-	-	-	-	-

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	-	7	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Academic	1	14	8	-	-	-	-	-
Students	-	1	3	-	-	-	-	-
Pilot	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

USER PROFILE (current FY)

NOTE: Although the number of PAYG Commercial users is greater than Infrastructure funded users (NERC and HEI), effort associated with servicing Commercial user requests is relatively small, e.g. for 2002/03, 95% of user request work was associated with NERC and HEI users. *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic

Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		
98	5	14	8	13	16	-	-	-	-	50

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic

Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		
129.00	11.00	8.00	2.67	13.00	25.67	-	-	-	-	68.67

USER PROFILE (current FY)

Academic 27	Centre/Survey 15	NERC Fellows 0	PhD 6	Commercial 50
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USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)

Academic 36.33	Centre/Survey 14.33	NERC Fellows 2.33	PhD 4.67	Commercial 68.67
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OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)

Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0	3	48	6	4	22	5	88	44	40	4

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
0	4	31	5	4	14	5

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)

Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0.00	2.00	30.67	5.33	7.00	11.67	2.67	59.33	27.00	30.33	2.00

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
0.00	5.67	33.00	8.00	7.33	20.33	6.00

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Progress for the year with the three main operational activities is summarised below:

- **Routine data acquisition/archiving:** 7231 NOAA/ SeaWiFS/Terra recordings, 99.46 % success rate
- **Processing user requests:** Requests from 98 users, no backlogs, 95 % of this activity for NERC & UK HEI users
- **Magnetic tape archive transcription:** Approx. 2500 AVHRR and 2200 CZCS archive recordings transcribed – details below

DSRS was included in a major SRIF funded building refurbishment costing a total of £142,500. The Satellite Receiving Station was refurbished and the Space Systems Research Group was moved to the floor below the Station bringing all the satellite related activities together. The work environment was improved and health, safety and security issues were addressed. Operational improvements were achieved by relocating equipment and re-routing, renewing and upgrading much of the cabling associated with the computer network, UPS power and antennas etc. Network hardware was also upgraded. This has led to a much improved and neater layout, which allows staff to undertake tasks and monitor systems more easily. Normal operations were maintained throughout.

Transcription of the final AVHRR archive recordings from tape to CD-ROM was completed. The Nimbus-7 CZCS archive was the only remaining tape based data and was also transcribed. More than 35,000 recordings in total have been transcribed over a 6-year period, ensuring long-term security of the archive. Completing this activity made it possible to begin receiving all available passes from the NOAA, Orbview-2 and Terra satellites. Data reception has increased significantly in recent years with a typical daily schedule now comprising 21 passes.

Near real-time transfer of MODIS Level 0 data to RSDAS commenced in June 2002. The EC CLOUDMAP2 project (coordinated by UCL) has been supported throughout the year by near real-time production of MODIS Level 2 cloud products at RSDAS. Funding from CLOUDMAP2 is supporting the development of a MODIS marine service at RSDAS, which will be needed to replace the SeaWiFS service. Agreement, in principal, has been reached with DLR, Germany for exchange of MODIS data with DSRS, which will extend the geographical coverage of each facility. Development work is ongoing to support this data exchange.

The overall success rate for Terra was high at 98.67% despite various problems, each unrelated, which resulted in the loss of a significant number of Terra passes. The lower success rate for Terra reception compared to NOAA and SeaWiFS S-band reception highlights the benefit of the improved availability provided by additional antennas.

Other activities included increasing disk space for online data, consolidating functions of older systems to one computer which also reduced maintenance support costs, replacement of photo facsimile receivers with inkjet printers for photo quality prints and construction of a data ingest computer for new X-band receivers. Software developments saw improved AVHRR image geolocation, MODIS upgrades for data ingest and processing and installation of Level 2 cloud product packages. Web site image browsing has improved with links added from images to related pages, e.g. previous/next pass, other sensor channels from the same pass and passes from other sensors on the same date. The main database of satellite recordings and auxiliary databases were merged for improved performance, computers were upgraded with security patches and email routed via NERC servers for virus checking/spam filtering.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

RSDAS used DSRS data for near real-time support of 17 research cruises. The partnership ensures support for marine projects, but distribution illustrates support for most science areas. The projects also map to all NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues:

Biodiversity	Environmental risks & hazards	Global change	Natural resource management	Pollution & Waste
5	17	30	24	12

The breakdown of projects by funding mode is 3 Thematic, 12 Non-Thematic and 13 Core Strategic. Thematic projects were associated with UTLS OZONE and URGENT. Core Strategic programmes at BAS, PML, SOC, POL and SAMS were supported.

Titles of the highest rated projects for the year are listed below – each was graded Alpha 4 or 5 by the DSRS Steering Committee.

- Orographic triggering of land-based tropical convection
- CORAL: Convection Observations with Radar and Lidar
- Dynamics and Chemistry of Frontal Zones II
- Potential use of medium resolution satellite data for detection and monitoring of oil spill events at sea (SADAMOS)
- CONVECTION: Greenland Sea convection mechanisms and their climatic implications
- Development of algorithms for processing ocean colour imagery from European coastal waters
- Monitoring the Atlantic Inflow toward the Arctic (MAIA)
- Emplacement of lava flow fields and tube systems at Etna volcano: satellite insights
- Faroes-Iceland-Scotland Hydrographic and Environmental Survey (FISHES)
- Spatial and temporal distribution of suspended sediments in the Southern North Sea
- Multi-sensor imaging of ocean organic films and sea surface slicks
- Study of coastal processes in the North Sea by combined analysis of satellite imagery from ERS-2 SAR, AVHRR and SeaWiFS
- SAMS Northern Seas Programme
- Effects of zooplankton gradients in fronts on the foraging and migration behaviour of basking sharks
- Inherent optical properties of marine particle suspensions and influence on Case II R.S. reflectance
- Irish Sea suspended sediment dynamics: testing ideas against satellite observations
- Biophysical interactions and controls on export production (BICEP): FerryBox
- Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory Coastal-Ocean Modelling System (POLCOMS) development
- Novel observation of frontal exchange and recirculation (NOFEAR)
- Relating satellite imagery to seawater composition in Case II shelf seas
- Physical-biological control of new production within the seasonal thermocline
- Evaluation of ISAR radiometer in the Western English Channel, Bay of Biscay and Celtic Sea area
- First deterministic sea-wave prediction (DSWP) system for moving ship and fixed site applications

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

DSRS will support current NOAA and NASA-EOS programmes which will continue over the next few years. The aim is also to enhance the infrastructure for future satellite missions planned under joint NOAA, NASA and EUMETSAT programmes and to provide support for small/micro satellites that are expected to become more prevalent in future. To achieve this, additional reception systems with S and X band capability are needed and they must be easily configurable for a wider range of satellites. With these systems, it will also be possible to receive from other EO satellites planned by ESA and commercial and national operators.

There are two permanent antennas on the Dental School for routine operations – a 2.4 m S-band antenna for NOAA/SeaWiFS and the new 2.8 m X-band antenna for MODIS, which replaced an old S-band system. A low cost 1.2 m antenna was also installed temporarily to maintain NOAA/SeaWiFS reception until the 2.8 m was modified for dual X/S band reception, but dual mode is no longer possible/desirable for several reasons. Additional permanently installed antennas are needed at another site for existing schedules, to improve availability and to support future missions. The University Tower Building is an ideal site for two antennas and relevant permissions have been obtained. Two new antennas will be installed on the Tower, a 1.8 m S-band and a 2.8 m X-band to address current and future needs. Significant progress is expected in this area over the coming year.

Dr Parkes was awarded NERC capital funding of £136k over the period 2001-2004 for R & D effort to implement a versatile digital receiver. The receiver will be capable of dual mode X/S-band reception and is needed to replace existing equipment reaching end of life and improve reliability. It is also intended to be easily configurable to receive from a wider range of satellites. The existing antennas use fixed frequency downconverters to interface the satellite signals to receivers. A synthesised downconverter is being developed which will provide versatility for multiple satellites and receivers. This will be controlled remotely via Ethernet.

General Developments

- Following successful implementation of a low cost RAID server for online storage of all quicklook browse imagery, a NERC capital allocation of £17.39k has been secured to fund additional servers for online storage of the entire AVHRR, SeaWiFS and CZCS archives of full resolution data, for immediate user access via the Internet.
- Cloud detection techniques are being developed so that once the new RAID servers are operational, cloud extent in every AVHRR scene can be determined to ease image searching with an option for percentage cloud cover. The MODIS cloudmask product will be used to provide a similar search facility for MODIS data.
- The existing antenna control PCs are older class machines nearing end of life and need to be replaced. Several suitable PCs have been provided by the University and will be configured and kept on the shelf for instant replacement in case of failures. Linux will replace Windows as the operating system on the new PCs to facilitate remote monitoring and management.
- Two factors are preventing routine reception of MODIS data from Aqua. Firstly, Aqua and Terra are simultaneously overhead for most daytime passes, so only one can be tracked with the single X-band antenna available at present. The new antennas will overcome this. The second and more serious problem is that Aqua direct broadcast is interrupted while recorded data for a complete orbit is transmitted to a NASA groundstation in Svalbard. There is a significant overlap in coverage between DSRS and Svalbard, so direct broadcast is not available while Aqua is over much of the DSRS area. This is a problem for all northern, high latitude stations. Aqua direct broadcast data will be received where possible. Receiving part of the Svalbard high-speed data dumps will also be investigated, but current DSRS antennas and receiving systems are unlikely to have the required performance.
- The Web site provides registered users with free access to global coverage, geostationary satellite images received via Meteosat. The images generate much of the public interest in the site and some academic and student projects also make use of them. The Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) system is due to become operational by the end of 2003. DSRS intends to provide reception capability for MSG HRIT data to maintain equivalent facilities to those available at present. Due to a spacecraft problem, data dissemination plans are under review. DSRS plans are on hold until the situation is clearer. HRIT will include all available bands from the 12-channel SEVIRI instrument at full resolution.
- Other future satellites of possible interest include UK Disaster Monitoring Constellation (DMC) microsatellite, ESA Global Precipitation Mission (EGPM) an Earth Explorer mission, and Fuego, which is a possible Earth Watch mission currently being studied.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

Routine data acquisition: Satellite recording equipment was used each day throughout the year. There was no significant downtime.				
Satellite	Successful Recordings	Recordings Lost	Success Rate	Data Acquisition
NOAA	4044	7	99.83 %	290 Gbytes (approx.)
SeaWiFS	892	1	99.89 %	60 Gbytes (approx.)
Terra	2295	31	98.67 %	2250 Gbytes (approx.)

Distribution of service capacity between the three main operational tasks:		
Satellite Recording/Archiving etc. 20%	User Requests 45%	AVHRR Archive Copying to CD-ROM 35%

Web Statistics: NERC Science Communication Activities are supported by providing anyone with free access to information and non-scientific products through the Web site, e.g. reduced resolution browse imagery. Information below relates to these facilities rather than the high-resolution data services available to scientific users.			
Total registered users 161,341	Registrations for the year 29,253	Requests/site hits for the year Approx. 23 million	Image requests for the year Approx. 13 million
Breakdown of registrations by user categories:			
Personal interest 65 %	NERC/UK HEI Project 14 %	Education 10 %	Research 6 %
			Commercial 2 %

Dr David Lin
Director, Science and Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
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Swindon
SN2 1EU

1 July, 2003

Dear Dr Lin,

2002-2003 Annual Report of the NERC Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy

I write as retiring Chairman of the EPFS Steering Committee, to support submission of the EPFS Annual Report for 2002-2003.

During the review period, EPFS has implemented a strategy that has successfully continued or put in motion:

- Strengthening the community,
- New instruments, measurement techniques and applications,
- Supporting airborne and spaceborne EO - in a European context,
- Fostering collaboration and partnerships between scientists, hardware companies and commercial groups.

As an example of introducing new ideas in new wavelength regions, EPFS is establishing a collaborative arrangement with the Molecular Spectroscopy Unit at RAL in order to develop applications in the thermal infrared.

EPFS has ably demonstrated that it continues to be a key facility, across many areas of NERC environmental research as well as for the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility in particular - confirmed through achieving a commendably high 4.88 score from the recent SRG review. This is a clear endorsement of the strategic approach undertaken by EPFS over the past two years, implemented through a minimum level of staffing. However, the degree of future growth and achievement beyond the successful 'status quo' will of course be dependent on resourcing levels.

I conclude by wishing EPFS (and indeed all the Services and Facilities) every success in the future.

Yours sincerely

A D LAMB (Mr)

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (EPFS)	FUNDING Block	AGEEMENT Contract	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1988	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The NERC Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (EPFS) is a unique world class facility supporting Earth System Science. It comprises a pool of high quality field spectroradiometers, operating over the optical wavelengths, with associated calibration and support equipment. The facility is based at the Department of Geography at the University of Southampton and is currently operated by 4 expert staff, all employed by the University (1.5 RA FTE plus 0.4 Tech FTE). The EPFS is distinctive because it focuses on techniques to make accurate measurements of the spectral properties of objects *in the natural environment*, and such data are essential to underpin quantitative EO from aircraft and satellite systems. Traditional laboratory-based spectroscopy cannot capture the complexity of natural targets such as plant canopies, and does not reproduce the illumination conditions under which airborne and satellite sensors operate. Field spectroscopy plays a central role in the application of quantitative Earth observation (EO) to key scientific issues such as global climate change, pollution monitoring and biodiversity assessment. The EPFS also performs a vital strategic function in underpinning the use of data from airborne sensors and the calibration of such sensors, especially those flown by the NERC ARSF. The Pool also provides a significant level of training for postgraduate students and other researchers new to quantitative remote sensing.

Over the last fifteen years EPFS has become the national centre for field spectroscopy and it has an international reputation founded upon EPFS support for international EO experiments and collaboration, especially with other European research groups. Access to EPFS resources is available free of charge to the UK research community, subject to expert peer review by the EPFS Steering Committee (SC). An average of 30 applications are received each year and the total requested spectroradiometer loan time exceeds available capacity by approximately 10-20%. The science supported by the facility is high quality and diverse. It includes papers published in international journals with exceptionally high impact factors such as *Nature* (e.g. Mumby *et al.*, 2001) as well as many papers in more specialised and influential EO journals such as *Remote Sensing of Environment* (e.g. Curran *et al.*, 2001). Since 1994, research supported by EPFS has led to over 260 scientific publications, including more than 80 papers in international refereed journals, 30 book chapters, in excess of 120 conference papers and at least 35 PhD theses. Support is provided across NERC Thematic and Non-Thematic programmes, with NERC grants and studentships accounting for 75% of loans in terms of annual cost allocation (average for April 1999-March 2002 period). The breakdown of current EPFS support in terms of grades reveals that over 80% of support, in terms of cost allocation, is allocated to projects graded alpha-4 or higher.

The service provided by EPFS is regarded extremely highly, both by users and by independent reviewers. The programme of instrument loans is managed very efficiently so as to maximise the availability of spectroradiometers to the user community. Special efforts are made to support community research programmes, as for example with the NERC/Itres SWIR campaign in 2002. The EPFS website (<http://www.soton.ac.uk/~epfs>) provides a comprehensive resource for users and the wider community. Training is an important aspect of EPFS work. On average, 15 projects are supported each year for post-graduate PhD research. Since 1999 over 10 NERC Research Studentships have benefited from spectroradiometer loans and EPFS input, usually multiple loans extending over a two-year period. On average the Pool attracts 17 new users each year. Training is usually performed on a one-to-one basis, although the EPFS hosted a two-day meeting on Field Spectroscopy in April 2002, one day of which was dedicated as a training workshop.

In order to maintain and expand the capability of the facility to meet the strategic and scientific objectives of NERC, the facility has developed its own Strategic Plan. This involves leading the scientific community through setting the agenda in field spectroscopy research, developing collaborative links with Europe, identifying new opportunities for field spectroscopy, evaluating tools and techniques, seeking greater synergy with airborne- and satellite-borne instruments and raising its profile internationally.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: January 2003	
Need 5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 5	Quality of Science & Training 4.5	Average 4.88

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 100%	Staff & Status 1 x Pool Manager (0.4) 1 x Post-Doctoral Research Fellow (0.6) 1x Electronics Technician (0.4) 1x Post-Graduate Research Assistant (0.5)	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March) 2004
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k £89,150	Unit Cost £k						Capital Expend £k £12,000	Income £k £11,460	Full cash cost £k £169,980
	Unit 1 ASD FS Pro £248	Unit 2 GER3700 £224	Unit 3 GER1500 DB £210	Unit 4 GER1500 SB £105	Unit 5 Cimel £95	Unit 6 Microtops £50			
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement) (2004 onwards estimated beyond current contract)									
2002-03	£ 89,150	2003-04	£ 92,943	2004-05	£ 121,000	2005-06	£ 134,000	2006-07	£ 130,000

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
EPFSSC	3	1	none

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	3	9	1					
Other academic		4	8				2	1
Students (NERC)		5 (3)	1					
Pilot								
TOTAL	3	18	10	0	0	0	2	1

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1	3						
Other Academic		6	8	3			1	1
Students	1	2	2	1				
Pilot								
TOTAL	2	11	10	4	0	0	1	1

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects**	2		6					
Other Academic			8	1				
Students (NERC)			6 (3)	5 (1)				
Pilot								
In-house	2							
Commercial (a4)			1					

**projects in support of NERC Grant and as well as PhD student research appear in the NERC Grant category (includes 2 projects)

USER PROFILE (current FY)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
31	8	11	4	4 (2 in-house)	8					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
30	6	12	5	5 (3 in-house)	7					

USER PROFILE (current FY)					
Academic	11	Centre/Survey	3	NERC Fellows	0
				PhD	14
				Commercial	1

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)					
Academic	10	Centre/Survey	3	NERC Fellows	1
				PhD	13
				Commercial	2

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0	1	2	1	27	15	0	46	10	34	2
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
1	1	5	3	20	6	1				

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0	2	3	2	25	24	1	57	15	40	2
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
0	3	3	1	18	1	1				

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

EPFS spectroradiometers have operated successfully throughout the year with instrument loans in support of 32 projects, several of which involved multiple loan periods or loan of more than one instrument. The highest graded projects received most support, with projects graded alpha-4 or higher accounting for over 85% of loans in terms of cost allocation. Nine projects involved use of the equipment at overseas destinations, including sites in Australia, Chile, S. Africa, Botswana and Palau in Micronesia.

The Pool continues to support the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARSF). Nine projects supported during 2002-2003 were associated with airborne remote sensing surveys carried out by ARSF or other aircraft facilities. Most of these required the deployment of field spectroradiometers simultaneous with overpasses of the aircraft systems. In addition, Pool staff worked closely with ARSF staff during the SWIR campaign in September 2002 to support a further 6 alpha-4 graded projects during this intensive campaign. EPFS performed five laboratory calibrations of the NERC CASI system under contract to NERC Scientific Services (26,27,28,28a,29).

Two major instrument failures/repairs were dealt with. In July 2002 the ASD FS Pro #6032 reported a shutter problem which necessitated repair by ASD. The repaired instrument was fully tested and made available for loan in November 2002. In December 2002, the GER1500 #2039 sensor developed a fault which required repair by the manufacturers. The repaired sensor is due back in early April and will be fully tested before returning to operation. The Cimel Sun photometer was repaired and fully refurbished during the year.

In April 2002 the EPFS hosted a two-day meeting of Field Spectroscopy which was attended by over 70 delegates from organisations in 9 different countries, including Canada and several EU countries. On the first day of the meeting there were keynote presentations from Dr Nigel Fox at the UK National Physical Laboratory (NPL) and Dr Michael Schaepman of SpectroLab at the University of Zurich. Several former users of EPFS instruments gave verbal or poster presentations and these focused on the application of field spectroscopy for a wide range of applications. The second day was dedicated to a workshop on the EPFS instruments and included the opportunity for hands-on experience.

In January 2003 the EPFS was reviewed as part of the SRG 2003 exercise. Paperwork was submitted at the beginning of December 2002 and in January 2003, Head of Service, Dr Ted Milton and EPFS user, Dr Tim Malthus gave a presentation to the SRG Committee. The facility was subsequently awarded high grades for all criteria, with an overall average of 4.88.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

1. Biomass Burning Emissions: Biogeochemical cycles

Research currently supported by EPFS is using field spectroscopy to quantify the energy emitted by burning savanna vegetation, and retrospectively estimate the amount of nitrogen and carbon emitted by such fires. Combustion of forest and grassland vegetation contributes to atmospheric pollution and rising greenhouse gases concentrations. Remotely measuring the energy radiated during natural fires has been suggested as a method for enhancing current emissions estimates. When made from satellites, such measures can potentially provide important new information on large-scale biomass combustion rates, which relate directly to the production of emissions. Experiments carried out in 2002 using an EPFS spectroradiometer to measure small experimental fires found a linear relationship between time-integrated fire radiative energy and total mass of vegetation combusted. Further information on the rate and intensity of burning was also retrievable from the emission spectra. These findings underpin the potential use of remotely sensed data for retrieving biomass combustion rates and improving burning emissions inventories.

The paper on this work, published in *Geophysical Research Letters*, (Wooster, 2002) was selected by the American Geophysical Union as a 'journal highlight'. Only 5% of American Geophysical Union [AGU] papers are highlighted in this way, and the author was invited to present this work to the NASA Aerosol Group (GSFC). EPFS continues to support this programme with loan of the GER3700 currently ongoing and scheduled to continue for several months. This is underpinned by EPFS effort to develop and validate the instrument calibration, which is of vital importance to this work.

Wooster, M., 2002. Small-scale experimental testing of fire radiative energy for quantifying mass combusted in natural vegetation fires. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 29, 2027-2030.

2. Monitoring Coral Reef Health: Biodiversity

EPFS users are engaged in important research on biodiversity and the consequences of biodiversity loss on ecosystem processes. A paper in *Nature* by Mumby *et al.* (2001) used a methodology developed in the field to classify areas of live coral on images acquired with an airborne imaging spectrometer, obtaining accuracies over large areas to within 10% of those measured on the ground. Live and dead colonies of *Porites* were readily distinguishable over large areas on the basis of their first spectral derivatives (rate of change of reflectance versus wavelength) in the region 506-565nm, as was expected from *in situ* measurements made using an EPFS spectroradiometer. Following these findings and demand from marine science users, staff from EPFS have collaborated with a group from the University of Uppsala (Dr Don Pierson) to design a housing allowing EPFS spectroradiometers to be used underwater (funded by NERC EOSI grant DST/26/57). Since its commission, this equipment has been used by a research group led by Dr Graham Ferrier to study coral reflectance in the South Pacific and the Great Barrier Reef. The work in Australia involved collaboration with the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) and was co-ordinated with an overpass of the NASA Hyperion sensor, making it the first simultaneous underwater and airborne survey of its kind.

Mumby, P.J. and Edwards, A.J., 2002. Mapping marine environments with IKONOS imagery: enhanced spatial resolution can deliver greater thematic accuracy. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 82, 248-257.

3. Sun photometry and correlation spectroscopy of Central American Volcanoes: Climate Change and Hazard Mitigation

During 2002, the EPFS has continued to support work carried out by Dr. Clive Oppenheimer (University of Cambridge) on volcanic plume monitoring, with a loan of the Cimel CE-318 Sun Photometer and Microtops II Sun photometer for field work in Central America. This work uses the EPFS Sun Photometers in conjunction with Correlation spectrometers to attempt to quantify sulphur-dioxide (SO₂) conversion to sulphuric acid in the moist atmospheres surrounding the volcanoes. The volcanoes studied are important contributors of sulphuric

compounds to the atmosphere, and therefore require regular monitoring. More importantly sulphur emissions are often linked to tectonic activity and hence, understanding of the emission cycles of such volcanoes can aid the process of hazard prediction.

This research was performed in conjunction with Dr. Matthew Watson of Michigan Technological University, USA and involved a number of South American volcanologists who, during fieldwork were trained in the quantification of emission and conversion rates of SO₂ from subduction zone volcanoes. EPFS equipment is committed to providing further support for this research during 2003.

4. The role of field spectroscopy in airborne sensor calibration: an example of the NERC CASI: In-house research

As part of the on-going programme of in-house research, the EPFS has pioneered a field method of validating the radiometric calibration of the NERC CASI flown by the Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARSF). This involves the use of airborne image data and field spectral obtained simultaneously over a calibration site established at Thorney Island. The development of such in-flight calibration procedures is important to monitoring the performance of the CASI, to supplement the schedule of laboratory based calibrations. With further refinement, the in-flight procedure could reduce the need for a mid-season laboratory calibration, which causes disruption of the flying schedule with consequential impact on the operators and users of the CASI. The work was reported at the EPFS Workshop in April 2002 and a paper has recently been submitted to IJRS.

Rollin, E.M., Milton, E.J. and Anderson, K., 2002. The role of field spectroscopy in airborne sensor calibration: an example of the NERC CASI. Submitted to *International Journal of Remote Sensing*.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

EPFS's future strategy is built around maintaining and enhancing the facility to ensure the capability of NSS to support Earth System Science. To facilitate this the EPFS will aim to deliver:

- An efficient, cost-effective programme of instrument loans, allocated to science projects on the basis of expert peer-review
- High quality user training and support, including induction courses for postgraduate students and others new to the subject of remote sensing;
- A calibration service for the NERC ARSF, traceable to the UK National Physical Laboratory;
- Training workshops and meetings on the subject of spectral measurements in remote sensing;
- Co-ordination between research groups in order to facilitate collaborative and community-wide search programmes, especially in support of airborne remote sensing campaigns;
- Links with leading research groups in Europe and between NERC Centres of Excellence, especially in terms of their requirements for spectral data and services;
- A focused R&D programme to ensure the fitness of the facility to address NERC science aims.

Key elements to the strategy are:

1. Collaboration with European partners (e.g. RSL Zurich and DLR) and others in the UK (e.g. NPL) to establish a Network of Excellence for the calibration and validation of physical measurements from EO sensors .
2. Establishment of a fully-instrumented vicarious calibration site for the UK, for use with airborne and satellite sensors, possibly at Thorney Island in Chichester Harbour, a site currently used by EPFS for such work. This could become the hub of a network of similar vicarious calibration sites around the UK, which EPFS could maintain and document for the benefit of the EO community throughout the country.
3. Investigation of the potential for remote sensing in new wavelength regions and/or using new types of instrument. The current configuration of EPFS was designed to support remote sensing in the optical region (0.35 – 2.50µm), but this has the potential to be expanded to include new applications such as fluorosensing and UV spectroscopy. Extension into the thermal region, based upon multispectral radiometry using FTIR instruments has recently been supported via collaboration with interested parties via the NERC Molecular Spectroscopy Facility (MSF).
4. Closer integration of the field spectroradiometers with airborne sensors operated by NERC, especially Imaging spectrometers such as the Itres Instruments CASI. EPFS staff are uniquely placed to conduct research that links these two data sources and we have already begun to study the spectral bandwidth of the various systems and the effect that differences in this parameter might have on data collected (e.g. Choi and Milton, 2002).

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

Breakdown of EPFS support in terms of per cent of cost allocation: 1999-2001 average and figures for 2002-2003.

By Grade

	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1
1999-2001 avg %	25	50	20	5	0
2002-2003 %	16	72	12	0	0

By Science

	SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
1999-2001 avg %	0	6	6	2	76	8	2
2002-2003 %	2	1	10	10	69	8	0

By Enri

	Biodiversity	Env Risks	Global	Nat RM	P & W	Other
1999-2001 avg %	4	7	15	47	20	7
2002-2003 %	27	1	24	29	2	15

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Dr David Lin
Director, Science & Innovation
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10 July 2003

Dear Dr Lin

I have been asked to write to you in my role as the chair of the Geophysical Equipment Pool Steering Committee (GEPSC), and in support of the Annual Report for the GEPSC. I took over as chair from Professor Mike Forde at the May 2003 meeting of the committee.

This has been an exciting year for the Geophysical Equipment Pool as we prepare for our new role as the Geophysical Equipment Facility (GEF). The new facility will operate as a two nodes: GEF-Leicester (SeisUK), will provide a comprehensive facility devoted to seismology including support for data archival, and GEF-Edinburgh will support the scientific areas of Ground Radar, Geomagnetism and Global Positioning Systems, as well as providing technical support for the seismic equipment and administrative support to NERC Swindon office. Mike Forde oversaw this transition and the next meeting of the GEFSC will, in recognition of the new structure of the facility, be held in Leicester.

Further opportunities for the coming year are presented by our plans to replace the current ground-penetrating radar systems, which have been in constant demand since their purchases in 1996. A new system is planned for purchase in FY 2003-4 together with the purchase of Transient Electromagnetic Method (TEM) instrumentation. We hope that the latter will both support unfulfilled scientific needs as well as stimulate new research in an area which presents enormous opportunities and is under exploited in the UK.

I understand that the final version of the Annual Report is not quite completed; however, I have read a draft of the report. Since I will be departing on fieldwork for 6 weeks from today I felt I needed to send this letter before I left. I would enthusiastically endorse both the quality of science supported by the GEP, evidenced by the scientific highlights presented in the final report, and the enormous opportunities presented by the creation of the GEF.

Yours sincerely,

Tavi Murray

Dr Tavi Murray
Chair, GEPSC

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE The Geophysical Equipment Pool (GEP)	FUNDING Contract to	AGREEMENT Edinburgh University	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1989	TERM 5 yr
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The Geophysical Equipment Pool (GEP) is an essential and unique facility that supports high-quality, peer-reviewed projects across a broad spectrum of earth and environmental sciences by provision of internationally-recognised, state-of-the-art geophysical instrumentation for field experiments. It is designed to enable researchers to undertake world-class research that utilises geophysical observations. The diverse customer base encompasses fields such as crustal structure, active tectonics, science-based archaeology, glaciology, sedimentology, volcano monitoring and magma chamber imaging, environmental hazards and geothermal resource mapping.

Further to a successful service review in January 2003, permission was granted to the GEP to expand its operation and merge with the JIF-funded SEIS-UK group at Leicester University to form a Geophysical Equipment Facility. This exciting and positive development will provide improved support for seismology, including data management infrastructure, in addition to the existing services. The instrumentation and scientific staff available within SEIS-UK brings the UK seismology community to the forefront of developments in onshore seismic data acquisition, processing and archiving. By integrating their research capabilities with the engineering and management expertise of the GEP, the value to NERC science for the money spent on the service increases significantly. The expanded Geophysical Equipment Facility will have an operating budget that is roughly twice as large as that of the GEP. We anticipate that the enhanced service will lead to an expansion in the user community since it will encourage geoscientists with little previous experience of geophysics to make use of the equipment.

Thus, the Facility provides researchers, council and NERC institute staff, including NERC studentship holders, with the planning, training, scientific and technical support necessary to meet the objectives of their proposed research projects. The instrumentation is provided to users through a free at the point of delivery service.

Key advantages –

- High quality science is ensured through a peer-reviewed application process. 17 projects of grade alpha 3 and above were supported by the GEP alone in 2002-3. 65% of projects also attracted NERC grants.
- A cost-effective, responsive, centralised equipment base and a small, skilled group of well-qualified electronic engineers and scientists provides advice, loans, scheduling, training, maintenance and data management. The GEP alone supported the training of ten PhD students during the period of this report.
- An ability to evaluate, tender for and acquire new instrumentation as a need is identified, thus maintaining provision of research quality instrumentation to the community. Geophysical equipment is prohibitively expensive for each individual university department to purchase its own state-of-the-art equipment on a routine basis. There is, therefore, a clear need for the continued provision of a community equipment facility.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review:		
Need 4.5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 4.5	Quality of Science & Training 4	Average 4.5

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F	Staff & Status 4 staff : NERC - Manager (B5), and Senior technician (B6) (100%) Edinb Univ - Deputy Manager & technician (100%)	Next Review (January) 2006	Contract Ends (31 March) 2004
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k 212.50	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k 32	Income £k	Full cash cost £k 516.42
	Unit 1 £21.34 per Unit of equipment per week	Unit 2	Unit 3			

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2003-04	£200.84k	2004-05	£400k : GEF	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
GEP Steering Committee (GEPSC)	10 (Chair – Dr. T Murray Univ. Leeds)	2	

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1	6	3				1	1
Other academic		2	6					
Students			1					
Pilot								
TOTAL	1	8	10					

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		5.33	3.33			0.33	0.33	
Other Academic		2	5.67	0.67	0.33			0.33
Students		0.67	1.33					
Pilot								
TOTAL		8	10.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects	1	7	2					
Other Academic		2	4					
Students			1					
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY) <i>nb - one project may have multiple students attached</i>						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		
17	10	13	1	1	5					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		
22.67	9.33	15.33	4	1.33	6.67					

USER PROFILE (current FY) <i>nb - one project may have multiple students attached</i>				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
16	1	0	10	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
21.33	1.33	1	15	0

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0	14	0	0	5	0	2	21	13	4	4

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
2	10	0	0	1	1	3

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0	17.33	0	0.67	5.67	1.67	4	29.33	16	9	4.33

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
0.67	11.67	0	0.33	3.33	1.33	2.67

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

In January this year (2003) a case was presented to the NERC Service Review group for a new enhanced facility, the Geophysical Equipment Facility (GEF). The bid was successful and funding approved for three years in the first instance, with a further two depending upon a successful Swindon Office review. The new venture will operate as a two-node Facility. GEF-Leicester (SEIS-UK) will provide a new, comprehensive facility devoted to seismology, including support for data archival, based in Leicester University. GEF-Edinburgh will continue to support the scientific areas of Ground Radar, Geomagnetism and Global Positioning Systems from their base in the Grant Institute, as well as providing technical support for the seismic equipment and administrative support to NERC Swindon office. The Steering Committee (GEFSC) will peer review all the science applications, grade all the scientific data reports and offer advice on capital expenditure on new equipment and on operational matters.

To meet concerns raised by the Steering Committee over the complex issue of the processing and interpretation of GPR data, a workshop with invited speakers was organised in May 2002, in Leeds University. Following an evaluation and comparison of data processing and visualisation packages by Dr. Tavi Murray and a PhD student at Leeds University, the ReflexW package was identified as the most suitable for the research community, and six copies were purchased for the Pool.

GEP staff continue to provide Labview software assistance for the new NERC Ion Microprobe unit based in Edinburgh, and undertake a small amount of equipment development work for researchers at Edinburgh University.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

The nature of the service offered by the Geophysical Equipment Pool (GEP) leads to the support of a very wide range of science, the common factor in this being the use of geophysical methods of data acquisition. The range is too wide to report fully here, but the fact that it is able to support the full range of NERC science worldwide (see figure below) is a great strength of the Pool. Moreover, the Pool provides a service that is at the very upstream end of research projects, including advice on data acquisition strategy and training in the use of field equipment. As a result of this, the four scientific cameos presented here, one from each of the four types of data acquisition supported by the Pool, serve to illustrate the scientific aims and objectives of the projects rather than their ultimate scientific results.

In 2002-2003 the Pool has continued to support geophysical research into the mechanisms of continental breakup (see Science Supported in 2001/2002 Annual Report). Prof. Kathy Whaler (Edinburgh University) received a NERC research grant, together with the provision of magnetotelluric (MT) sounding equipment from the Pool, to investigate the distribution of igneous melt beneath the continental rift system in Ethiopia. Seismic experiments being conducted there with the support of the Pool are capable of defining the structure of the crust and upper mantle, but the presence of low-velocity melt zones within parts of the rift restricts the capabilities of the seismic method. MT measurements, on the other hand, are capable of defining the extent of the melt zones and the structure of the crust and mantle beneath them. The combination of seismic and MT methods will provide valuable information on the volume and movement of melt immediately prior to the evolution of the rift from a continental, fault-dominated mode to an oceanic, magma-dominated mode with a sea-floor spreading centre.

The Pool has again supported Prof. Peter Sammonds of University College, London in his ARCICE research programme to understand the interaction of ice masses in response to climate change. A component of the programme is to resolve the mechanical behaviour of sub-glacial sediments and thus understand their role in facilitating glacier movement. There are two conflicting views on how sediments deform sub-glacially: by thin-layer plastic deformation, or by thick-layer viscous deformation. Previous work at the Langjokull ice cap in Iceland pointed to the former; thus a need arose to carry out the same measurements at another ice cap, Breidamerkurjokull, where thick-layer viscous deformation had been proposed, to confirm or reject this behaviour. Ground Penetrating Radar provided by the Pool has been used to map the structures in the immediately pro-glacial sediments and inform their interpretation with laboratory measurements of the mechanical behaviour of sediment samples.

A Differential Global Positioning System provided by the Pool has been used over two successive field seasons by Prof. Jim Best of Leeds University to locate precisely measurements of natural turbidity current activity in Lillooet Lake in Canada. An understanding of the movement and fluid dynamics of turbidity currents has, until now, been based on laboratory observations in flume tanks. Now they can be quantified using acoustic Doppler profiling (ADP) of the temporal and spatial distribution of the currents as they enter the lake as sediment-laden freshwater glacial melt. Additionally, the interaction of underflows with delta and lakebed topography is being studied. However, accurate, real-time positioning of the survey vessel is essential in order to make use of ADP and echo sounding measurements at the resolution required.

One of the most controversial topics in earth sciences at the moment is the concept of mantle plumes. In the 1990s a strong line of argument was developing for deep sources for plumes near the core-mantle boundary. Yet maintaining fixed, deep-sourced upwellings of the dimensions of an oceanic swell is fluid-dynamically problematic. An excellent set of discussion papers on this topic has recently been published by The Royal Astronomical Society in "Astronomy & Geophysics". The Cape Verde Swell is supposed to be buoyed up by a plume and the islands to be the products of a plume magma source. George Helffrich of Bristol University is using broadband seismic receivers and associated equipment from the Pool to record teleseismic arrivals at the Cape Verde islands over a two-year period to learn more about the nature of the hot upper mantle beneath – is there a plume conduit and how far does it extend? He notes that the Cape Verde situation is different from other plume sites that have been studied seismically in that the African plate is stationary over the plume. Thus the plume source should be directly beneath the island.

NERC GEP - GB and Worldwide and instrumentation deployments 2002-03

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

From Aug 2003 the Geophysical Equipment Facility (GEF) will commence operation with all seismology loans being provided by GEF-Leicester (SEIS-UK).

The Pulse Ekko Ground radar systems (PE100 & 1000) have been in constant demand since their purchases in 1996, with a marked preference for the PE100 system. To meet a busy schedule, and ensure continued high-grade science, consideration was given to a further GPR system, and a new system is planned for purchase in FY 2003-4. Also planned is the purchase of Transient Electromagnetic Method (TEM) instrumentation. Advances in technology will require that a review of all modern systems is undertaken before tendering for new equipment in both cases.

As opportunities arise, and if workload permits, the GEP will continue to provide an electronics engineering service for other areas of NERC science.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

ALLOCATION OF CAPACITY

- Usage versus Capacity: - Sixty percent of equipment is estimated to be available for loan during the year after deductions have been made for scheduled maintenance, and modifications etc. This figure is used to derive the equivalent hire-charge of £21.34/unit/week that underpins the cost allocations exercise and the usage/capacity figures. For this year, the Pool has recovered costs of £488,167. A detailed spreadsheet is included in the appendices.

MAKING KNOWLEDGE WORK

3 July 2003

Dr David Lin
Director, Science & Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
North Star Ave
Swindon SN2 1EU

Dear Dr Lin,

**Annual Reports from the NERC Inductively-Coupled Plasma Steering
Committee**

I have great pleasure in writing this covering letter for the two Annual Reports (one for ICP-MS and one for ICP-AES) considered by the Inductively Coupled Plasma Steering Committee. I am taking the liberty of only providing one covering letter, since, starting this year, the opportunity has been taken to combine these two facilities into a 'one-stop shop', and in future we will only provide a single report.

It is clear from these reports that both the ICP-MS and the ICP-AES continue to provide an excellent service to the NERC community. Customers come from 25 different Institutions (including Oxford, Cambridge, UCL, IC, Brighton and Hertfordshire), and from 35 different Departments (including History, Ocean Sciences, Environmental Health and Risk Management, as well as Geography, Environmental Sciences, Biology and Earth Sciences), with RAE ratings up to and including 6*. As previously, there has been a particular emphasis on student training – over half the supported projects are associated with PhD studentships. The science areas supported are primarily in the Earth and Terrestrial & Freshwater Sciences, but a substantial number come from the interdisciplinary area of Science-based Archaeology.

Projects completed this year include 35% graded by the ICPSC as $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 5$, and 45% as $\alpha 3$ (but in line with our previous policy decision, $\alpha 3$ projects have only been prioritised for completion if they include a substantial PhD student training element). Both services offer excellent value for money to NERC, but the ICP-AES has been particularly outstanding this year – for a cost to NERC of c. £33k, more than 7,500 samples have been analysed – often for more than 20 elements per sample. This gives a per sample cost to NERC of £2.50~~pa~~, or a per element cost of a few pence.

One issue arising out of this financially modest commitment (particularly to the ICP-AES) is that the pursuance of reports and publications from customers cannot be as rigorous as is the case with larger operations. This probably results in an under-reporting of the scientific outcomes of the work carried out. The adoption of the 'one-stop shop' service (launched this year) should enable us to be more cost-effective in this aspect, and we look forward to providing the same level of service but with a higher degree of customer focus.

Yours sincerely

AP Professor A.M. Pollard,
Chair, NERC ICPSC

cc. Dr. R.L.F. Kay, NERC

Dictated by Professor Pollard and signed in his absence.

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES)	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT F14/6/8	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1978	TERM 3 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES) is an important analytical tool in a wide range of scientific disciplines. ICP-AES data contribute to projects from across the Science Areas and ENRIs. It is one of the most widely used techniques and is often the first line of attack in producing high quality, elemental analyses of environmental, archaeological, geological and biological samples. The data provided by the ICP-AES Facility frequently underpin data obtained by other analytical techniques. The ICP-AES operated by the Facility can determine major, minor and trace element concentrations in a variety of matrices, and is often the most appropriate and cost effective method for many applications.

The Facility is dedicated to producing accurate and precise data, suitable to its users needs. It is also heavily involved in training its users in data quality monitoring techniques, and provides full instruction and access, where possible, to reference materials suitable to the users sample matrix. In addition, the Facility provides access to the fully equipped sample preparation laboratories within the Department of Geology, and gives training and advice in all the sample preparation techniques available. This includes developing new methodologies where necessary, in conjunction with the user. These sample preparation facilities are particularly important for those users who do not have access to these types of facilities at their home institution. NERC fund 60% of a PGRA and she is available to supervise users in the laboratories or to provide advice and support to users before they visit the Facility. NERC also provide a contribution to the consumables costs of the Facility, which covers the costs of Argon and some chemicals.

The main strengths of the Facility are:

- High levels of research students visiting the Facility and gaining experience of sample preparation and instrumentation
- Access to comprehensive sample preparation laboratories
- Flexibility and versatility of modern instrumentation
- High throughput of samples, meaning that there is no significant backlog of users or samples awaiting analysis
- In house expertise in ICP-AES and data quality monitoring along with established analytical protocols and procedures

ICP-AES is an established technique, and it is highly unlikely that further instrumental developments will be made in the near future. However, there is a high demand for the services of the ICP-AES Facility, and there is still a need for the high quality, high throughput data that the service provides.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: Jan 2002	
Need 5.00	Uniqueness 3.50	Quality of Service 5.00	Quality of Science & Training 4.50	Average 4.50

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 50%	Staff & Status 60% PGRA	Next Review (January) 2005	Contract Ends (31 March) 2006
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k 32.91	Unit Cost £			Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k 40.20
	Unit 1 5.32	Unit 2	Unit 3			
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07		
	32.91	32.91	32.91			

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
ICPSSC	5	2	ICP-MS Facility

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		1					1	
Other academic		2	6				2	1
Students		5	5				1	
Pilot								
TOTAL		8	11				4	1

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		4.33	2.00				0.33	
Other Academic		1.33	3.67				0.67	0.67
Students		2.67	4.33				2.67	1.00
Pilot								
TOTAL		8.33	10.00				3.67	1.67

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects		1	1					2
Other Academic		2	9					2
Students		8	8					
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other			
33	4	16	7		13								

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other			
34.00	5.00	20.33	9.33		8.67								

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
17			16	

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
15.00		0.33	18.33	0.33

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
	5			2			7	6	1	

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
7	14	1	1	10		

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
3.33	18.33	0.33		16.00			38.00	13.33	16.00	8.67

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
5.67	13.33	3.00		11.67		0.33

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

This Annual Report covers the last year in which the Facility will operate in its current mode. In future, the pre-existing NERC ICP-AES and NERC ICP-MS Facilities will operate as a joint, one-stop-shop, ICPS Facility offering both techniques as an integrated package.

Currently the Perkin Elmer Optima ICP-AES is continuing to perform to expectations and there have been no significant instrumental difficulties or breakdowns during this year. Demand for ICP-AES analyses was very high and the instrument has been running at, or even above, the allocated capacity for much of the year. This year has seen a number of large projects come on line from users, and at times the instrument has been running in excess of three hundred samples a day to meet their needs. The heaviest use of the instrument has been made by projects within the environmental and archaeological fields, with some users analysing over 1000 samples as part of their research. The use of sequential extractions for characterisation of soils and sediments has been particularly high this year, and this process generates large numbers of solutions from each sample.

Student training remains a large part of the Facility's activities, with research students being trained in sample preparation, analytical methodology and, to some extent, data interpretation. Of the 33 projects undertaken by users of the Facility in the current Financial Year, 48% have been research students. The Facility continues to provide important training for students within their research programme that may not be available within the users host institution, as demonstrated by the large proportion of student use.

Users from 23 academic departments have visited the Facility this year, and 7,552 samples have been analysed. This represents an increase in the number of samples analysed, although the total number of users and applications has remained consistent with previous years. The large numbers of samples processed by the Facility represents good value for money, with samples costing the equivalent of less than £3 each. The increase in sample numbers is due to the large projects undertaken as mentioned above. As in previous years, many of the analysed samples have been prepared at Royal Holloway, with 26% of the total numbers analysed being prepared at the Facility.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Many of the Facility's users simply use the facility to generate the data they require for their research. But in some projects, the Facility provides a greater input into the project planning and implementation stages. One example of this is illustrated in the project outlined below. Here the Facility agreed to undertake the analyses requested, but subsequent discussions with the Principal Investigator indicated that there was a need for statistical analysis and interpretation of the data, which could not easily be done by the PI or the Co-Investigators. The Facility has been instrumental in interpreting the data and in advising the Investigators on future strategies. This demonstrates the contribution that the Facility can make to certain projects, particularly those that come from the less chemistry based disciplines such as, in this case, Archaeology.

Ballast, Basalts and Boats: Trade in the Roman Red Sea.

David Williams and David Peacock, Department of Archaeology, University of Southampton

As part of this project, samples of Roman ballast have been collected from known Roman ports in Egypt. The ballast was offloaded from cargo ships at these ports, prior to the ships being re-loaded with cargo for transportation to the Indian subcontinent. The original hypothesis was that laden ships sailed to India where their heavy cargo was offloaded and a lighter cargo of silks, spices etc was taken on board. This lighter cargo would necessitate taking on board ballast to stabilise the ship for the return journey. It was supposed, therefore, that the ballasts (which are almost exclusively basaltic in composition) would have originated from the Deccan Basalts of India. However, initial dating of the ballasts gave ages of 1-2Ma, far too young to be Deccan basalts. It is known that Roman ships would put into port along the coasts of Eritrea and Yemen, and these areas also have localised outcrops of basalt.

The aim of this project has been to geochemically characterise the ballast rocks and attempt to relate their composition to the composition of basalts from quarries near known and supposed Roman ports. This has been undertaken by determining the elemental compositions of the ballasts and basalts and using a range of statistical methods to establish populations and investigate if the ballasts can be related to a source area.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

The main future development will be the joining of the two existing NERC ICP Facilities (AES and MS) into an integrated, one-stop-shop facility. This takes effect from April 2003, and this Annual Report, therefore, represents the last one where each Facility will be handled separately.

The new ICP Spectrometry Facility has introduced a single application form and introduced a simplified application process, to ensure that potential users have a clear route of access to the Facility. Whilst the two instrumental techniques will continue to be operated at Kingston University (ICP-MS) and Royal Holloway (ICP-AES), applications and routine enquiries will be handled by Kingston branch of the Facility, due to their higher staffing levels. However, technical enquiries will continue to be dealt with by the relevant individual institutions to ensure that access to high quality advice is continued and technical expertise is maintained. The peer review system for processing of applications has been altered to ensure parity between applications for both techniques.

The joint facility will enable users to have a single point of contact for both techniques, and ensure that the resources of both pre-existing facilities are used in a cost effective manner. Applicants who require access to both techniques can be handled in an integrated way, ensuring that instrument time is scheduled to enable the user to prepare one set of samples for both techniques. Sample preparation can be performed either at Kingston or Royal Holloway, whichever is most appropriate. Slight alterations in the individual preparation methods may become necessary to ensure parity between techniques.

The ICP-AES instrument operated at Royal Holloway is nearly 4 years old, and is no longer covered by a full manufacturer's warranty. At present, a preventative maintenance agreement exists, but it is likely that a request for some funding will be made to NERC to ensure that NERC users continue to have access to a reliable instrument.

The lower administrative load now carried by the ICP-AES section of the Facility has freed up some additional time for the Research Assistant to spend with the users, meaning that the training element of the Facility on a one-to-one basis has expanded further. This has always been an important part of the service provided, but in future it is hoped to expand this, with the possibility of running integrated training programmes in both ICP techniques.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

Projects completed by project grade

■ a4 ■ a3 □ a2 □ Pilot

Projects completed by Science Area

■ ES ■ TFS □ AS □ MS ■ SBA

MAKING KNOWLEDGE WORK

3 July 2003

Dr David Lin
Director, Science & Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
North Star Ave
Swindon SN2 1EU

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Annual Reports from the NERC Inductively-Coupled Plasma Steering Committee

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Projects completed this year include 35% graded by the ICPSC as $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 5$, and 45% as $\alpha 3$ (but in line with our previous policy decision, $\alpha 3$ projects have only been prioritised for completion if they include a substantial PhD student training element). Both services offer excellent value for money to NERC, but the ICP-AES has been particularly outstanding this year – for a cost to NERC of c. £33k, more than 7,500 samples have been analysed – often for more than 20 elements per sample. This gives a per sample cost to NERC of £2.50, or a per element cost of a few pence.

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Yours sincerely

AP Professor A.M. Pollard,
Chair, NERC ICPS

cc. Dr. R.L.F. Kay, NERC

Dictated by Professor Pollard and signed in his absence.

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2001 to March 2002

SERVICE Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT F14/G6/91	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1986	TERM 3 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

ICP-MS instrumentation now plays a vital role in many geochemical, environmental and earth system studies for the provision of elemental and isotopic data. The data is used to interpret evolutionary processes, to evaluate pollution, define regulatory limits and is often required for quantitative modelling. The data must be fit for purpose, normally of good accuracy and precision. The ICPMSF offers a level of expertise, both of instrumentation and applications, which cannot be matched in the UK. This expertise is used to provide a high quality service able to support even the most demanding requirements within the NERC science remit.

The Facility exists to provide ICP-MS facilities to the NERC community in support of research, and undertakes research and development, which meets the current and future needs of NERC science. The service is delivered in three main ways. Firstly, the Facility offers ICP-MS instrument time utilising two quadrupole ICP-MS instruments and a new high-resolution magnetic sector instrument. In addition, laser ablation microprobe analysis is available for spatially resolved elemental microanalysis of solid samples. Secondly the Facility organises and teaches short courses, workshops and gives one to one training on the preparation of samples, ICP-MS instrumentation (basic to advanced) and data handling. Thirdly, there is an internal R&D programme covering all aspects of ICP-MS instrument development and applications, which meets the current and future needs of NERC science.

The past 12 months have seen a continuing, steady flow of customers through the Facility from the Earth, Terrestrial and Freshwater and Science Based Archaeology science areas, with further growth in the area of Science Based Archaeology. We have supported 18 projects, 33% of which were pilot studies that will form the basis of full applications in the future. Approximately 60% of the full projects supported were graded $\alpha 4$ or $\alpha 5$. Of the ENRIs, only biodiversity is not represented, with a very even distribution between all others. Demand for the Facility remains high. We received 21 new applications during the year, with nearly one half in Terrestrial and Freshwater Sciences. Several projects were rejected to ensure that the capacity of the Facility was not overextended. We continue to receive new, high-quality applications from the top earth and environmental science university departments in the UK.

One of the prime elements of the ICPMSF mission is to enter into dialogue with users to ensure appropriate use of instrumentation and to add scientific value to project proposals, thereby increasing the knowledge base of the Facility to the benefit of the whole user community. In addition, it has a role to promote the awareness, application and technology of ICP-MS technique and to disseminate this to the wider scientific community thereby enhancing the UK's industrial competitiveness and quality of life.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: 2002	
Need 5.00	Uniqueness 3.50	Quality of Service 5.00	Quality of Science & Training 4.50	Average 4.50

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F	Staff & Status	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March)
85%	50% Facility Head, 100% PDRA 100% PGRA	2005	2006

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1 Analytical day	Unit 2 Sample Preparation day				
122.05	1.6	1		0	0	169.05

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)							
2003-04	125.03	2004-05	127.96	2005-06	130.89	2006-07	2007-08

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
ICPSSC	5	2	ICP-AES Facility

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1		1				1	1
Other academic		2	3				1	1
Students		1	4				4	1
Pilot								
TOTAL	1	3	8				6	3

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 4 years —1999/2000, 2000/2001, 2001/2002, 2002/2003)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	0.25		0.5				1.25	0.25
Other Academic		0.75	2	0.25			1.25	0.25
Students	0.5	5.5	3	0.25	0.5		2.25	0.75
Pilot								
TOTAL	0.75	6.25	5.5	0.5	0.5		4.75	1.25

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects			1					
Other Academic		2						
Students		5	3					3
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (Current FY — 2002/03)									
Grand Total	Infrastructure					*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic			
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	PAYG		
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC	NERC C/S
18	2	13	3		3				

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 4 years)									
Grand Total	Infrastructure					*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic			
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	PAYG		
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC	NERC C/S
19.25	1.5	13.75	3.5	0	4				

USER PROFILE (Current FY — 2002/03)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
3		1	14	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 4 years —1999/2000, 2000/2001, 2001/2002, 2002/2003)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
4.75	0	0.25	14.5	0

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (Current FY — 2002/03)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
8	30			7			45	10	30	5
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
4	6	1		7						

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 2 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
4	23	0.5	0	6	0	0	33.5	10.5	15.5	7.5
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
3.25	9.75	0.75		5.25						

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2001/02):

The Facility has been fully operational for ten of the past twelve months. Dr Greenwood, who had been with the Facility since 2000, left in September to take up a new post in industry. In March, Dr Kathryn Linge from the University of Western Australia joined the Facility as a PDRA. Kathryn's PhD investigated arsenic and phosphorus contamination in the sediments of a shallow wetland in Perth, Western Australia. The Facility has also secured funding for a project to investigate 'Source apportionment of heavy metals around road systems' and we have been joined by Dr Sam Cook from the University of Reading to carry out this work. This project is supported by the Environment Agency.

In late November all instruments and lab equipment moved to a new, purpose built laboratory block. After installation in early December and re-commissioning of the three ICP-MS instruments, the Facility was again fully operational by the middle of January. Contamination levels in the new laboratory are significantly reduced compared to the previous facility and have allowed the introduction of new clean operation procedures.

Following the decision to integrate the existing facilities at Royal Holloway, University of London with Kingston University and form the new ICP Facility, work has begun on the development of a new joint website which is aimed to be live by 1 April, 2003 for the start of the new contract. New application procedures for the combined Facility have also been developed

No formal training courses were run in this financial year, principally due to staff changes. However, one-on-one training for all aspects of the analysis process continues with NERC customers where needed. We have made some headway with the production of comprehensive training notes for both instrument operations and data handling. Facility staff continue to make significant contributions to the supervision of 'external' PhD student projects.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2001/02):

The following are highlights from two of the 18 projects supported during the year and reflect the flavour of the research supported.

Improving the performance and environmental impact of co-combustion of coal and wastes in FBC boilers designed for coal firing (in collaboration with Kandiyoti, Imperial College)

A major problem facing developed nations is the disposal of wastes, including plastics, paper pulp sludge, domestic refuse and sewerage sludge. Increasingly stringent regulation on environmental releases render many current disposal methods (eg., landfill, sea disposal, and open burning) unacceptable. An alternative is co-combustion with conventional fossil fuels, where the associated energy release is recovered for power generation or heating purposes. However, the fate of toxic elements in combustion reactors have not been widely studied. A suite of trace elements (Hg, Se, Cr, Be, V, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Cd, Sb, Pb) were studied by examining concentrations in the solid ash remaining after combustion. Experiments showed that most elements volatilised to a some extent but that Hg, Se, and Cr were particularly volatile, with less than 20% retention in residual ash. The addition of chlorine increased the retention of Be, V, Cr, Co, Ni, Se, and Sb, but decreased the retention of Cu, As, Cd and Pb. However, the addition of sorbents (eg., kaolinite, limestone, dolomite, calcium carbonate, titanium dioxide) to combustion enhanced trace element retention in the ash, with kaolinite seeming the most promising.

Turbidity effects on coral reefs and reef associated communities off the west coast of Barbados, WI (in collaboration with Coleman, Reading)

Corals grow for very long time and the mineral from which they are made incorporates chemicals from the seawater in which they live. The variation in chemical composition of cores carefully cut from living corals were used to produce a history of changes in seawater chemistry off the coast of Barbados. Laser ablation ICP-MS allowed analysis of several trace metals (e.g. Pb, Cd) that had been found to be below detection limit using conventional analysis. The analysis showed changes in heavy metal pollution over the last 60 years and also the effects of storms that caused mixing of polluted near-coast waters with those further off-shore.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Administration

From 2003 the ICPMSF will be amalgamated with the NERC ICP-AES Facility. Since their inception, the ICPMSF and ICPAESF have been truly complementary with AES providing routine major and trace element data and MS providing trace, ultra-trace and isotopic information. Combining the administration and operation of the existing Facilities will improve efficiency and NERC customers will be offered a 'one stop shop' with application for ICP instrument time via a single, simplified application. The proposed combination of state of the art instrumentation and, more significantly, specialist expertise will make the combined Facility a cost-effective, world class resource that is unique in the UK.

Science - Future areas of research will include:-

- *Chromatography ICP-MS for metal speciation.* Techniques for organo tin speciation of DBT, TBT and TPhT have now been evaluated for both HPLC-ICP-MS and GC-ICP-MS using reference materials, and tested in an inter-laboratory comparative exercise. The technique will now be used to speciate Sn compounds in the Tilbury Docks, UK. Techniques for As speciation by LC-ICP-MS have also been developed and will be evaluated further.
- *Calibration standards for fully quantitative determination of spatially resolved analysis of environmental samples using HR-LA-ICP-MS.* Work has already begun in collaboration with the Geological Survey of Norway using synthetic apatite crystals.
- *Sample and matrix independent calibration.* The calibration of LA-ICP-MS data is one of the most significant problems remaining, making widespread use of the technique difficult. Research continues to produce a sample independent calibration procedure that could be used for a range of sample types.
- *Ultra trace elemental analysis in ice cores using HR-ICP-MS.* The performance of HR-ICP-MS to analyse trace concentrations of 'difficult' elements (ie., As, Se) in Antarctic ice cores with significant Cl concentrations has begun.
- *Improving sensitivity.* Some projects have been limited by the inability to detect high mass elements (eg., REE, Th, U) at low concentrations using LA. Operating with high capacity vacuum pumping has been shown to improve sensitivity, however further investigation to learn the true capacity of this technique is required.
- *Measurement of iodine by HR-ICP-MS.* A methodology for the high precision analysis of both ¹²⁷I and ¹²⁹I will be devised. The project will investigate instrument optimisation and how isotopic ratios may best be obtained.

Equipment

The existing quadrupole ICP-MS instrumentation will be replaced in 2003-04. This is essential for the successful delivery of service into 2006. The use of laser ablation with high resolution sector ICP-MS will also be evaluated with a view to assessing future requirement for laser ablation hardware.

Training

Formalised training courses are scheduled for the next financial year and will be promoted through the Geochemistry Group, Mineralogical Society and on the Facility's web site. It is anticipated that one to one training will become more intensely required and staff time will be allocated for that purpose. Appropriate training material will be developed specifically for this purpose.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

Targets and Milestones – The NERC contract covers the costs for about 83% of Facility operation. During the past year NERC work has utilised 80% of the capacity

Capacity vs use

Activity	No of days used	% of total days	% of usable days
NERC customer analysis	89	34	53
NERC R&D activity	26	10	15
Kingston University	34	13	20
NERC Training activity	21	8	12
Scheduled maintenance	15	6	
Breakdown	21	8	
Public holiday	14	5	
No staff available*	20	8	
Transfer to new laboratory	20	8	
Total	260		
Total usable	170		

*Due to minimum staff leave requirements, health and safety training

Progress and comments

Evaluation of laser ablation with magnetic sector ICP-MS – This target has not been met due to the high demand for laser ablation facilities with the conventional quadrupole instruments

Development of data-handling software for LA-ICP-MS – a data handling protocol is now in place.

Improving sensitivity. Operating with high capacity vacuum pumping has been shown to improve sensitivity and technique development continues.

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Dr. N.B.W. Harris

8 July 2003

Mr David Lin
Science Programmes Directorate
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wilts SN2 1EU

Dear David,

NERC Isotope Geoscience Facilities: Annual Reports

On behalf of the Steering Committee I write to approve the annual reports from the facility managers of:

NERC Isotope Geoscience Laboratory (NIGL) at BGS;
NERC Isotope Community support Facility (ICSF) at SUERC;
NERC Argon Isotope Facility (AIF) SUERC; and
NERC Uranium Series Facility at the Open University (OUUSF)

Over the past 12 months all four facilities have continued to respond positively to the increasingly competitive scientific criteria imposed by the committee and we endorse the progress made in both the range and quality of science that they have undertaken. For 3 of the facilities, recent months have been dominated by the Review, the results of which, relative to previous reviews, I enclose. The committee was pleased to see upward movement by all 3 facilities, virtually across the board. It is interesting to note that the Review identified a marked increase in 'uniqueness', emphasizing that the skills and resources that are offered cannot be found elsewhere in the U.K. The most outstanding progress however, was made by NERC Isotope Geochemistry Laboratory increasing its average grade from 3.8 to 4.25. In my view this success reflects the sustained high level of work approved by the committee, the innovative science now being undertaken, the strong publication record and the effective management of the Facility by Prof. Parrish.

Yours sincerely,

Prof. N.B.W. Harris
Encl:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Nigel Harris', written over the typed name and 'Encl:'.

**SRG 2003 Facility Review Scoring
(previous review in parentheses)**

	NEED	Uniqueness	Quality of service	Quality of science and training	Average
ICSF	4.0 (4.0)	5.0 (4.5)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
OU USF	4.0 (4.0)	4.5 (3.0)	4.5 (4.5)	4.5 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
NERC IGL	4.5 (4.4)	4.0 (3.4)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (3.6)	4.25 (3.8)
AIF	(4.5)	(5.0)	(4.0)	(5.0)	(4.63)

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Isotope Community Support Facility ICSF	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT F14/G6/11/01	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1991	TERM 3 or 5 Under review
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

ICSF meets the need in the Geoscience Community for isotopic analyses and training primarily in support of high quality research in the full life cycle of the Applied Minerals research, from genetic modelling informing exploration and exploitation, through to remediation. Training of postgraduate students in the principles and practice of Stable Isotope Geochemistry lies at the core of ICSF support (every project since 1999 has a student undergoing training) with students gaining access, via ICSF, to an international-class suite of isotope systems at SUERC for analyses of fluids, minerals and organic compounds. This Facility, embedded in SUERC with its complementary expertise, offers a unique environment (2003 Services Review Group marking 5) with a high level of service (4.5), as reflected in a recent formal user survey (>95% users think overall service, and student training to be excellent).

Output is primarily measured by (i) peer-reviewed publication, and (ii) the production of motivated young scientists, trained to fulfil the strategic needs of the NERC and the UK. Since ICSF inception in 1991, 92% of students from ICSF approved projects have gone on to work in the mining/exploration/environmental industries or are applying their skills in academia. ICSF is committed to revealing and explaining the Earth's resources and supporting their sustainable use in an environmentally conscious manner to provide significant benefits for society. From approved projects addressing fundamental ore genesis, to dealing with remediation strategies for acid mine drainage, ICSF is involved in shaping science that contributes to the Sustainable Economies and Earth's Life Support Systems NERC Priorities. Around 80% of approved research undertaken in the past year falls within the NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues (ENRI) "Natural Resource Management" and "Pollution and Waste".

The Facility is headed by Prof. Tony Fallick and run day-to-day by Dr. Adrian Boyce. Dr. Boyce's salary and that of Mrs Alison McDonald (50% time) are paid through the contract. Access to researchers is through (i) application to the NERC Isotope Geoscience Facilities Steering Committee (NIGFSC); and/or (ii) pilot studies preparatory to future applications, approved by Prof. Fallick. Analyses are produced for successful projects (currently $\alpha 3$ and above are funded for postgraduate, or $\alpha 4$ for higher level science) most commonly through intensive, one-to-one postgraduate supervision. All training and supervision is guided by Dr. Boyce, assisted by Prof. Fallick.

Quality is assured through peer-review of formal applications by the NIGFSC, and by PRC and Thematic Grant applications for personal research ($\leq 15\%$ per annum). In the current Financial Year, 15 approved and 1 pilot project were supported from 10 UK Institutions. Twelve PhD students underwent extensive training in stable isotope techniques, making use of five isotope ratio mass spectrometers and appropriate preparation systems at SUERC. In this way, ICSF continues to support and promote the government's priority for the long-term health of the science base. Two new projects were approved, both involving PhD students, and graded $\alpha 3/4$ and $\alpha 4$. Whilst these projects remain core to ICSF's commitment to student training, Dr. Boyce actively seeks to take part in interdisciplinary larger scale research. This earned NERC Grant income adds value to the Facility by financially underpinning personal research; participation in grant-funded science also provides a yardstick for quality that is applied to Facility applications.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: January, 2003		
Need 4.0	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 4.5	Quality of Science & Training 4.0	Average 4.38

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 100%	Staff & Status 1 Manager – Dr. Adrian Boyce (RA3) (100%) 1 Part-time Technician – Mrs Alison McDonald (Grade E) (100%)	Next Review (January) 2006 (under review)	Contract Ends (31 March) 2004 new one in place to at least 2007
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY					
Recurrent Allocation £k 14.0	Unit Cost £k		Capital Expend £k 20.3	Income £k -	Full cash cost £k 118,220
	Half Day of Full Facility Time 0.277				

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement) NB ESTIMATED FROM 2003-04 ONWARDS					
2003-04	118,220	2003-04	115,000	2004-05	122,000
				2004-06	124,000
				2006-07	126,000

STEERING COMMITTEE NIGFSC	Independent Members 8	Meetings per annum 2	Other S&F Overseen AIF, OUTF, NIGL
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APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3/4	α3	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other academic								
Students		1	1					
Pilot							2	
TOTAL	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	0

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years —1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3/4	α3	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic								
Students			1.5	1.5				
Pilot							2	
TOTAL	0	0	1.5	1.5	0	0	2	0

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic			1					
Students								
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	PAYG		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Student Total	NERC		
24	3	12	6	1	8					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	PAYG		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Student Total	NERC		
23	3	11	5	1	9					

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
12	1	0	12	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
13	1	0	11	0

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
NB ONLY PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS AND THESES ARE LISTED - REFEREED = OUT NOW OR IN PRESS										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc Not listed	PhD Theses
	17						17	14		3

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
	100%					

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
NB ONLY PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS AND THESES ARE LISTED - REFEREED = OUT NOW OR IN PRESS										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc Not listed	PhD Theses
	13						13	11		2

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
	100%					

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

TRAINING – THE CORE EFFORT

The production of highly motivated and educated young people remains a primary objective of the NERC strategy, *Science for the Sustainable Future*. ICSF contributes to this resource by investing our expertise in young and talented people. ICSF core support continues to centre on student training in the principles and practice of isotope geochemistry, especially stable isotopes (C, H, O and S). In the past year, 12 PhD students (4 NERC/CASE, 2 NERC, 1 EU, 1 DENI, 1 Industry, 1 Fermor Studentship, 2 University funded) received training in the principles and practice of stable isotope geochemistry. Six presented data to national conferences (one winning best student talk at the MDSG AGM, 2003), two have a peer-reviewed paper out or in press in international journals (*Economic Geology*, *Geology*), and three PhD theses were completed. In all cases, training starts with the development of the project, through formulation of the application (in all cases in close consultation with Dr. Boyce) and on-site training, and ends with thesis completion and peer-reviewed publication. Quality of these projects – all student based – has been improved, with no application receiving less than $\alpha 3/4$ from the NIGFSC since 2000. Through CASE students and other links, there is a strong interaction with UK industry.

PROJECT THROUGHPUT

15 approved and 1 pilot project (under review at next NIGFSC meeting), plus 3 NERC Grants (via personal research mechanism) were supported by ICSF this year, involving 24 researchers. The bulk of effort went into four areas, (1) data accumulation and training for recently approved projects; (2) paper redaction; (3) personal research mostly via successful NERC Grant income, and technical development; (4) development of new projects with academic partners.

RESULTS – PAPERS

Since last year, 14 papers have been published or are in press in international-class journals (Annex 6A), and three PhD thesis completed, incorporating an extensive database acquired from ICSF. All of the papers are collaborative, reflecting the nature of the Facility, with 90% in journals with citation indices above 1, and 30% above 2. This highlights the commitment of the Facility to produce and foster quality, international-level science, and tangible measures for the NERC portfolio.

PERSONAL RESEARCH – ADDING VALUE

Whilst NIGFSC-approved projects remain core to ICSF's mission, Dr. Boyce is a co-PI/named collaborator on 4 successful grants including 2 from Thematic programmes (Micro-to-Macro and Ocean Margins). Support to one "new researcher" NERC Grant bid is under review (Leicester), and a successful collaborative grant (with SOC, Soton) has been obtained from the Swedish GEORANGE programme. In addition, Dr. Boyce actively seeks to take part in interdisciplinary larger scale research, for example, ICSF is contributing to a NERC Consortium bid (see Future Developments below) involving mathematical modellers, engineering geologists, microbiologists, mineralogists and more to identify and track redox processes which are key in the natural attenuation of acid mine drainage, with potential for other potentially toxic soil-anoxic/oxic environments (e.g. paddy fields). This project is also closely linked with industry, and will utilise the newly-created CL:AIRE National Mine Site Remediation Research Facility.

PROJECT DEVELOPMENT – SUSTAINED TEMPO

A scrutiny of time-cost allocations of ICSF indicates that each year three to four new approved projects can be taken on by ICSF. All applications have been successful since the previous review 1999, and all have the training of a PhD student at their centre.

Dr. Boyce has made good progress in his career this year through his efforts as ICSF manager. For example, he is an elected Council member of the SGA (Europe's pre-eminent Applied Geological Society), and has been invited onto the organising committee of the Fermor Flagship meeting of the Geological Society (Cardiff, 19-21 August, 2003), where he is organising the Session entitled: *Sedimentary mineral deposits: do they constrain the ancient atmosphere and hydrosphere?* He gave an invited keynote address to the Irish Association for Economic Geology Weekend Conference on the evidence for basement interaction in the formation of the Irish base-metal ore province in May, 2002, as well as an invited talk to the SEG UK Student chapter on "*Latest views on the genesis of the Irish base-metal deposits: the world's most concentrated Zn province*". The subject of these talks was based largely on ICSF approved project work (IP/668/0900; IP/528/0997; IP/495/1096; IP/406/0294). He was also invited to be external examiner in two international PhD examinations (University of Orleans and University of Annaba).

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

ZAMBIAN COPPERBELT – PARADIGM SHIFT

The Zambian Copperbelt preserves a spectacular scale of mineralisation illustrated by the fact that despite the enormous quantities of ore extracted to date (~1.1 billion tonnes at 2.7% Cu) it is estimated that current reserves are ~260Mt or ore at 2.9% Cu, with a possible resource in excess of 2 billion tonnes at 2.5% Cu: a truly world class mineral province. Approved project IP/755/0302 with Dr. Roberts at SOC, involved S isotope analyses of petrographically well characterised samples, which indicated that the pre-eminent syngenetic model of ore formation is seriously under question, since true diagenetic pyrite (-17 to -1‰) has a totally different isotope signature compared to ore stage sulfides (-1.5 to +15‰) indicating that they were clearly not derived from the same source, which is a central tenet of the syngenetic model. The use of the *in situ* laser S system provided a resolution high enough to enable this distinction to be made. Prof. David Vaughan (U of Manchester) who reviewed the script for Geology, noted the vital importance of using the new technique and said the manuscript gave "...a new perspective on the origins of one of the world's great mineral deposits...". The paper is due out in the June issue. The PhD studentship was part sponsored by Anglo American plc, and they have agreed to sponsor a two year PDRA for the student, Ross McGowan.

DEVELOPMENTS IN UNDERSTANDING LASER-INDUCED S ISOTOPE FRACTIONATION

Laser heating of sulfides in the presence of O₂ - a technique pioneered by ICSF and SUERC, with part funding from NSS capital budget - is the most commonly used method of *in situ* sulfur isotope analysis. Previous work indicated that a small, but reproducible fractionation of ³⁴S/³²S exists between the product SO₂ gas, and the mineral. The magnitude of this fractionation varies with bond strength, as reflected in Gibbs free energy of formation. The correction factors are known for common sulfides and anhydrite, but not hitherto for stibnite and the sulfosalt minerals, which are important constituents of many classes of ore deposits. In our paper with Dr. Thomas Wagner (McGill University: Wagner et al., 2002 - see Annex 6A) the correlation of ΔG_{298}^0 with the laser correction factor for the sulfosalts fits well with the trend previously established for simple sulfides. There is an excellent correlation between the fractionation factor and mineral composition, a parameter that does result in bond strength variations (e.g. mole fraction of PbS in sulfosalts), allowing estimation of the correction factors for simple intermediate compositions. Finally, bond strength also varies with variation in inter-atomic distances, and we have therefore investigated the behaviour of stibnite, a strongly anisotropic mineral. Our results indicate that there is a significant variation in fractionation factor depending on crystal orientation. The fractionation factor along the prismatic b-axis, which displays the strongest chemical bonds (as monitored by the shortest bond lengths), is more negative (-1.7‰) than along the other crystallographic directions (-0.7‰ to -1.0‰), in full agreement with theoretical predictions. Reviewing the manuscript, Prof. Mike McKibben (UC Riverside) said of the paper "...it develops a very useful analysis and discussion of the significant effects of bond strength, solid-solution composition, and crystallographic orientation on the mineral-gas isotopic fractionation that is observed during laser ablation and isotopic analysis."

MULTI-SCALE FLUID-FLOW PATH ANALYSIS: MICRO-TO-MACRO PROJECT GOES TO FINAL REPORT, AND PUBLICATIONS

Isotopic analyses for the successful Micro-to-Macro multi-disciplinary collaborative project (GST/03/2653) centring on the giant Navan Zn+Pb deposit are complete, and the project has moved into the final report stage. Publications are in the course of preparation on petrography, geochemistry, structural development and modelling. The isotope analyses are now providing critical parameters for modelling of non-conservative components that undergo exchange with the rock during flow. We anticipate that progressive modification of these tracers during flow can be used to define flow directions. To this end, we will be using the accumulated dataset and existing constraints on end-member fluid compositions in the Irish orefield which our team has assembled largely through successful approved project bids (IP/668/0900; IP/572/0998; IP/528/0997; IP/495/1096; IP/406/0294), to inform fluid modelling codes developed at Yale, CSIRO and Imperial College to carry out isotopic modelling for the quantification of isotope exchange and fluid mixing processes.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK UPGRADING SULFUR SYSTEMS

With cooperative funding from NERC and SUERC, construction is under way on a new conventional S line. This is the workhorse line for conventional S analyses, and often the first line to be used by students undergoing any stable isotope training. The new layout has been designed to better facilitate student training, as well as acquire quality isotopic data. Separately, SUERC are funding a rebuilding of the laser S extraction line, which will employ similar ergonomics to the redesigned conventional line, again facilitating better training. NSS funding also purchased a digital image capture system for the laser S system, which will again prove extremely useful for student training and paper redaction purposes.

POLLUTION AND WASTE – EVOLUTION OF PORTFOLIO

In addition to the proposed truly multidisciplinary Consortium bid on the identification and tracking of redox fronts in naturally attenuated acid mine sites (which is anticipated to result in applications to NIGFSC), ICSF will also be involved in a project with colleagues in Manchester University's Environmental Geochemistry and Geomicrobiology Group (Drs Polya and Lloyd) centring on the potentially environmentally disastrous problem of environmental arsenic pollution in SE Asia and India. The group currently has two projects envisaged to involve ICSF in obtaining stable isotope analyses. Dr Polya has a NERC/CASE (with NIIM) PhD student starting work on controls on arsenic release from aquifer sediments. We believe that O and H isotopic analysis of arsenic contaminated groundwaters will be helpful in identifying pre-Pleistocene waters, and understanding their evolution. An additional benefit of involvement of the ICSF is the potential cross-over to the NERC ¹⁴C Laboratory for the dating of groundwaters (ICSF is already contributing to that application). In parallel, Dr. Lloyd (microbiologist) is studying experimentally the microbial controls on arsenic release rates. As release occurs through a process of reduction of Fe(III), we consider that it may be possible to use C and N isotope measurements as a tracer for concomitant oxidation of organic matter.

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Dr David Lynn
Director Science & Innovation Funding
Natural Environment Research Council
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January 12th 2004

Dear Dr. Lynn,

IMF/MEMF Annual Reports

I have great pleasure in presenting to you the annual reports of the Ion Microprobe Facility and the Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility. While the support for the MEMF is now being withdrawn, the IMF continues from strength to strength, and this report demonstrates the high calibre of the work in progress, as well as the continuing innovation and development that keeps this facility at the international forefront.

There are two points, which my committee has asked me to bring to your attention on behalf of the user community, in the hope that NERC will be able to provide some clear guidelines.

Firstly, there is the issue of continuing support for use of electron microprobes and other related facilities. Despite the withdrawal of support for the MEMF, these techniques remain widely used, and in particular the introduction of environmental SEM's means that a wide range of new applications in the environmental sciences are opening up. These laboratories are very expensive to operate, and the community would appreciate some guidance from NERC on the circumstances in which NERC PhD supervisors will be able to obtain additional funding from NERC for students to make use of Electron Optical Facilities in their own or other Universities.

A second, related question concerns the status of Edinburgh students making use of the IMF. Should they apply in the usual way to the steering committee for instrument time, and if not, are they eligible for support from NERC for the exceptional laboratory costs that their work will incur?

Yours sincerely

Bruce Yardley
Chair, IMF/MEMF Steering Committee

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE ION MICROPROBE FACILITY (IMF)	FUNDING Contract	AGREEMENT	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1987	TERM 5yrs
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

Facilities

The Ion Microprobe Facility (IMF) provides a unique service to the UK scientific community for microanalysis of a wide range of geological and environmental materials using SIMS (secondary ion mass spectrometry). A special feature of this technique is *in-situ* high spatial resolution (5 –20 µm) chemical analysis, which permits zones of minerals or fragments of shells to be analysed for a variety of elements and isotopes. Present facilities support analysis of a wide range of stable isotope ratios (H, B, C, O, S), trace elements (e.g. for rare-earth elements, large ion lithophile elements, high field strength elements) and light elements (H, Li, Be, B, C, N). Depth profiles of elemental or isotopic composition can also be obtained; this is particularly useful for diffusion studies. The Edinburgh instrument is unique in having been modified to permit the storage under vacuum of 8 samples at a time. This substantially improves the vacuum in the specimen chamber and thereby the isotopic and elemental analysis of elements such as H, C and N.

The Ion Microprobe Facility is located in the School of Geosciences, University of Edinburgh, and in addition to the Cameca ims-4f SIMS instrument also provides access to electron microprobe (EPMA) and analytical SEM facilities (including EDS, CL and EBSD), which may be used for characterisation of samples on site. Tephrochronology, involving high precision microanalysis of glasses to permit correlation of tephra layers for relative age dating, forms an important service. A new Cameca SX100 electron microprobe will be available in the FY 2003-2004.

Access and Training

Access to the Facility is by peer review via the IMF Steering Committee and is free for members of the NERC community; overseas users are charged at variable scales depending on the extent of collaboration with members of the NERC community. Advice on research strategy is given. All visitors to the IMF are trained in basic instrument operation and also in data reduction and interpretation. This 'hands-on' approach for all users contributes strongly to the training of the post-graduates and young post-doctoral researchers. Over 68 research students have been trained to use the ion microprobe and have discussed ion microprobe data in their theses. Over the last three years sixteen research students have been trained in electron microprobe analysis for tephrochronology.

Scientific Reputation

The IMF has a very strong international reputation, and has pioneered the development and application of stable isotope analysis techniques on insulating materials (e.g. silicates, carbonates). Such 'in-house' research developments have led to further demand on the Facility from the NERC community, particularly with respect to oxygen isotope analysis.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review:	
Need 5.0	Uniqueness 5.0	Quality of Service 5.0	Quality of Science & Training 5.0	Average 5.0

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 65%	Staff & Status Richard W Hinton (T2B) Nicola Cayzer (AR1B)	Next Review (January) 2007	Contract Ends (31 March) 2008
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k 129K	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k			
	Unit 1 62 per hour	Unit 2 250 per session	Unit 3						
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)									
2002-03	£122K	2003-04	£129K	2004-05	£139K	2005-06	£233K	2006-07	£245K

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
	6	1 or 2	1

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03) Tephrochronology Analytical Unit TAU GRADES = ()								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1 (1)	1	1					
Other academic	2	4 (2)	1					1
Students		2 (2)	2 (1)	1				
Pilot								
TOTAL	3 (1)	7 (4)	4 (1)	1				1
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years —1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002) TAU= ()								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1	1.7	.7					
Other Academic	1 (0.3)	4 (1)	2.3	0.3	0.3		1.3	
Students	1 (0.3)	1.3 (2.7)	1 (1.3)				.7	
Pilot								
TOTAL	3 (0.6)	7 (3.7)	4 (1.3)	0.3	0.3		2	

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY) TAU = ()								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects			3 (1)	1				
Other Academic			5 (1)	2 (2)				
Students			1 (3)	(3)				
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY) TAU = ()										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		
19 (10)	4 (1)	3 (6)	2 (4)		12 (3)					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		
24	4.3 (0.3)	11.3	5		12					0.7

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
15 (4)			(6) 4	
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
16.3 (5.3)			7.7 (8.7)	

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type) both IMF and TAU										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
	34						34	22	11	1
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	100%									
OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years) both IMF and TAU										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
	62.7						62.7	31.3	23.7	7.7
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	100%									

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

New Developments:

Following the JIF EMMAC award, two major new instruments have been delivered and installed during 2002/3. The first was a Cameca SX100 electron microprobe, which was delivered in June 2002 and finally completed all its acceptance tests in March 2003. The second was the Cameca ims-1270 ion microprobe which passed its pre-delivery tests in Paris in December 2002 and was delivered just prior to Christmas. After assembly and initial vacuum, electronic and mechanical checks the ims-1270 passed most of its standard delivery tests by the end of April 2003. Some stringent additional Specification Tests, designed by the IMF staff will be completed in May 2003. These additional tests will check the instrument's multicollector capability for isotope measurement. The implementation of additional computer control of secondary ion focussing has resolved significant problems associated with making analyses on grains which were either a long distances apart, or were present in separate mounts.

Implementation of this JIF award has permitted creation not only of a new ims-1270 laboratory but also the complete renovation of existing facilities. The Philips XL 30 CP SEM has been upgraded to include an EBSD system for crystallographic orientation measurement and improved imaging and EDS software. The combined suite of ims-1270, ims-4f ion microprobes, SX100 electron microprobe and Philips XL 30 CP SEM now have common electrical, air-conditioning and cooling water supplies to permit high specification control of room and instrument temperature. Installation of UPS (uninterruptible power supply) units for the ims-1270 and SX100 will provide a clean electrical supply and a backup on power failure. The system on the ims-1270 and SX-100 was tested during two short-lived interruptions in power due to external building works. It is hoped to supply similar protection to the ims-4f in the near future.

JIF funds and earned income was used to update the ims-4f computer control to a Windows and PC based system by installation of a new computer interface and software supplied by C. Evans and Assoc. The new software is structured in a similar way to the original system and has not created any significant problems for existing users.

Simone Kasemann has filled the new staff post for ion microprobe studies provided initially by JIF (to be taken over by the University of Edinburgh after 3 years). She has previous experience on an ion microprobe and has combined well with existing staff to provide continued access to the ims-4f over the second half of the year as pre- and post-delivery work on the ims-1270 has proceeded.

Instrument usage:

- The NSS usage on the ims-4f has been unaffected by the new instrument installation and the total operational hours were close to the 5 year average.
- Access to the Cameca SX100 for tephrochronological studies has commenced.
- It has proved possible to train inexperienced users on the ims-4f to undertake stable isotope analysis for relatively short projects of a few week's duration and to implement single day access for short projects.
- Publications by the ion microprobe facility continue at high level with 22 papers published in refereed journals including ion microprobe and electron microprobe data (18 of which are from non-Edinburgh University users and including 4 on tephrochronology).

There has been some minor disruption of the booking system due to uncertainties in the manufactures completion date of the new ims-1270 and the timing of its pre-delivery tests. One of the ims-1270 pre-delivery visits to the Cameca factory involved all IMF staff resulting in closure of the laboratory for a week. However, most users have been scheduled for access at their preferred dates. The Kings Building site was struck by lightning during the summer and a number of instruments on the campus were damaged. The ion microprobe's main isolating transformer was damaged and had to be replaced. A new transformer, took a week to make, deliver and install.

Some instrument time was allocated for Simone Kasemann to familiarise herself with the Edinburgh ims-4f. Significant internal use during this year was also dedicated to the investigation of new analytical procedures for light element isotopic analysis, particularly for lithium and boron. A further week was set aside for the installation of new instrument control software and associated computer interface.

The combination of late delivery of the SX100 and knock-on effects on the refurbishment of laboratory space necessitated a longer suspension of tephrochronology services than was initially intended. However, the SX100 has now been installed and passed its specification tests.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

The ims-4f is a highly versatile instrument and scientific research during the financial year studies have included NERC ENRI and FORESIGHT topics on: Global Change; Natural Resources; Waste and Pollution; Structure and Properties of the Earth's Subsurface, and the Micro-to-Macro Thematic Programme.

The ims-4f instrument usage during the year continues to highlight the instrument's versatility with projects including oxygen, carbon and lithium isotopic analyses, trace element analysis (both in natural samples and experimental run products) and depth profile measurements for diffusion studies. Science supported by the facility is described in detail in Annex 9, the Annual Science Report. Several highlights of research in 2002-2003 are:

- The subduction hypothesis for the origin of eclogitic material in the Earth's mantle was given major support by new ion microprobe measurements. For the first time oxygen isotope data on minute mineral inclusions in natural diamonds were combined with carbon isotope determinations on the host diamond. The results for both isotopes are in harmony with derivation from subducted ocean floor parent material.
- Definite correlations were demonstrated between trace element profiles in recent speleothems from South Africa and rainfall records in 2002/3. Variations between years, and over extended periods of time, have been postulated to be record changes in climate but have previously not been tested against known climate records. It was demonstrated that the Sr/Ba ratios best encodes changes in growth rate and permits identification of recent to prehistoric drought events.
- The possibilities of using trace element compositions of chamber walls of foraminifera tests as proxies for seasonal seawater temperature variation were also advanced. Correlations between temperature and chemistry were unproven due to problems associated with silicate mineral contamination and extremely thin chamber walls (often <15 – 20 microns thick). Chamber walls of two forams from 100m depth in the Celtic Sea, based on multiple analyses of each chamber wall, show similar Sr/Ca variations, pointing to the encoding of seasonal variations in bottom water temperature.
- Variations in Sr content of minerals during crystallisation are often thought to reflect mixing of melts from a number of sources. However, a study of trace element partitioning between aluminous clinopyroxene and anhydrous silicate melt has shown that positive or negative Sr anomalies in melts can be produced simply by changes in P and T of melting, without the need to invoke the addition of enriched or depleted source materials.
- Tephrochronological analyses have been combined with palaeoenvironmental records to determine whether changes to wetter conditions or volcanic activity were the cause of a widespread social collapse during the Later Bronze Age 1200-800 BC. The results of these investigations do not support the theory that climate changes or Icelandic volcanic eruptions during the past 4,000 years were detrimental to marginal agricultural settlements in the Strath of Kildonan.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

The ims-1270 has only recently been installed and, as it is a major jump in complexity compared to the ims-4f, it is anticipated that it will take from between 6 months to a year before its full analytical capabilities are realised. In particular, operation in multicollector mode is expected to lead to a significant improvement of precision but it is a relatively new instrument development and a new area for IMF staff (especially for multi-electron multiplier operation).

Future developments for the ims-4f instrument will be inextricably linked to progress made on the new ims-1270 instrument. The ims-4f, thanks to continued upgrading by NERC funds, continues to perform extremely well in comparison to newer (computer controlled) ims-6f instruments. It also continues to be an extremely reliable instrument; this is essential when analytical time is often booked up to six months in advance. It is envisaged that any U/Pb geochronological research using the high-resolution capabilities of the ims-1270 will require complementary trace element work on the ims-4f. Work on zircons, in particular, will also require significant individual mineral grain characterisation on the SEM by both Backscattered Secondary Electron (BSE) and Cathodoluminescence (CL) imaging. Structural determination (to determine degree of crystallinity) using EBSD is also likely to be necessary to resolve mineralogical versus age differences. The multi-sample airlock and high vacuum performance of the ims-4f still makes it the instrument of choice for hydrogen concentration and isotopic measurements. It is therefore believed that demand on the ims-4f will increase over the next few years.

Our reference

Your reference

Direct line/e-mail

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**School of Life and
Environmental Sciences**

3rd July 2003

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Dr D. Lin,
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NERC LIFE SCIENCES MASS SPECTROMETRY FACILITY

Dear Dr Lin,

The annual reports of the three nodes of the Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility are testament to the continuing success of the Facility. Each of the nodes received consistent highest scores for need, uniqueness, quality of service and quality of science and training in the review for the financial year 2002-2003. The combined nodes of LSMSF supported 38 projects during 2002/2003. A significant number of these projects contributed the NERC thematic programmes (GANE, Soil Biodiversity), as well as to responsive mode funded projects and Ph.D. projects. During 2002 the Facility achieved an excellent output of 35 peer reviewed publications, many of which included facility staff as authors. The training of graduate students is an important activity undertaken by the staff of LSMSF, resulting in a number of Ph.D theses, most supported by NERC studentships.

During 2002/2003 the Organic Mass Spectrometry node of LSMSF received a significant level of refurbishment and additional instrumentation that was supported by funds secured from SRIF. While this will strengthen the excellent reputation and capability of the node, it did cause very considerable disruption during the year, with equipment 'down time'. Nonetheless the node sustained a good performance for which the staff must be congratulated. The ¹⁵N SIF node is preparing for its imminent move to Lancaster University, which is likely to impose some disruption during 2003/2004.

While the three elements of LSMSF have operated in a complementary fashion for many years, we are always seeking ways to maximise operational efficiency and to deliver a more streamlined service to NERC users. Together the three nodes provide

THE QUEEN'S AWARDS
FOR ENTERPRISE
INTERNATIONAL TRADE
2001

THE QUEEN'S
ANNIVERSARY PRIZES
FOR HIGHER AND FURTHER EDUCATION
2000

Head of School: Professor J Laybourn-Parry

Professor D Archer, Professor C J Barnard, Professor J M Behnke, Professor J Bradley,

Professor J F Peberdy.

support for virtually all applications of organic and light stable isotope mass spectrometry, however, there are potential problems with respect to new applicants and their understanding of the services available from each node. Applicants may make a number of applications to the different nodes, which results in confusion and an inefficient use of Facility staff time. In future the LSMSF will operate a single entity. Not only will this increase the efficiency of service, it will enable synergistic operation of the three nodes by facilitating sharing of knowledge, expertise and analytical capabilities. Moreover, it provides a level of insurance in the event of serious instrument failure. In future applicants will make a single electronic application – effectively a one-stop-shop. The advantage of this is that it enables LSMSF to direct an application to the appropriate node(s). The current Directors of each node will undertake the role of LSMSF Director in rotation.

In summary the LSMSF has sustained a strong performance during 2002/2003 and has implemented measures to enhance the quality of its service to the NERC community.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Johanna Laybourn-Parry". The signature is written in a cursive style with a long horizontal flourish at the end.

Johanna Laybourn-Parry
Chairman NERC LSMSF

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope Facility	FUNDING Contract	AGREEMENT	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1994	TERM 5 yr.
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The *raison d'être* for the LSCSIF is to provide access for training and research for the scientific community in the application of:

1. Natural abundance $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$, $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$, and D/H of bulk organic matter and $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ measurements of molecular oxygen to the study of animal ecology, particularly food webs and elemental cycling.
2. Isotopically enriched water (D_2^{18}O) to energy expenditure studies.

The LSCSIF is unique amongst the NSS funded isotope facilities as it is the only one that has the capacity for doubly labelled water (DLW) analysis, and has also offered measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of molecular oxygen. The new facility manager, Dr. Jason Newton, and the support scientist, Dr. Rona McGill, have 12+ years practical experience each of stable isotope mass spectrometry. Since Facility inception (1994-), there has been a shift in demand from DLW analysis to natural abundance measurements. DLW studies this year required approximately 16% of facility resources, and now comprise only 21% of applications (average over three years). Demand for natural abundance measurements continues to rise, and we are in the process of bringing D/H analysis by continuous flow isotope ratio mass spectrometry routinely on line to meet demand from the User Community.

Applications made to the Facility are peer-reviewed by an independent Steering Committee, and if successful are granted access, with analysis 'free at the point of delivery'. A collaborative relationship (advice with project design and data redaction from Facility staff, in addition to analytical support) is considered a productive *modus operandi* for all concerned. Where it is apparent that the number of analyses required from a given PI is likely to lead to a distortion in the resources available for the whole community if channelled through the Facility at our current level of NSS support, Facility staff have been successful in helping PI's seek more appropriate NERC funding. This approach will remain policy. Appropriate pilot projects, performed at the joint discretion of Facility Service Head and Manager, use minimal resources but deliver data useful in deciding whether to proceed with a larger application to the Facility, or for NERC grant funding. This is an effective use of resources for if it transpires there is no merit in proceeding further, NERC saves resources by preserving steering committee, grant review panel and Facility time.

100% of Facility capacity is dedicated to projects approved by peer review and minor pilot projects. The NSS support is subsidised by the SUERC through for example access to SUERC financed equipment, expertise from SUERC based and funded academic staff, and technical support in an informal capacity, for example maintenance of equipment used by the Facility but not purchased by NSS.

The SLA agreement allocates 50% of time to lab. Work on approved projects, 10% to technique development, 25% to Facility co-ordination /administration, and 15% to PDRF/A personal research. The previous Facility manager, Dr. Waldron has been successful in gaining one Royal Society, three NERC non-thematic and one EU grant since 1998; thus the facility consumable budget has not been used to support her personal research, which contributes to NERC ENRI's of Global Change and Pollution & Waste and complements the Facility contribution to the ENRI's of Biodiversity and Global Change.

To date all Ph.D. students and most post-doctoral researchers named on approved projects, including NERC fellows, have been trained to carry out their own analyses. This NERC priority (Skilled People, Strategic Plan, 2002-2007) is encouraged for the following reasons: a) the output of trained personnel contributes to the long-term health of the science base, b) such training significantly enhances the students' portfolio of skills, c) the analyst develops a more critical eye for data quality and c) it is an effective way to manage resources.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: Jan 2003		
Need α5	Uniqueness α5	Quality of Service α5	Quality of Science & Training α5	Average α5

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 50%	Staff & Status Dr. Jason Newton, Facility Manager, RA2 Dr. Rona McGill, Support Scientist, RA1A	Next Review (January) 2008	Contract Ends (31 March) 2009
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k 12	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k 17.7	Income £k	Full cash cost £k 120.22			
	Unit 1 0.282	Unit 2	Unit 3						
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)									
2003-04	£112,550	2004-05	~£134,000	2005-06	~£140,000	2006-07	~£148,000	2007-08	~£156,000

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NERC Isotope Life Sciences	8	2	^{15}N SIF, OMSF

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		2		1				
Other academic			1				1	
Students			3					
Pilot								
TOTAL		2	4	1			1	
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years —1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	0.3	1	1.3					
Other Academic	0.3	0.3						
Students		1.3	2.3					
Pilot								
TOTAL	0.7	2.7	3.7					

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects		1	2					
Other Academic								
Students			1					
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)									<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG						
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other		
19	6	8	3	1	4							

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)									<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG						
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other		
12	4.0	5.0	2.0		3							

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
10	1		8	
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
7.0			5.0	

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
				13			13	4	8	1

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
	1	2		16		

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
		1.3		4.0			7.3	5.3	0.3	1.7

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
	0.3	1.3		9.7		

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OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

This has been a year of change and progression for the facility, with a major new analytical technique being developed for routine use, and a change of personnel mid-year. After eight years with the Facility, Dr. Waldron felt it timely to pursue her personal research interests, and in September 2002 was awarded a NERC Advanced Fellowship. Dr. Jason Newton took over as Facility Manager, and a new post of Support Scientist, which was taken by Dr. Rona McGill, was created to replace and augment the remaining 50% technical support. Past and present facility staff overlapped by a month and ensured a smooth changeover with a thorough introduction to the workings of the facility. The facility website (<http://www.gla.ac.uk/surrc/research/nerclifesci.html>) has been updated to reflect the staff changes, and Dr. Newton has also updated the publications page (<http://www.gla.ac.uk/surrc/research/facpub.html>), with links to online publications so that new users can see the results of the high quality science performed at the LSCSIF. Dr Waldron represented the facility, chairing a session at the International biennial conference, Applications of Stable Isotope Techniques to Ecological Studies in Flagstaff, Arizona; and Drs Newton and McGill represented the facility at the annual British Ecological Society conference in York, in December.

(1) TRAINING – THE CORE EFFORT

With all approved projects, the isotopic analyses are designed to complement field based observations. Nearly half of the projects accommodated during 02/03 were student projects and required visits to the lab since our strategy is to fully involve the Ph.D. student in the analytical process. To date, none of the students we have trained have had previous experience of high precision quantitative stable isotope analysis, and this is their first introduction to vacuum-line cryogenic chemistry and/or isotope-ratio mass spectrometry. The, often intensive, training they receive within the LSCSIF therefore develops skills different and complementary to those required in the field. The combination of laboratory analysis and data interpretation with field skills is considered an attractive attribute of our 'alumni' and fulfils NERC's responsibilities to students and fellows as part of their skill development portfolio. Respondents of our User Survey described the quality of training as well as overall service as 'excellent' or 'good'.

(2) QUALITY OF SCIENCE

The quality of applications to the Facility has remained consistently high. Eight applications were received again this year, two were graded α_4 , four α_3 and one α_2 . One application, which was passed on to us from another facility, was recommended for resubmission. It is felt that this proposal was unsuccessful in the steering committee at first reading because it was not subject to the usual informal discussions between facility staff and the user prior to submission. Four manuscripts have been published in peer-reviewed journals this year, two are currently in review and five are at an advanced stage of preparation. Two PhD dissertations have been awarded and another submitted, while at the BES winter meeting 3 oral presentations was given, one poster, and at the International Conference on Applications of Stable Isotope Techniques to Ecological Studies in Flagstaff 4 poster presentations were made.

(3) PROJECT PROFILE – CONTINUING DEVELOPMENT

Another year when a large number of high quality applications has been received. Despite an initial settling-in period for the new facility personnel, the standard has remained very high. Of the seven successful applications received five are from new PIs and two from more regular applicants. With these new applicants the shift in user interest is towards increased demand for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analysis of organic material. Dr Bearhop, previously trained in the facility for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analysis as a student, fronts his first application as PI, exploiting the development of D/H analyses in the facility. This illustrates the way in which the facility keeps abreast of new developments and can respond to the increasingly sophisticated demands of our recurrent users. While 5 of the new projects are based around analysis of bird feathers, an area of acknowledged expertise in the facility, we are receiving an increasing number of enquiries for projects concerning coastal and marine fish and animals. It will be interesting to see if isotope applications in this area flourish to the same extent as the strong terrestrial demand of past years.

On-going demand for facility time remains healthy, with four projects just beginning and twelve already in-hand of which nine are anticipated to reach completion in the next six months. Approaches have already been made concerning another 4-5 projects for the next meeting of the steering committee in May, one of which has already been submitted regarding jellyfish impact on fisheries stocks.

(4) CAPITAL PROCUREMENT

The capital bid granted for 02/03 for a new analyser (to be linked to an existing SUERC mass spectrometer) will have sufficiently high furnace temperatures to permit pyrolysis of organic matter for measurement of D/H. This will allow us to keep abreast with the North American isotope ecology community using bulk measurements to study ecological phenomena such as migration. Installing, testing and rendering this analysis routine will be a priority in the short term, and has already generated considerable interest from the ecological community. A new microbalance with improved precision/accuracy was purchased with the joint capital bid with the ICSF granted for 03/04. This enhances the facility's ability to serve its users and offsets the increased workload on the other balances.

(5) PERSONAL RESEARCH

Drs. Newton and McGill have been working in the facility for just seven months and while concentrating on the staff training they are receiving via their OU Biology course, both are exploring areas of personal interest. Dr Newton's interest in avian migration studies and Dr McGill's interest in marine food webs and seabirds complement areas of higher demand from the current user community.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Three highlights of this year's science are given below:-

- 1.) The main new technological advance this year has been the ongoing development of a system, which will analyse stable hydrogen isotope ratios in organic material. This has numerous ecological applications, but the principal one is the study of animal migration. This relies on the premise that latitude is reflected in the hydrogen isotope ratio of precipitation, which is in turn reflected in hydrogen isotope ratios of biologically synthesised organic material (e.g. feathers or hair). The first investigation (Dr. S. Bearhop, NERC Research Fellow, Univ. Glasgow) using this apparatus will analyse hydrogen isotope ratios in the feathers of the blackcap (*Sylvia atricapilla*) which breeds in summer in Germany and winters in Portugal and (increasingly) in the UK. We have already shown that blackcap feathers grown in UK and Portugal are isotopically distinguishable, so it is therefore possible to recognise the wintering areas of Blackcaps breeding in summer in Germany, in order to make some conclusions regarding the reasons for the change in wintering habitat.
- 2.) Dr. B. Tigar (Univ. Paisley) has used stable isotope analyses to study *Prostephanus truncatus* (Horn), an invasive, post-harvest beetle pest of maize in Latin America. Using Mexico as a study site, carbon isotope signatures of *P. Truncatus* captured using pheromone traps, revealed that this pest can complete its life cycles outwit the maize store (previously unconfirmed). Further, regional differences existed in beetle habitat selection. For example, *P. Truncatus* from North West Mexico (Sonora) were highly ^{13}C -depleted, indicating that they had not consumed maize even though captured close to stores of agricultural maize.
- 3.) Mangroves may provide nursery sites for commercially and artisanally important species of fish. Stable isotopes of oxygen and carbon preserved in fish ear bones (otoliths) may serve as natural tags to identify migration. In Gazi Bay, Kenya, Dr. M. Huxham is using the steep gradients in temperature, salinity and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ which exist between mangrove, sea grass, and the offshore coral reef environment, to assess whether differences in the oxygen and carbon isotope ratios of the otolith can be used to detect fish moving between habitats at different stages in their life, and whether juveniles use the mangroves as nursery sites.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analysis of organic material remains the predominant requirement of LSCSIF users. In addition to four out of the seven new proposals this year requesting this analysis, three new applications are also in the pipeline for next year, which also need C and N isotope data. Therefore support for maintenance of the two CF-IRMS instruments we access from SUERC is paramount. It is anticipated that while current instrument availability is effectively keeping pace with user demand for C and N isotope analyses: new technique developments such as D/H work, will have considerable influence on mass spectrometer scheduling and potentially necessitate an addition to the instrumental capabilities of the facility.

Our aim is to make D/H analysis of organic material a routine measurement in the near future - the technique is already being used to look at the migration of blackcaps, and two additional projects have recently been accepted which will utilise the same methodology for other avian migratory systems. This technique is likely to become an important part of the analytical portfolio we offer the Life Sciences Community, in collaboration with SUERC.

This year we began our first application measuring the C and O isotopic composition of biogenic carbonates - in this case fish otoliths. The analyses for this project were carried out using bulk measurements on separated otoliths, but in the future, laser-ablation carbonate analysis (traditionally in the domain of isotope geology) could be used to analyse incremental growth rings in the otolith and thus provide a detailed history of population movements.

The facility, which was considered along with OMSF and 15NSIF in this year's Service Review, has achieved its target of continued funding for a 5-year period. The merger between the three facilities, which will produce the Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility, will require a significant amount of coordination in the short term between us and the other members in Merlewood and Bristol to form a "one-stop-shop" for our users. Whilst all three facilities already share a Steering Committee and direct new applications to the most appropriate laboratory, we will fuse our paperwork and advertising (i.e. our homepages) to reflect the new organisation. It is hoped that this may also encourage some interdisciplinary applications, exploiting the expertise of more than one lab. Any short-term costs in time will be outweighed by long-term benefits in efficiency in service use and value for money.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

School of Earth Sciences
University of Leeds
Leeds LS2 9JT

Dr David Lynn
Director Science & Innovation Funding
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU

January 12th 2004

Dear Dr. Lynn,

IMF/MEMF Annual Reports

I have great pleasure in presenting to you the annual reports of the Ion Microprobe Facility and the Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility. While the support for the MEMF is now being withdrawn, the IMF continues from strength to strength, and this report demonstrates the high calibre of the work in progress, as well as the continuing innovation and development that keeps this facility at the international forefront.

There are two points, which my committee has asked me to bring to your attention on behalf of the user community, in the hope that NERC will be able to provide some clear guidelines.

Firstly, there is the issue of continuing support for use of electron microprobes and other related facilities. Despite the withdrawal of support for the MEMF, these techniques remain widely used, and in particular the introduction of environmental SEM's means that a wide range of new applications in the environmental sciences are opening up. These laboratories are very expensive to operate, and the community would appreciate some guidance from NERC on the circumstances in which NERC PhD supervisors will be able to obtain additional funding from NERC for students to make use of Electron Optical Facilities in their own or other Universities.

A second, related question concerns the status of Edinburgh students making use of the IMF. Should they apply in the usual way to the steering committee for instrument time, and if not, are they eligible for support from NERC for the exceptional laboratory costs that their work will incur?

Yours sincerely

Bruce Yardley
Chair, IMF/MEMF Steering Committee

SERVICES & FACILITIES (DRAFT) ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility MEMF	FUNDING Contract PAYG	AGREEMENT F/14/32	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1996	TERM 3 year
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The Manchester Electron Microprobe Facility (MEMF) provides access to state-of-the-art electron beam-induced X-ray microanalysis methods. These include techniques for determining elemental distribution (element mapping) and quantification on a micron scale of major, minor and trace elements within solid materials including minerals, rocks, soils and sediments and artefacts of archaeological interest. Microprobe analysis also provides essential characterisation of materials prior to studies employing other advanced techniques.

The service is designated for UK based researchers (both students and more established workers) who operate within the NERC remit area (primarily Earth Science, Environmental Science and Science-Based Archaeology).

In addition to the access to instrumentation, users are trained in the use of the equipment and given advice on the interpretation and evaluation of the data that they acquire. This advice is provided both by the staff of the Facility and through discussions with academic staff with the relevant expertise in the Department of Earth Sciences, University of Manchester. The MEMF is committed to developing the applications of microbeam analytical methods, not only in the Earth Sciences, but also in wide fields of environmental research and in science-based archaeology.

Instrumentation in the facility currently available to the NERC service:

CAMECA SX100

Fully configured electron probe microanalyser, with 5 wavelength dispersive spectrometers and integrated PGT IMIX energy dispersive spectrometer. Confocal zoom optical polarising microscope (x100 to x800 magnification) and electron imaging (SEI & BEI). Spectrometer/analysing crystal combinations have been selected to optimise performance for a wide range of mineralogical analysis. Determinations may be made for the elements beryllium to uranium in the periodic table. Detection limits of the order of a few tens of ppm for many elements can be achieved. One spectrometer is configured to enable oxidation state studies to be performed.

CAMBRIDGE GEOSCAN

This completely rebuilt GEOSCAN is fitted with an energy dispersive analysis system (PGT Avalon 4000). It is very easy to use and is ideal for certain visiting workers. Spot analyses for major and minor elements can be obtained at the rate of about 1 per minute with a detection limit of about 0.2wt. %. Only light optical (polarised transmitted and reflected) viewing is available, so this machine is best used for studying coarse and medium grained rocks in thin section.

JEOL JSM 6400 Analytical SEM

The JSM 6400 is fitted with an energy dispersive analysis system (PGT IMIX-PC) with low atomic number capabilities, backscattered electron detector, cathodoluminescence detector and a liquid nitrogen cold stage. This machine is most appropriate for users requiring quantitative analyses of very fine grained rocks (e.g., slates) which requires the probe to be accurately placed using backscattered electron imaging; also for the analysis of unstable hydrous or volatile rich samples (e.g., Na-rich hydrous minerals and glasses) taking advantage of the cooling stage facility. The instrument is also has a JEOL 'Semafore' digital image acquisition and archiving system.

The X-ray analysis system fitted to this instrument has a feature known as PTS (Position-Tagged Spectrometry). This allows X-ray data to be collected from each pixel point within a selected field of view of the sample, over a period (typically) of some 30 minutes acquisition time. The image, with associated analytical X-ray data, is automatically saved and may then be viewed and processed, off-line, using a remote computer equipped with the PGT software.

Instrumentation in the facility not currently available to the NERC service:

PHILIPS ESEM-FEG Analytical Environmental SEM

This instrument was purchased with JIF funding and installed in September 2001. The instrument is equipped with GATAN 'Alto' cryo system and PGT 'Spirit' X-ray analysis system. It permits microanalytical investigations of 'environmental' specimens and certain biomaterials.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review:		
Need 3.5	Uniqueness 4	Quality of Service 3.5	Quality of Science & Training 3.5	Average 3.63

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 25%	Staff & Status	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March) 2002
	Mr D.A. Plant: Senior Experimental Officer, Service Manager - 30% NERC Dr. C.L. Hayward: PDRA - 100% NERC (to Aug. 2002) Dr. P. Hill: PDRA (half-time October 2002 - March 2003) Mr S. Caldwell: SEM Technician - 20% NERC		

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £40k	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend nil	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3			
	.4	.25				

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2002-03	40k	2003-04	20k	2004-05	2004-06	2006-07

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
IMF	6	2	Ion Microprobe

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other academic		1						
Students		1	2		1			
Pilot								
TOTAL		2	2		1			

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years —1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	.5	1.4	.33					
Other Academic		1.3	1.4	.33				
Students		.66	1.9	1			.33	
Pilot								
TOTAL	.5	3.36	3.63	1.33			.33	

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)							
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot
NERC Grant projects		2					
Other Academic		2					
Students		2	2	1	1		
Pilot							

USER PROFILE (current FY)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other			
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC					
14						3	7	3		4			

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other			
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC					
12.6						5.66	6.66	4.66		3.33			

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
6	-	1	7	-

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
5	1	0	8	-

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
-	10	-	-	-	-	-	10	8	1	1

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
21%	79%	-	-	-	-	-

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
2	28	-	-	-	-	-	30	24	1	5

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
12%	88%	-	-	-	-	-

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Demand for the service has been exceptionally heavily during the first year of ramp-down funding. This has resulted in an additional forty-two sessions of instrument time being used, over and above the funding level in place for the year

The MEMF has continued to provide essential support for research, across a wide range of fields relevant to the NERC mission. It is also notable that projects employing more recently developed microanalytical techniques (e.g. LA-ICP-MS) often require complementary electron microprobe studies to facilitate proper interpretation of results.

Analytical programs have been undertaken for researchers from the following departments and institutions:

Earth Sciences, Cardiff University
Earth Sciences, University of Liverpool
Geology, University of Leicester
Earth Sciences, Birkbeck College, University of London
Earth Sciences and Geography, Keele University
GEMRU, University of Gloucestershire
Environmental Sciences, University of East Anglia
Geography, University of Liverpool
Environmental and Geographical Sciences, Manchester Metropolitan University
Environmental Science, University of Stirling (two projects)
Archaeological Sciences, University of Bradford
Archaeology, University of Glasgow
Archaeology (formerly, Archaeology and Prehistory), University of Sheffield

The MEMF laboratories are now in excellent order following the major refurbishment that took place in the previous reporting period. Whilst similar laboratory refurbishments were in progress at Edinburgh and the tephrochronology unit service was unavailable for a period during this year, tephra analyses were carried out at the MEMF for one project.

Considerable time has been spent in collaboration with workers in soil science from the University of Stirling in suitably preparing large-area thin sections of soils for microprobe investigations. Analytical work has taken place on two of five projects from this institution, and novel approaches to processing data derived from these investigations have been developed.

Developmental work on analytical techniques in new areas has been ongoing throughout the reporting period. 'Light' element analysis procedures have been approached on two fronts; in conjunction with Manchester based NERC funded research student, Mr M Rigby, and via industrial interest and collaboration with BNFL. Trace Element studies in sphalerite and other sulphides were conducted over a period of several months by visiting Marie Curie Fellow, Francesco Di Benedetto, Dept. Scienze della Terra, Firenze, Italy.

The extensive usage of the SX100 instrument gave rise to a number of malfunctions of the sample stage of this instrument. These problems were rectified by several engineer service visits at the beginning of 2003. Although some instrument time was lost as a result of this, at no point was user access to the NERC service compromised.

The period of employment for NERC PDRA, Dr. Chris Hayward (funded by this contract) concluded in August 2002 (third anniversary of appointment, i.e. six months overrun into this financial year). Although a three-month continuation contract had been arranged, Dr. Hayward was unable to take this up, as he had accepted a full-time position as a microprobe specialist in the Department of Earth Sciences at the University of Cambridge. His new appointment will permit him to complete his microprobe-based research projects commenced at the MEMF, with particular emphasis on the collaborative work undertaken with BNFL, as detailed in the previous years report.

The appointment of Dr. Hayward, to his new position at Cambridge coincided with the retirement of Dr. Stephen Reed and the installation of a new CAMECA SX 100 instrument at that institution. It is gratifying to note that the period of 'apprenticeship' in the technique of electron probe microanalysis undertaken by Dr. Hayward at the MEMF will now provide added value to the UK earth science community. We wish him well in his future career.

Dr Paddy Hill was awarded a short time fixed contract to work in the MEMF on a half-time basis between October 2002 and March 2003 as Dr. Hayward's replacement.

The MEMF was pleased to receive a visit in March 2003 from David Brown, NERC director of Science, as part of a wider visit to the JIF-funded Williamson Research Centre.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

The MEMF has continued to support a wide range of science during 2002-03. Including fundamental geological studies by NERC postgraduate students and senior scientists, along with science-based archaeology investigations and environmental science projects.

Electron microprobe analysis is central to the work being done on gabbro cumulates from the Troodos ophiolite, Cyprus (PG Graham Banks; PI Dr C. MacLeod). Microprobe and LA-ICP-MS analysis of zoning patterns in single crystals and closely spaced vertical chemical variations in these layered rocks are being used to understand crystal accumulation processes and melt migration in the lower oceanic crust. The ways in which rocks in the lower oceanic crust are formed through crustal scale subsidence or intrusion of sill swarms, remains enigmatic. This study is providing new understanding of this important part of the earth system.

The genesis and evolution of igneous and metamorphic rocks is the central area of several of the other ongoing geological studies being supported by the MEMF. Work based at Keele university, (PG C. Lewis; PI Prof. J. Winchester) involves microprobe analysis of the minerals in ultramafic rocks from the Leinster Massif, SE Ireland in order to elucidate their petrogenesis. The electron microprobe analysis of minerals in complex igneous and metamorphic rocks has also extended to work on the Norwegian Caledonides (PG Ruth Foreman; PI Dr J. Wheeler, Liverpool University) where detailed mineral analysis is being used for geothermometry and geobarometry, and to the Ista greenstone belt, West Greenland (Prof. H. Rollinson, University of Gloucestershire) where the growth chronology of garnets has been studied. The objective of a study undertaken by Dr Gavin Foster (NERC Postdoctoral fellow, Leicester University), and involving detailed textural and compositional studies of a wide range of samples, has been understanding the petrogenesis of metamorphic monazite. The microprobe studies of this mineral, a phase of particular importance in geochronology, have complemented work done at the NERC isotope facility (NIGL).

Although tephrochronology has not been generally undertaken at the MEMF, during the reporting period the Tephrochronology Unit at Edinburgh University was temporarily unavailable and PG D. Xia (Liverpool University; PI Dr J. Blomendal) performed a series of analyses on Icelandic tephra samples.

This period has seen continuing growth in the use of the electron microprobe for archaeological investigations. There is considerable interest in careful quantitative microanalysis and element mapping of a wide range of materials. PG E. Godfrey (PI Dr G. McDonnell, University of Bradford) concluded a study of the compositions of Saxon iron artefacts, whereas two separate investigations were concerned with the pigment "Egyptian Blue": Dr C. Jackson (Sheffield University) analysed a range of Egyptian blue glass samples; Anne Brysbaert (PI Dr R. Jones, University of Glasgow) investigated the pigments present in bronze age painted plasterwork.

An important newly developing area of research at the interface between archaeological and environmental investigations concerns the analysis of soils that have been affected by past human activities. Work based at the University of Stirling supported by NERC (PI D. Davidson) and the EC (Marie Curie Fellow Dr G. Dercon) is demonstrating the power of the electron microprobe in mapping a wide range of elements (P, Pb, Zn, Cu, Cd, Mg, Ca, Ti, Rb, Sr, K and Ba) in soils of archaeological interest. This mapping on centimetre and millimetre scales is facilitating comparisons of element distribution patterns in soils of known archaeological context with those where the nature of the human input remains to be established. In a detailed examination of anthrosols from different sites in NW Europe, the impact of agricultural activity is being evaluated much more effectively than in previous work (for example, through discriminating between different amorphous black materials by using C/O ratios).

The other important growth area in the application of MEMF resources concerns the wider field of environmental science. Here the (possibly unique for the UK) expertise of MEMF staff and related support staff in preparing delicate samples for analysis has proved invaluable. Studies undertaken in the reporting period have ranged from those with an essentially biosciences emphasis to those concerned with the mineralogy and geochemistry of anthropogenic sediments. In the former category work by Dr P. Bruneau (PI Dr I. Grieve, University of Stirling) on the effects of biodiversity on the pathways and rates of transfer of carbon in upland grassland soils has been initiated. In the latter case; Dr K. Taylor (Manchester Metropolitan University) has been involved in continuing work on the analysis of urban sediments recovered from the Manchester Ship Canal, a critical aspect of the evaluation of polluted areas of former industrial activity. Although involving similar analytical challenges, the continuing work by Dr K. Hudson-Edwards (Birkbeck College London) on heavy-metal polluted mine wastes embraces areas as diverse as Bolivia, Spain and Cyprus. Here, the characterisation of the mineralogical forms and compositions of phases carrying toxic elements (Pb, As, Sb, Cd, Hg, etc) represents a major step forward in risk assessment and the development of remediation strategies compared with previous bulk analysis of waste materials, or poorly defined selective extraction of toxic elements for analysis.

The period 2002-2003 has therefore seen ongoing applications of MEMF resources to fundamental geological problems alongside important new developments in applications to archaeology and environmental research. Access to world-class electron probe microanalysis facilities is clearly very important for a wide range of NERC science.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

The ramp-down funding period for the MEMF will extend into 2003-2004 but with reduced financial support. This will allow completion of work on existing approved projects.

The chairman of the IMF committee wrote to David Brown in May 2002 to express concern for the lack of future provision for microprobe analysis for NERC funded PhD students.

It should be noted that three installations of new microprobes have taken place during the last year in UK earth science/geology departments (Cambridge, Bristol and Edinburgh). Although these will provide microanalysis facilities within their universities, a considerable number of UK earth science, environmental science and science based archaeology departments remain, who have no direct access to microprobe instruments within their host institutions.

Department of Physics and Applied Physics,
University of Strathclyde,
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107 Rottenrow,
Glasgow G4 0NG

DATE: 11 July 2003

Dr David Lynn,
Director, Science and Innovation
NERC
Polaris House, North Star Avenue,
Swindon, Wilts SN2 1EU

Dear Dr Lynn,

I enclose a copy of the annual report of the Molecular Spectroscopy Facility (MSF). The Facility has had a very successful year and has supported a wide range of activities. In particular it has built on the success of the aerosol cell, which was designed and constructed at the MSF, to support an increasing range of projects related to atmospherically important aerosols. This led to a well attended "break out" session at the users meeting on June 12th which was concerned with future developments of this activity. At least twenty representative of research groups interested in aerosols attended this meeting which was organised by Dr Don Grainger of the University Of Oxford.

Not only is the aerosol research activity expanding, the presentations given at the users meeting under the general headings of "Atmospheric Chemistry" and "Climate Studies, Earth Observation and Optical Remote Sensing" demonstrate the support that the MSF is also providing for these key areas of atmospheric research.

A final area of user support, which is under development, is the provision of a portable Fourier transform infrared spectrometer. This is a new and valuable collaboration between two NERC facilities, the MSF and the Equipment Pool for Field Spectroscopy (EPFS). Following discussions between the Chairman of the MSF Steering Committee and Dr Ted Milton, the Director of the EPSF, at the users meeting on June 12th, it was suggested that the new service would be based upon the technical support of the MSF and the administrative skills of EPFS. The MSF Steering Committee endorsed these plans at its meeting on June 13th.

Recent changes in the management of the MSF have been brought about by the recent resignation of Dr Newnham, the Facility Scientist, and the ill health of Dr Ballard, the Head of the Facility. However, both the MSF Steering Committee and the Space Science and Technology Department of Rutherford Appleton Laboratory are confident that the facility will continue to deliver the excellent service that has been its hallmark since it was set up.

Yours sincerely,

Geoffrey Duxbury,

F.R.S.E., F Inst. P., Professor of Chemical Physics,
Chairman of the MSF Steering Committee

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Molecular Spectroscopy Facility – MSF	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT SLA	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1997	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The Molecular Spectroscopy Facility (MSF) provides world-class central laboratories, scientific equipment, training, scientific/technical support, and high-quality data for the UK environmental science community in support of a wide range of interdisciplinary research across the spectrum of the NERC remit and ENRIs. Infrared, visible, and ultraviolet spectroscopic data are increasingly important for studying the important chemical, physical, biological, and geological processes occurring in the natural environment. The MSF provides essential inputs to many key NERC science and technology areas, in particular Earth observation of the atmosphere and surface using optical remote sensing techniques, atmospheric chemistry, and climate research.

Through the MSF, broadband, high spectral resolution Fourier transform and fibre-optic spectrometers are provided to NERC researchers for measuring the absorption, emission, and scattering properties of solid, liquid, gas/vapour, and aerosol samples contained in a range of spectroscopic cells. High-quality spectroscopic data over the entire spectral range from wavelengths (wavenumbers) of 1 mm (10 cm⁻¹) in the far-infrared/sub-millimetre range to 180 nm (55,000 cm⁻¹) in the far ultraviolet are generated at spectral resolving powers of up to 1 part in a million and time resolutions as high as 5 µs, and archived and distributed by the MSF. Customised sample cells are available for specific temperature-dependent measurements over the range 190 to 500 K at optical path-lengths from 1 mm to over 1 km using multi-pass optical systems. For atmospheric chemistry studies, recent improvements to the chemical synthesis area and installation of laser-safe laboratories are now permitting a wider range of projects to be supported. Further details can be found on the MSF Web site (www.msf.rl.ac.uk).

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: January 1999	
Need 5.0	Uniqueness 5.0	Quality of Service 5.0	Quality of Science & Training 5.0	Average 5.0

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 85%	Staff & Status		Next Review (January) 2004	Contract Ends (31 March) 2005
	Head of Service	8.5% established		
	Scientist	85% established		
	Technician	85% established		

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY							
Allocation paid to RAL £k	Unit Cost* £k				Capital Expend £k	Income £k	NERC Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1 (Entire MSF)	Unit 2 (Bruker IFS 120HR FTS)	Unit 3 (Bruker IFS 66v/S FTS)	Unit 4 (Miniature Spectrometers)			
159.30	1.29	0.78	0.39	0.13	0.00	0.00	233.91

*In all cases Unit Costs include expert assistance in the use of the MSF and acquisition of relevant data, provided by a full-time scientist and technician; Assisting users in preparing grant and facility applications; Training users in use of equipment and in procedures, especially the complex FTS and sample cells; Compliance with safety practices; Full scientific supervision of visiting scientists and students; Recording spectra as required; Provision of data analysis software and assistance in data interpretation, error analysis and publication preparation; Archiving of data and delivery to users' home sites; Administrative support of visiting scientists. Management tasks include: Reporting and secretarial services to the MSFSC; Budgetary control; Liaison with users on MSF applications and schedules; Preparing quarterly, annual, cost allocation, and OPM reports to NERC.

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (Allocations paid to RAL in £k by year until end of current agreement)									
2002-03	159.3	2003-04	152+Capital	2004-05	157+Capital	2005-06	-	2006-07	-

STEERING COMMITTEE Molecular Spectroscopy Facility SC	Independent Members 5	Meetings per annum 2	Other S&F Overseen -
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□ 65

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		5.00					3.00	1.00
Other academic		1.00						
Students								
Pilot								
TOTAL		6.00					3.00	1.00

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/01 & 2001/02)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	0.67	6.67	0.67					0.33
Other Academic		1.67					0.33	
Students		3.33	0.33				0.33	
Pilot								
TOTAL	0.67	11.67	1.00				0.67	0.33

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects	2.00	6.00						
Other Academic		3.00						
Students		1.00						
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY — 2002/03)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other			
21.00	9.00	9.00	4.00	0.00	3.00								

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG							
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other			
16.67	6.00	6.00	3.33	1.67	3.00								

USER PROFILE (current FY — 2002/03)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
21.00	0.00	0.00	9.00	0.00

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/01 & 2001/02)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
24.67	2.00	0.33	17.67	0.00

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY — 2002/03)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/Conf Proc	PhD Theses
			7.00		16.00		23.00	8.00	15.00	0.00
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
							66.67%		33.33%	

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/01 & 2001/02)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/Conf Proc	PhD Theses
			12.70		17.00		29.70	8.30	20.30	1.00
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
							56.00%		42.00%	2.00%

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR 2002/03:

The reporting year has been a very productive period in terms of number of projects supported, generation of high-quality data, and extensive development of the Facility to meet NERC customer requirements. Data resulting from MSF studies were made available to international agencies including NASA, EUMETSAT, and ESA, and distributed world wide to scientists CD-ROM, HITRAN (www.hitran.com) and other international molecular databases.

Fully adjustable temperature-controlled liquid sample stage for reflectance spectroscopy.

NERC customers and our literature reviews have confirmed the need for a high quality, quantitative database of reflectance spectra for solid and liquid samples in the thermal infrared (2-25 μm). In order to meet these needs, diffuse and specular reflectance accessories for FTIR spectroscopy were developed and feasibility studies carried out on a range of solid and liquid substances including liquid water (pure and salty) and ice, vegetation, sand, and soil and rock samples – a report is available on the Web.

High quality broadband reflectance data in the thermal infrared for a powdered rock sample (lunar regolith simulant) where the peak reflectance value is only 0.2%.

Infrared signatures of ice and liquid water reflectance – new laboratory data such as these could lead to better exploitation of remotely sensed data and new Earth observing techniques.

A precision adjustable stage and customised sample holders for liquids, solids, and powders were built and a novel thermoelectric module designed and constructed to permit temperature control of samples over the 265 K to 320 K range, utilising heat-pipe technology to efficiently remove heat from the measurement area.

Herriot-type multi-pass optics for broadband FTIR spectroscopy and kinetics of trace atmospheric species.

Progress was made towards developing a new facility for atmospheric chemistry in which broadband FTIR spectroscopy will be combined with a corrosion-resistant multi-pass optics gas cell for improved sensitivity in detecting trace species such as Criegee intermediates. An external two spherical Herriot optics mirror system was designed to be coupled to the Bruker spectrometers via off-axis paraboloid mirrors. The long path-length absorption cell cooling and vacuum control systems were replaced by a state-of-the-art automated computer system operating under LabVIEW. This will enable users to dial in their specific temperature requirements between 190 K and 280 K allowing the system to automatically control the temperature of the LPAC as well as providing feedback from the hardware for diagnostic purposes. The flexible design of the system will permit MSF staff to modify and add components later on to greatly enhance the control of various experimental conditions, e.g. temperature, pressure, humidity, and mixtures of gases.

New pressure gauges were purchased and tests carried out to confirm that the gauges and electronic control systems were working correctly. The new pressure gauge systems were then integrated with existing vacuum lines and gas handling systems in the MSF for use on many NERC projects. A new laser laboratory was set up in the MSF by dividing an existing room with a new partition wall, door, and installing laser warning lights/interlocks.

The MSF scientist prepared and submitted four NERC, EC FP6, and European Space Agency research proposals, provided inputs to other grant proposals submitted by HEIs that involve use of the MSF laboratories, and peer-reviewed proposals and journal publications as requested.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY 2002/03:

Twelve NERC projects involving 21 visitors from 11 organisations were supported by the MSF during FY2002/03. Three projects that highlight new scientific achievements of the MSF are described below.

1. Spectroscopy of Reactive Intermediates, and Complexes, as well as Reagents and Products, in the Reactions of Atomic and Molecular Chlorine with Dimethyl Sulphide (DMS) (University of Southampton /University of Bristol)

The importance of sulphur chemistry in global climate change emerged over the last few decades. Dimethyl sulphide (DMS) is a major by-product of organosulphur compound biodegradation in the marine environment with 10-50 Mt emitted into the atmosphere by the Earth's oceans each year. Atmospheric oxidation of DMS leads to methane sulphonic and sulphuric acid, which serve as cloud condensation nuclei and contribute to the natural acidity of precipitation. Quantitative modelling of sulphur chemistry is problematic due to considerable uncertainty about the chemical pathways involved in DMS oxidation and the kinetic coefficients for the proposed reactions. DMS reactions with chlorine and the other halogens are a likely explanation of discrepancies between chemical models and field observations in the marine boundary layer. Measurements of IR, visible, and UV photo-absorption cross-sections of reactants, intermediates, and products of such reactions at the MSF are providing valuable data to improve our understanding of these important chemical processes.

Probing the reaction of DMS-Cl₂ using FTIR spectroscopy. Strong absorption bands are due to the product monochloro dimethyl sulfide (MDMS) and weaker features indicate unreacted DMS. Visible and UV spectra provide additional information on reactant, intermediate, and product species.

2. Identification of New Metastable Neutral Hydrates Of Sulphuric Acid (University of York/University of Manchester)

Sulphuric acid aerosol is ubiquitous in the Earth's atmosphere and plays a role both in radiative energy transfer, in heterogeneous chemistry and acting as cloud condensation nuclei. Sulphuric acid aerosols are formed from the liquid or gas phase oxidation of SO_2 .

The processes involved in the liquid phase formation of sulphuric acid are well known. However the gas phase processes, which are likely to be important in the upper troposphere and in the stratosphere, are less well understood. ATR-IR studies of thin film mimics have identified new metastable hydrates that are expected to play an important role in the nucleation of new aerosol and the stabilisation of the surface of equilibrated aerosol. Work done using the 75-dm³ aerosol chamber at the MSF has confirmed that these neutral metastable hydrates are also stable in aerosols at low temperature (and are not an artefact of the thin film method). Further, recent work has followed the nucleation of new sulphuric acid aerosol from SO_2 and H_2O vapours at low temperatures. This has shown that the initial nucleation material is also a metastable hydrate of the form $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$. This species has been predicted by computational methods to be stable at very small particle sizes and this work at MSF provides the first experimental evidence that confirms metastable $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ hydrates are formed during a nucleation event.

IR spectra of aerosol formed at 195 K in the 75-dm³ aerosol chamber: (a) $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ stable aerosol; (b) $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ - initially formed during a nucleation event.

The processes involved in the liquid phase formation of sulphuric acid are well known. However the gas phase processes, which are likely to be important in the upper troposphere and in the stratosphere, are less well understood. ATR-IR studies of thin film mimics have identified new metastable hydrates that are expected to play an important role in the nucleation of new aerosol and the stabilisation of the surface of equilibrated aerosol. Work done using the 75-dm³ aerosol chamber at the MSF has confirmed that these neutral metastable hydrates are also stable in aerosols at low temperature (and are not an artefact of the thin film method). Further, recent work has followed the nucleation of new sulphuric acid aerosol from SO_2 and H_2O vapours at low temperatures. This has shown that the initial nucleation material is also a metastable hydrate of the form $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$. This species has been predicted by computational methods to be stable at very small particle sizes and this work at MSF provides the first experimental evidence that confirms metastable $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ hydrates are formed during a nucleation event.

3. Oxygen and Water Complexes and their Role in Climate and Atmospheric Chemistry (University of Oxford)

The aim of this project is to record and analyse spectra of two complexes of oxygen ($\text{O}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{O}_2\text{-O}_2$) in order to properly assess their role in long- or short-wave atmospheric radiative transfer and other poorly understood processes involving water in the atmosphere, e.g. UV photo-nucleation of water vapour to produce cloud droplets. Studies at the MSF are complementing sensitive laser magnetic resonance (LMR) measurements at Oxford by providing broadband, high-resolution, long path-length observations under appropriate, but well-controlled and characterised, atmospheric conditions of mixing ratio, pressure, and temperature. A series of quantitative long-path near-infrared measurements on oxygen and mixtures with pure water have been made at the MSF to determine line pressure-shifts of the O_2 A- and Δ bands.

Determining spectroscopic parameters for the O_2 Δ band centred at 1.27 μm using least squares line fitting techniques.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

NERC has identified major environmental problems, such as climate change, pollution of the atmosphere and improvement of air quality that must be addressed over the next five years. Achieving this objective will require improved knowledge of atmospheric chemical composition and the radiative properties of gases, aerosols and surface components. Advanced measurement systems will be needed, including those using optical remote sensing techniques from the ground, aircraft, balloons and satellites, and *in situ* instruments exploiting absorption, emission, and scattering of electromagnetic radiation. Quantitative exploitation of data from current and near-term satellite missions will be important as well as development of the next generation of sensors. Central to many of these activities is quantitative spectroscopic information on atmospheric gases and aerosols, and biological and geological systems. The MSF will pursue a development strategy that enhances its position as the foremost UK (and in many respects World) facility providing environmental scientists with high-quality spectroscopic data, and which ensures its continued relevance to ongoing and future NERC thematic programmes, non-thematic research, NERC Centres for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) and DIAC, Centres of Excellence in Earth Observation (e.g. DARC), COSMAS, and student training. The strategy will also enhance the MSFs ability to win commissioned research from the EC, ESA, NASA, NASDA, EUMETSAT, and other customers.

During 2003/04, the following developments will be carried out to further enhance the MSF and permit a wider range of studies to be carried out by NERC customers. These will utilise the NERC MSF time (approx. 21 days) that is permitted for 'R&D', and in most cases will closely support ongoing or new NERC projects. Further small-scale developments will be completed in response to NERC customers' requests or to address safety issues.

- Instruments for characterising the size and number density of aerosol particles with radii from 3 nm to 1 μm (e.g. scanning mobility particle sizer and a novel optical particle counter) will be interfaced with the 75-dm³ aerosol cell through collaborations with the University of Oxford and University of Canterbury, New Zealand), and an aerosol generator for introducing solid mineral aerosol particles (e.g. volcanic ash and Saharan dust) into spectroscopic cells and reaction chambers will be designed and built;
- A flow-tube system for atmospheric chemistry will be established at the MSF, including mass-flow controllers, multi-pass optics for IR/UV probing of stable and reactive species, and vacuum pumping systems for different flow and pressure regimes;
- Automatic pressure data acquisition to PC using LabVIEW, and an assessment of the potential for further control and measurement of gas flow using mass-flow controllers and automatic gas valves to increase the range of experiments that can be carried out at the MSF, and to enhance safety;
- High-temperature gas cells will be developed together with appropriate temperature control and measurement systems;
- Proposals to establish new equipment, services, and calibration at the MSF, e.g. portable FTIR spectrometers, laser devices, a reflectance spectroscopy database, and alternative designs for aerosol cells such as those utilising large-volume PTFE sample bags, in consultation with potential NERC customers;
- A proposal on the methodology and resources needed to integrate MSF data acquisition and storage with long-term electronic archiving and distribution by an authorised NERC data centre (e.g. BADC).

The University of Salford Salford Greater Manchester M5 4WT
United Kingdom
Telephone 0161 295
Facsimile 0161 295

23 July 2003

Dr David Lynn,
Director Science and Innovation
NERC,
Polaris House,
Swindon SN2 1EU

Our reference: T/CGC/NARFSC

Dear Dr Lynn,

Re: MST Radar Facility Annual Report for 2002/03

I believe that you should have received an electronic copy of the above Report. This Report has been finalised after review by the NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee at their meeting on 27 June 2003.

Regards,

Yours sincerely,

Professor Chris Collier

Chair, NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee

Cc Dr Stuart White, RAL
Dr Andrew Kaye, NERC

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE The NERC MST Radar Facility at Aberystwyth http://mst.nerc.ac.uk	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT SLA	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1996	TERM 5 years to March 2005
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The Mission of the NERC Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere Radar (MSTR) Facility is to provide high quality atmospheric data products in near real-time to the UK scientific community in support of environmental research. It arranges for peer review of projects thereby ensuring that only science of the highest quality is supported. It maintains an awareness of users' requirements so as to ensure that the service is fulfilling actual needs. It provides appropriate scientific and technical support to scientific customers in order to aid in the analysis and interpretation of the data. It achieves these objectives by:

It achieves these objectives by:

- operating and maintaining the MSTR system and a climate data logger (for measuring surface temperature, pressure, humidity, rain fall and solar radiation) at Capel Dewi, a wind measurement system at Frongoch Farm (3 km to the west of the radar site), and associated computer systems at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)
- monitoring and maintaining the quality of the data
- archiving the data with the NERC British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) within 24 hours of acquisition thereby providing access for users through the internet
- investigating novel techniques in order to maximise the usefulness of the data products
- conducting research and development to ensure the Facility and its technology are state-of-the-art
- promoting the value of the data products, through seminars and presentations at conferences, in order to make them available to the widest possible audience
- maintaining a dedicated website
- holding one-to-one discussions with data-users
- executing commissioned work with the UK Met Office in order to supplement the annual budget.

The NERC MST Radar at Capel Dewi, near Aberystwyth in West Wales, is a 46.5 MHz pulsed Doppler radar ideally suited for studies of atmospheric winds, waves and turbulence. It is run predominantly in the ST mode for which such radars are unique in their ability to provide continuous measurements of the three-dimensional wind vector over the altitude range 2 – 20 km at resolutions of a few minutes in time (typically 2-3) and a few hundred metres in altitude (typically 300). Additionally, under certain circumstances the radar returns can give information about the atmospheric static stability (thus allowing monitoring of the altitude and sharpness of the tropopause), humidity fields and turbulence (of at least moderate intensity). The extensive data-set of high-resolution observations from the NERC MST Radar, which covers a period of more than 10 years, offers the potential for studies to be made of atmospheric phenomena ranging from the micro and meso scales through to the synoptic and seasonal scales and beyond. The Radar is the most powerful and versatile wind-profiling system in the UK.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review:	
Need 4.5	Uniqueness 5.0	Quality of Service 5.0	Quality of Science & Training 4.5	Average 4.75

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F	Staff & Status	Next Review	Contract Ends
76%	Head of Facility: Dr Stuart White 50% Project Scientist: Dr David Hooper 100% Site Manager: Mr Tony Olewicz 100% (UWA contract)	(January) 2004	(31 March) 2005

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3			
125.2	14,375	7,118	1,438	Nil	34.0	138.0
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2003-04	£130.5k	2004-05	?	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08

- Unit 1: Specific Project – NERC Funded
- Unit 2: Specific Project
- Unit 3: Pilot Project, Educational, or Teaching Use

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NARSFC	5	1-2	Chilbolton Radar Facility

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		1						
Other academic		4	2					
Teaching/Educational	3 (applications in this category are not graded)							
Pilot	1 (applications in this category are not graded)							
TOTAL		5	2					

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 2 years — 2000/2001 & 2001/2002; no data pre-2000)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1.00	3.50						
Other Academic	0.50	0.50	0.50					
Teaching/Educational	3.50 (applications in this category are not graded)							
Pilot	4.00 (applications in this category are not graded)							
TOTAL	1.50	4.00	0.50					

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY) – NOT APPLICABLE								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic								
Students								
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)									<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG						
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC	NERC C/S	Other
19	2	6	3			9						

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 2 years; no data pre 2000)									<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>			
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG						
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC	NERC C/S	Other
23.50	1.50	5.50	2.50	0.50		14.50						

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
12		3	4	1

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
19.00		1.00	2.50	1

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS 10	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total 10	Refereed 9	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc 1	PhD Theses 1

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	100%			

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS 7.33	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total 7.33	Refereed 5.67	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc 1.33	PhD Theses 0.33

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	100%			

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

During the last year 10 Supporting Scientific Cases have been submitted as applications for access to the MST Radar Facility datasets through the British Atmospheric Data Centre. Of these 4 were from researchers for specific projects, 2 were from PhD students, 1 was for a pilot project, 2 were for teaching use, and 1 was for an undergraduate project.

The MST Radar acquired data for 98% of the projected time for the year. Surface meteorological data (i.e. temperature, pressure, humidity, rainfall, and solar radiation) were recorded at 10 minute intervals without interruption for the whole year. Wind speed and direction data from the wind-sensor at Frongoch, 3 km to the west of the radar site, were acquired at 1 minute intervals for all but one week of the year. Quick-look plots and data files were, for the most part, made available through the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) website within 24 hours of the acquisition of the data. Specific requests for data were typically taken care of within 24 hours.

Considerable progress has been made with the processing and management of MST radar data. Particular emphasis has been placed on a new method of data reliability flagging. The existing method relies on rejecting all data which fail to meet a threshold signal-to-noise ratio. Although this method is reasonably effective, it fails to reject strong spurious signals, such as those arising from aircraft echoes. Moreover it rejects a significant number of weak but apparently reliable signals. This effectively limits the maximum observable altitude, for wind-profiling purposes, to around 16 or 17 km. The new reliability flagging system is based on the continuity of horizontal velocity components as a function of time. In addition to improving the quality of the low-level data products, it can significantly increase the altitude coverage for higher-level data products; wind-profile information is regularly available up to 20 km. This is achieved because the number of beam pointing directions used in the standard mode of operation (typically more than 5) is larger than the minimum required for wind-profiling purposes (3). The availability of reliability flagging allows the redundancy to be adaptively exploited in order to maximise the altitude coverage. The Met Office have expressed an interest in receiving samples of wind-profile data processed using the new algorithms as soon as they become routinely available.

To coincide with the introduction of new signal processing routines, standardised file formats have been defined in collaboration with the staff of the BADC. The original file formats reflect the relatively limited storage capacity available in the early years of the radar project (c. 1990). They are difficult to understand for a first-time user and cannot be interpreted without reference to external metadata. The new files are written using the self-descriptive NASA-Ames format which has been adopted for many datasets stored by the BADC. This step will radically improve the current accessibility and will ensure long-term utility of the data.

The most significant developments to take place at the radar site during the last financial year have been those in connection with the new University Facilities for Atmospheric Measurements (UFAM) instruments. A variety of instruments have been acquired by a consortium of 6 UK university departments on behalf of the entire UK atmospheric science community. The instruments are intended primarily for use in field campaigns although those owned by the University of Wales Aberystwyth (a mobile boundary-layer wind-profiler and a mobile ozone lidar) will be operated at the MST radar site whilst not otherwise engaged. The boundary-layer wind-profiler covers the approximate altitude range 200 – 3000 m and therefore both fills-in and overlaps with the wind information provided by the MST radar (2 – 20 km). However, both instruments provide more than just wind information and owing to the large difference in operating frequencies (1290.0 and 46.5 MHz, respectively), they give slightly different views of the atmosphere. The availability of such complementary information has proved to be particularly useful in connection with precipitation studies.

Some of the content on the Facility's website (<http://mst.nerc.ac.uk>) has been generalised over the past year so that it can serve the anticipated needs of an increasing wind-profiling community. In addition to the new UFAM boundary-layer wind-profiler at the MST radar site, a similar UFAM instrument is currently under construction at the Chilbolton radar facility. Although the mode of operation of the latter is significantly different to that of the other two instruments, the relevant radar return mechanisms and signal processing techniques are similar in all 3 cases. The MST Radar Project Scientist has provided valuable assistance to the UFAM instrument scientists responsible for both of these instruments in relation to signal processing and data analysis.

The MST radar facility continues to be represented and promoted to the wider atmospheric community. Facility posters have been presented at the UTLS/COSMAS workshop, held at the University of Bristol 8-11 July 2002, and at the UWERN Annual Conference, held at the University of Essex 9-11 September 2002. Seminars promoting the facility have been given at the University of Salford and at the University of Bath. It is noteworthy that the latter case was through the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, which is not an immediately obvious candidate for such a seminar. The group is interested in the effects of refractive index structures on the propagation of radio waves in the lowermost region of the atmosphere. Such structures also have an effect on the radar returns observed by the MST radar and boundary-layer wind-profiler, hence the interest.

The Project Scientist has had four abstracts accepted for the forthcoming international MST Radar workshop to be held in Peru in May. One of these relates to a poster promoting the NERC MST Radar Facility. The other three relate to research and development work; two of these involve collaboration with UK scientists at the Universities of Reading and of Aberystwyth.

The Project Scientist has also made a start on Science Communication Activities. An article on atmospheric gravity waves, which are commonly observed by the MST radar, has been submitted for the autumn 2003 issue of NERC's publication "Planet Earth". A short presentation on the radar was given to a group of A-level students visiting the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. It is intended that activities in this area will increase during the forthcoming year.

A number of Health and Safety issues have been addressed during the last financial year including collation all the relevant Health & Safety and site security information. An incident log-book, for H&S and security matters, has also been introduced at the radar site.

A 2-year extension to the contract with the Met Office for the supply of quasi-continuous wind data for 2003/04 and 2004/05 was agreed and ratified.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

A number of studies over the past year have focused on the interaction of normally distinct regions of the atmosphere, often through the effects of gravity wave activity. Gravity waves are known to play a number of significant roles within the atmosphere and consideration of them in global circulation models is essential in order to reproduce realistic results. However, since the waves span a large range of spatial scale sizes, and since a significant proportion of these fall below the resolution of the models, it is necessary to parameterise them statistically. Therefore, although it is known that gravity waves of different scale sizes are able to interact, this is typically demonstrated by inference. However, a recent case study using observations made by the NERC MST radar gives direct evidence of a mountain wave/inertia-gravity wave interaction event. Mountain waves extract energy from the low-level wind and transport it to higher regions of the atmosphere. The energy is typically returned to the background flow where the waves encounter a critical layer, i.e. where the wind vector has rotated more than 90° relative to the low-level flow direction. It is common to observe mountain wave breaking at critical layers related to changes in the synoptic-scale winds. However, for the case in question the necessary rotation is only achieved where the wind vector is modulated by inertia-gravity wave activity in the lower-stratosphere.

Investigations into tropopause erosion by mountain wave breaking, mentioned in last year's report, are on-going. Tropopause erosion is significant because it can give rise to mixing between the otherwise distinct upper-tropospheric and lower-stratospheric air masses. A second mechanism by which tropospheric and stratospheric air masses can be mixed is through convectively generated turbulence; this has the subject of a study making use of data from the Dynamics and Chemistry of Frontal Zones campaign, which was already mentioned briefly in last year's report. In this case the lower stratospheric air was transported down into the middle troposphere along a tropopause fold. Simultaneously, a tongue of moist air moved under the dry stratospheric air resulting in a potential instability and hence convective activity. This observation is significant because turbulence within a tropopause fold is more often a result of shear instability. Moreover, the tropospheric air being transported into the tropopause fold was of boundary layer origin and so the mixing involves two air masses which are normally separated by 10 km in the vertical direction.

Two more investigations are concerned with convective activity, although they focus on the signature observed by the radar. The radar return signal strength has a dependence on the vertical humidity structure and is often dominated by this contribution in the lower-troposphere. Convective activity can transport humid air from the moist lower atmosphere to the drier regions of the higher troposphere leading to an increase in the radar return signal strength associated with these altitudes. Coincident increases in the radar return spectral widths confirm the fact that these regions are turbulently active. Moreover, under such conditions the assumption of a locally homogeneous wind field, which is necessary for the derivation of the three dimensional wind vector from radar observations made in a variety of beam directions, appears to be violated. This has implications for data reliability flagging. The second investigation concerns a statistical study of the temporal variations in tropospheric radar return signal strength. It is already known that precipitation can lead to a reduction in signal strength, i.e. to the opposite effect of (non-precipitating) convection. An analysis of the perturbations of signal strength, at various tropospheric altitudes, and a comparison with rainfall rates measured at the same site, appears to give a good indication of whether convection or precipitation has a dominating influence.

The raw (sub-spectral) radar data collected as part of the Egrett campaign, during summer 2000, continue to be of value. One investigation is using a novel approach to identifying regions of turbulence based on the distribution of signal amplitudes. A second investigation is experimenting with novel techniques for signal processing. Instead of using the traditional Fourier transform method of analysis it employs wavelet transforms, multi-tapering and harmonic decomposition. The technique is thought to out-perform the traditional method under conditions of low signal-to-noise ratio and hence should lead to an increase in the altitude coverage for wind-profiling purposes.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

A major undertaking for the forthcoming financial year will be the reprocessing of the entire archive of MST radar observations. Initially the old and new signal processing routines will be applied in parallel to the in-coming data. Data users will also be invited to request individual days, or groups of days, from the archives, for reprocessing. It is hoped that user feedback will help in identifying any weaknesses in the sample files. Thereafter all data, including those from the other instruments associated with the Facility, will be made available in the new file formats.

An application has been received to operate the MST radar in an experimental mode in connection with the investigation of a novel technique for identifying turbulence. The usefulness of the traditional technique decreases with increasing wind speed. Observations have therefore been requested to coincide with mountain wave breaking at a critical layer; this results in turbulent activity in a region of low wind speed. The novel technique is based on an analysis of the sub-spectral data which must be specially recorded. Other notable studies for the forthcoming year include those investigating humidity, precipitation and inertia-gravity waves.

During the last year, the number of applications for access to MST radar data for teaching and educational purposes has increased. Although these represent non-core uses of data, further promotion can be achieved with relatively little effort. It is felt that exposure of students to the data at undergraduate level might encourage them to continue their studies at postgraduate level.

The MST Radar Facility and its performance are due for review towards the end of the next financial year since this year is the fourth of the 5-year SLA contract funded by NERC; significant effort will therefore be applied to the production of the required documentation for submission to the NERC Services Review Group by the end of the calendar year.

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

 NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL	FUNDING AGREEMENT:	ESTABLISHED AS	TERM: 3 years	
		Block Funding under the NERC SLA with RAL	A FACILITY:~1985	

TYPES OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

NERC has acquired - in support of high alpha-grade science during the preceding 30 years - a vast quantity of remotely sensed data of the surface of the Earth obtained by a variety of satellite sensors and airborne instruments. This valuable resource - estimated present value in excess of £15M - has fortunately been retained and now provides a unique record of environmental conditions during the previous three decades. It comprises digital data which in most cases have been rigorously calibrated and geo-corrected and scientists are therefore able to use such data with confidence in support of research and survey to understand and predict the natural environment and as a valuable input to long-term environmental monitoring.

The NEODC Mission - in line with the NERC Data Policy - is to ensure the responsible stewardship and distribution of its own Earth Observation (EO) data, to give guidance on the availability and use of this and other EO data, and to routinely acquire additions to the data holding; all such data services to be carried out in an efficient and cost-effective manner in response to requests from accredited customers. The NEODC also has a responsibility to monitor the stewardship accorded to other Earth observation data acquired by NERC so that such data are managed as a valuable resource for present and future environmental science. The NEODC is also increasingly acting as a single portal regarding Earth Observation data and information supporting environmental research - both in the UK and worldwide.

The NEODC Mission is:-

" To achieve the objective that the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC) shall deliver effective and efficient services to the NERC community in locating, accessing, interpreting and exploiting Earth Observation data and associated EO information, and shall also ensure the long-term integrity of EO datasets produced and acquired by NERC projects and programmes".

In order to achieve its mission the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre :-

- maintains a central archive and catalogue of NERC commercial satellite data and NERC airborne remotely sensed data - accessible through the NEODC website: www.neodc.rl.ac.uk
- provides access to this data for NERC Centres and Surveys, the UK HEI community, NERC Thematic Programmes, NERC EO Centres of Excellence, and NERC-funded academics in accordance with the terms of the NERC Data Policy
- co-ordinates and supervises the archiving of all digital data and ancillary information relating to the annual flying campaigns of the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility
- enhances the information and metadata content of its web pages
- continues to ensure the professional curation, and ease of access for registered customers, of all EO data acquired by NERC by the addition of such data held at the Centres & Surveys, and EO Centres of Excellence onto the NEODC archive
- continues to develop its infrastructure software/hardware to improve the quality and scope of its data services to the scientific community
- acts as a contact and liaison point for communications on other national and international archiving/cataloguing initiatives relating to EO data
- provides policy and strategy input to NERC corporate data policy through the NERC Data Management Group.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: January 1999	
Need	Uniqueness	Quality of Service	Quality of Science & Training	Average
5.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.25

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by NERC	Staff: Dr Stuart White Established - 50% of time Dr Matt Pritchard Established - 100% of time	Next Review 2006
100%		

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY											
Recurrent Allocation £k 133.5	Unit Cost £k *								Capital Expend £k Nil	Income £k Nil	Full cash cost £k 135.8
	Unit1	Unit2	Unit3	Unit4	Unit5	Unit6	Unit7	Unit8			
	2.241	2.689	1.345	1.793	3.137	2.689	.448	.896			

*Unit 1: Commercial Satellite Data Programme Request; Unit 2: Commercial Satellite Data Archive;
Unit 3: NEODC Satellite Data Archive; Unit 4: NEODC Airborne Data Archive; Unit 5: NEODC Aerial Photo Archive
Unit 6: Commercial Aerial Photo Archive; Unit 7: General Data Enquiry; Unit 8: Unsuccessful Data Search.

STEERING COMMITTEE	Earth Observation Expert Group	Meetings/ annum 2
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APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY - 2002/03) NB: All NEODC Datasets – curated since 1972 - have been acquired in support of high α-grade science funded by NERC.

	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1		
NERC Grant projects	1	1					
Other academic							
Students		4 Studentships	were supported				
Pilot							
TOTAL							

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1998/1999 1999/2000 & 2000/2001)

	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1		
NERC Grant projects	1.4	5.5					
Other Academic							
Students		10.8 Studentships	have been	supported			
Pilot							
TOTAL							

USER PROFILE (current FY) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic

Grand Total	Infrastructure				PAYG					
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
59	2	4	3	7	45					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic

Grand Total	Infrastructure				PAYG					
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
57	20	10	10	5	35					

USER PROFILE (current FY)

Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
36	7	2	3	5

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)

Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
42	5	3	8	3

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)

Publications (by science area & type) – Data not collected by NERC Designated Data Centres										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
9	18	7	1	24	28	0				

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)

Publications (by science area & type) – Data not collected by NERC Designated Data Centres										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
7	17	8	1	35	21	2				

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Customer Data and Information Services

Throughout the year the NEODC has continued to provide a cost-effective and efficient service for the purchase or acquisition, curation, search and provision of satellite and airborne remotely-sensed data on behalf of the NERC-funded community. A search and delivery service has been provided for all satellite and airborne data requests which could be sourced from the NEODC archives. Although the process of search, retrieval and supply of data is becoming more automated, the operation of the NEODC "help desk" is still a significant aspect of the NEODC service. Many associated enquiries relating to Earth Observation data resources, applications information, and copyright regulations and means of access have been received at the Data Centre and these have also been dealt with in a timely manner with appropriate advice and information provided.

A summary tabulation of customer data enquiries received by the NEODC is provide in Annex 2 to this report - these customer requests required archival searches and/or delivery of Earth observation scenes - either satellite or airborne data. Following confirmation of image specifications and data pricing, the supplier delivery time for new satellite data rarely exceeds 15 working days, except where data is sourced from non-European ground stations. Response time targets for both commercial archive data provision - two weeks - and the delivery of NEODC archive digital data - 1-2 days - have been maintained for all data deliveries. Copy prints of archive aerial photography are usually delivered within two weeks. No significant data quality problems were recorded during the year and no formal/informal complaints regarding the quality and delivery of the NEODC services during 2002/03 have been received. In fact, there has frequently been correspondence complimenting the NEODC on the quality and timeliness of its data and information services.

Infrastructure Development

New online storage hardware was procured for the NEODC and near-line data was transferred to this server thereby providing faster access to data for customers as well as simplifying internal data processing and metadata creation tasks. Software was produced for the creation of standards-compliant metadata for a significant proportion of the current NEODC datasets. This allowed the compilation of a new, informative and consistent metadata catalogue with an improved web interface which is now online.

Additional technical input and software development was provided towards the creation of the ATSR Ungridded Brightness Temperature(UBT) archive – a major new dataset which will shortly be managed by the NEODC.

Collaboration with ATSR Post Launch Support(PLS) and EISCAT Radar groups at RAL has been integral to the critical development of systems to enable effective access by scientific customers to this large (5 Tbytes) valuable dataset.

Discussions with industry have fostered the potential application of commercial software to enhance the visibility of NERC data collections among the Geographic Information community. This will provide cross-compatibility between the NERC Metadata Gateway and the "GIGateway" of the Association of Geographic Information (AGI).

NEODC staff have continued to collaborate and provide technical input to the NERC DataGrid working group with regard to metadata standards and database technologies.

A completely new, and vastly improved, website for the NEODC - www.neodc.rl.ac.uk - was launched in late March 2002 and is designed to act as a one-stop portal for Earth Observation data and information. Further development work and the production of additional information content has been carried out this year. Key interface components such as dataset footprint maps, download area, XSL stylesheets for the display of XML metadata, and a "shopping basket" system for ordering data have been developed. The new website has been designed to enhance its attractiveness to both regular academic customers and other visitors and has been constructed to ultimately allow efficient search and access to Earth Observation information as well as data - whether held at the NEODC or at other data centres. The website includes enhanced graphics with a hierarchical menu section for both the airborne and satellite data, a simplified search interface to the existing NEODC metadata catalogue, graphical tools for selection of geographical areas, and detailed information pages describing each type of data held by the NEODC.

Strategic Papers/Presentations/Reports/Bids

Dr Matt Pritchard – the NEODC Project Scientist – gave oral presentations on metadata management within the NEODC at the workshop held at Cambridge University by the National Institute for Environmental e-Science. He also presented a paper on recent developments within the NEODC of benefit to the NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility (ARSF) user community at the ARSF annual Workshop which was convened with assistance from the NEODC at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. NEODC staff also attended the Workshop for NERC's Earth Observation Centres of Excellence which was held at the University of Swansea.

Revisions were carried out to the NEODC Implementation Plan in the light of the projected reduced funding available to the Facility for carrying out its 5-year business plan.

A bid was prepared and submitted to the NERC Data Management Advisory Group - "Earth System Science: Enhanced Delivery and Visibility for Multiple Earth Observation Datasets" - seeking additional funding for the NEODC for a 3-year period. The bid was successful and will allow the appointment of an additional staff member – specifically with knowledge/experience in the application of EO data for environmental research in the terrestrial regime.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Remotely-sensed digital and analogue imagery of the surface of the Earth – terrestrial and aquatic – are used extensively in support of research and survey across the full spectrum of NERC’s environmental sciences. In this context, the NEODC data and information services made a major contribution to all five of the NERC Environmental and Natural Resource Issues (ENRIs) during the past year:

ENRIs	Bio-diversity	Environmental Risk	Global Warming	Natural Resource Management	Pollution & Waste	Other
No. of Projects	7	9	4	35	3	35

In previous years the NEODC has provided data services in support of this research to many UK University departments carrying out investigations into the natural environment. These include:- Geology, Geography, Biological Sciences, Earth Sciences, Soil Science, Ice and Climate, Archaeology, Planning and Landscape, Environmental Sciences, Remote Sensing, Marine Science and Coastal Management, Oceanography, Civil Engineering, Zoology, Hydrogeology, Epidemiology and Public Health, Land Use, Glaciology, Built Environment and Engineering Geology.

Likewise, within the NERC Centres and Surveys, there is wide application of Earth observation data and users of NEODC services during the period of the present SLA include most of the component Centres and Surveys.

New and archive satellite and airborne data were delivered to 5 NERC award holders in 2002/03 – two of these were projects relating to Research Grant awards and three comprised Studentships. (This is a significant reduction in the usual annual support of NERC-funded research by the NEODC and almost certainly reflects NERC’s cancellation of one of its two Grant rounds in 2002/03).

The titles of some of the high α -grade projects supported this year and last are listed below and demonstrate the breadth of NERC science for which the NEODC data and information services provided a valuable input:

The application of satellite imagery for the monitoring of performance of young forestry plantations in Galloway and Kielder forests.

Using remotely sensed data sources and GIS techniques to identify suitable sites for habitat creation/restoration under the requirements of EU habitats directives.

Modelling incision in the Sorbas Basin, SE Spain: an integrated GIS and remote sensing approach.

Geomatics for the detection, prediction, monitoring and understanding of geohazards.

Evaluation of satellite imagery in the archaeological assessment of arid zone environments.

The ecology and genetics of Mauritian skunks earmarked for use in habitat reconstruction.

The late Cenozoic development of the Gediz River, Turkey.

The temporal and spatial distribution of active deformation in the Basin and Range.

Source mechanisms of shallow earthquakes in the Alpine-Himalayan belt from INSAR and waveform modelling.

Individual dispersal decisions and emergent metapopulation dynamics of an endemic Afrotropical mammal – the Angolan black-and-white Colobus monkey.

To understand the distribution of archaeological sites in relation to natural landscape factors.

Differentiation between different grassland types using very high spatial and spectral resolution images.

Mapping and scientific observations of caves in Thailand.

Use of high resolution base maps for determination of key sites for peat gully blocking.

Remote sensing and the use of GIS for archaeology in alluvial landscapes.

Estimation of the input of dissolved inorganic carbon from rivers into the North Sea.

The impact of Little Ice Age floods on steepland river systems, Crete.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

The successful bid to NERC for additional funding to support: “Earth System Science: Enhanced Delivery and Visibility for Multiple Earth Observation Datasets” will allow the appointment of a new staff member to the NEODC thereby increasing its staff resource by 70%.

The NEODC has proposed, during this 3-year project, wide-ranging and integrated initiatives which will improve visibility and access to its growing portfolio of EO datasets, namely:

- Development of a new software infrastructure which will provide a flexible framework for the NEODC’s future activities, providing the ability to “bolt on” specialised on-line services in response to NERC science community demand. Initially these will include services for on-line processing of ATSR and ARSF data, and an improved data ingestion system for more efficient data management within the NEODC.
- Groundwork for hosting upcoming datasets, such as Airborne LIDAR, MODIS, MERIS, SeaWiFS and AATSR.
- Bringing forward the start date for ATSR data services and restoring ATSR data availability to a community which has been lacking this service during archive development. Also, exploiting a current window of opportunity to produce preview images for all the ATSR Ungridded Brightness Temperature(UBT) data products.

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Dr. N.B.W. Harris

8 July 2003

Mr David Lin
Science Programmes Directorate
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wilts SN2 1EU

Dear David,

NERC Isotope Geoscience Facilities: Annual Reports

On behalf of the Steering Committee I write to approve the annual reports from the facility managers of:

NERC Isotope Geoscience Laboratory (NIGL) at BGS;
NERC Isotope Community support Facility (ICSF) at SUERC;
NERC Argon Isotope Facility (AIF) SUERC; and
NERC Uranium Series Facility at the Open University (OUUSF)

Over the past 12 months all four facilities have continued to respond positively to the increasingly competitive scientific criteria imposed by the committee and we endorse the progress made in both the range and quality of science that they have undertaken. For 3 of the facilities, recent months have been dominated by the Review, the results of which, relative to previous reviews, I enclose. The committee was pleased to see upward movement by all 3 facilities, virtually across the board. It is interesting to note that the Review identified a marked increase in 'uniqueness', emphasizing that the skills and resources that are offered cannot be found elsewhere in the U.K. The most outstanding progress however, was made by NERC Isotope Geochemistry Laboratory increasing its average grade from 3.8 to 4.25. In my view this success reflects the sustained high level of work approved by the committee, the innovative science now being undertaken, the strong publication record and the effective management of the Facility by Prof. Parrish.

Yours sincerely,

Prof. N.B.W. Harris

Encl:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Niall Harris', written over the typed name.

**SRG 2003 Facility Review Scoring
(previous review in parentheses)**

	NEED	Uniqueness	Quality of service	Quality of science and training	Average
ICSF	4.0 (4.0)	5.0 (4.5)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
OU USF	4.0 (4.0)	4.5 (3.0)	4.5 (4.5)	4.5 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
NERC IGL	4.5 (4.4)	4.0 (3.4)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (3.6)	4.25 (3.8)
AIF	(4.5)	(5.0)	(4.0)	(5.0)	(4.63)

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE NERC Isotope Geosciences Laboratory (NIGL)	FUNDING Direct from Swindon	AGREEMENT SLA	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1987	TERM 5 yr
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

Purpose. NIGL is a comprehensive stable and radiogenic isotope laboratory facility that undertakes highly relevant environmental, life, and earth science research, and educates and trains PhD students, in a collaborative research environment. The science addressed is interdisciplinary and involves problems where isotope analysis is pivotal. NIGL serves many grade 4 and 5 academic departments in the UK, and several NERC institutes, especially the British Antarctic and Geological Surveys. Complementing the responsive mode of the service, NIGL has built up national and international leading expertise in several areas and, in its overall programme, has focussed its research impact on a number of major initiatives that are important for NERC's Environmental and Natural Resource Issues. NIGL was reviewed by SRG 2003 and renewal of funding for the period after April 1 2004 has been secured.

The Facility and its equipment. NIGL comprises four analytical facilities complemented by a skilled scientific and technical staff:

- C, H, O Facility: isotope analysis of waters, carbonates, and diatom silica.
- CAL Facility: combustion and laser analysis of organic and inorganic materials
- U-Th-Pb Facility: high precision U-Pb dating using TIMS, and laser in situ U-Th-Pb dating using PIMMS
- PIMMS/Tracer Facility: high precision isotope (U, Pb, Hf, Nd, Sm, Cd, Sr, Rb, Cu, Zn) analysis of solids and solutions using both PIMMS and TIMS instrumentation.

Leading capabilities in the UK comprise: U-Th-Pb high precision and *in situ* geochronology, climate change research using H-C-O isotopes in waters, carbonates and diatom silica especially in the lacustrine environment, high precision measurement of isotopes of anthropogenically notable elements (Cd, Zn, Cu, Pb, S, N, C) in the environment using both plasma multicollector and gas source mass spectrometry, and Hf isotope measurements and geochemistry applied to the solid earth. NIGL has world-leading capabilities in several of these protocols (especially U-Th-Pb geochronology and diatom silica oxygen isotope analysis in palaeoclimate research), and students receiving training are exposed to the best approaches and methods available anywhere. Analytical innovation and efficiency are ongoing goals of our development work in support of the programme, and also the concept that complex problem solving requires multiple isotopic methods. It is the integrated laboratory philosophy that remains a very strong and unique aspect of NIGL. The NIGL operates a total of 10 mass spectrometers in addition to chemical and sample preparation laboratories. The continuous flow gas source stable isotope mass spectrometer installed in 2001 is operating smoothly. NIGL has continued efforts to improve Health & Safety and remains compliant with NERC/BGS Health and Safety Policies.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: 2003		
Need	Uniqueness	Quality of Service	Quality of Science & Training	Average
4.5	4.0	4.5	4.0	4.25

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F	Staff & Status 15 NERC BGS Staff supported c.15-80% with S&F funds Administration-management provided by BGS BGS and commissions support PDRAs and remainder of staff %	Next Review (January) 2008	Contract Ends (31 March) 2009
60%			

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £ per half day						Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	Unit 1 NIGL Staff	Unit 2 Students/ academics	Unit 3 BAS Staff	Unit 4 PDRAs via grant	Unit 5 PDRAs pd by others	Unit 6 In kind Staff			
438	215	32	65	32	215	44.5	85	1043	
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)									
2003-04	£ 438k	2004-05	£ 451k	2005-06	£464k	2006-07	£478k	2007-08	£492k

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NERC Isotope Geosciences Facilities SC	8 independents 7 ex officio	2	AIF, ICSF, OUUSF

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/2003)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		3	1	2				2
Other academic		13	12	5	1			
Students			3					
Pilot								
TOTAL		16	16	7	1	0	9	2

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000, 2000/2001, & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		4	7	1			2	
Other Academic		11	18	4	3	2	9	2
Students		1	8	1	1		3	1
Pilot								
TOTAL		16	33	6	4	2	14	3

Note: This represents all applications submitted and from 2000/2001 all projects graded less than mid- $\alpha 3$ have not been accepted.

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects		5						
Other Academic		1	14	5	1	1	1	
Students		6	7	2				2
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other
117	4	31	17	8	39	4			18	12

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other
121.67	4.67	34.33	18	7.33	40.67	1			22.67	11

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
38	8	1	31	31

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
39.67	7.33	1	34.33	34.67

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (calendar year)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
6	66	9	4	20	0	0	105	40	58	7

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
13	68	5	2	33	0	2

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
7.33	73.00	6.67	2.33	26.67	0.33	0.67	116.33	40.33	68.33	7.67

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
11	92	6.33	3	27.67	0	3

PAYG NERC C/S projects include the BGS-NIGL Programme and BGS commissioned projects. Total of the PAYG users are shown as commercial.

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OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

The NERC Isotope Geosciences Facilities Steering Committee (NIGFSC) approved 33 new projects with a mean grade of α_4 . A total of c.140 projects were worked on, most of a multi-year nature, and 39 PhD students (including 10 CASE) and 9 post-doctoral researchers received training. The programmes that continue to be in highest demand are U-Th-Pb geochronology, stable isotope measurements in support of palaeoclimate research, and research using the plasma ionisation instruments. Two new mass spectrometers were ordered during the year mainly with external funds that augment the facilities. A new continuous flow stable isotope mass spectrometer installed in 2001 has been operating smoothly. Considerable effort was devoted to preparation of renewal paperwork for SRG2003 including a user survey, and the renewal of NIGL into the next 5 year term was successful. NIGL's publication output during the year was 103 refereed papers (51 published, 29 in press, 22 submitted). Together, the publication output, training, grant and other commissioned income, and grading of proposals exceeded all performance targets as set out by the 1999 expert review of NIGL. Developmental work carried out during the year concentrated on investigation of plasma ionisation mass spectrometry facilities to measure Zn and Cu isotopes laser ablation MC-ICP-MS U-Pb dating methodology, extraction and measurement of N isotopes from nitrate in snow using the CF-IRMS instrument, temperature controlled elemental reduction of phosphate to measure tooth and bone oxygen isotopes using CF-TRMS, and measurement of uranium isotopes in urine and other matrices in very low (ng/litre) concentration using PIMMS solution analysis.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2001/02):

Palaeoclimate Studies

Circulation changes in the Late Quaternary Aegean Sea. The modern Aegean Sea is an important source of deep water for the Eastern Mediterranean. Stable isotope data was used to investigate longer-term climate variability during the Late Glacial and Holocene, in particular that associated with the deposition of the early Holocene dysoxic/anoxic sapropel S1. Prior to the onset of sapropel-forming conditions the data show an onset of seasonal stratification followed by year-round stratification, identified through the lagged $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ response of planktonic and deeper water foraminifera. This suggests that isolation of intermediate/deep-water preceded the start of sapropel formation. The lag is of the order of 1 kyr and helps to explain one of the major problems in sapropel studies, namely the source of nutrient supply required for productivity to reach levels needed for sustained sapropel deposition. (With J Casford, E Rohling, and S Cooke Southampton Oceanography Centre).

West Greenland palaeoclimate. Western Greenland has numerous lakes that have enormous potential for palaeoclimatic reconstructions. The records derived from lakes are complimentary to those derived from ice and marine cores in that the lakes are reflecting regional climate variability and varying precipitation. Such alternative proxy records are necessary because the ice-core records show limited variability during the Holocene. Oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) isotope records from laminated sediment cores show that apart from inferred wetter periods around 7000 and 5000 years BP, this area has always been drier than today. An extremely rapid change in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data started at around 7000 years BP suggests a marked arid phase causing substantial evaporation and lowering of lake levels. Our data suggest that at a regional scale climate was quite dynamic in the early Holocene, perhaps representing an interplay between changing ice masses and processes in the Davis Straits. (with University of Liverpool and University of Copenhagen).

Isotope Geochemistry

A radical re-interpretation for the origin of the lower crust beneath the Pannonian Basin. New isotopic data (Sr, Nd, Pb, Hf and O) for a suite of mafic lower crustal granulite xenoliths from the Pannonian Basin have led to a radical reinterpretation of the nature and origin of the lower crust in the region. The new data show that the granulite protoliths are considerably older than Tertiary basalt underplating and formed in an oceanic environment as hydrothermally altered basalts and gabbros. At least 1/3 of the xenoliths have $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values less than average MORB and/or mantle peridotite - a situation not observed in any other lower crustal granulite xenolith suite. These values require a period of hydrothermal alteration at high temperature, the most likely location being in the oceanic lower crust.

Archaeological Science

Rapid analysis of O in teeth. Methodology has been developed to use the new rapid throughput CF-IRMS instrument to measure oxygen isotopes in bone and teeth using temperature controlled elemental reduction using silver. This allows precision of measurement to meet or improve on that previously in use at NIGL with the laser fluorination facility off line, and this enabling methodology will allow projects of higher sample numbers to be done in a considerably more cost effective fashion in the future. NIGL has the only UK facility with this new technique.

Pollution and Waste

Possible stratospheric sources for polar nitrate. The first N isotopic measurements to be undertaken on nitrate in precipitation on the High Arctic (Svalbard at 79°N) suggest that some of the nitrate may be derived from the stratosphere. Winter 2001 snowpack had very low nitrate concentrations and $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ measurements were made possible through use of new analytical procedures and equipment. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of -18 to -13‰ for Svalbard snow are substantially lower than the -5 to +5‰ range typical of nitrate of tropospheric origin at low to mid latitudes, but are similar to a high latitude site in the southern hemisphere. Recent isotopic studies of N_2O suggest that its photo-degradation in the stratosphere could be the source of this light nitrogen. The data have important consequences for debates about the dispersion of anthropogenic pollutants from mid-latitudes in the northern hemisphere (U Nottingham, NERC GANE programme).

Landfill nitrogen pollution naturally attenuated by denitrification. Investigations of a chalk quarry landfill near Cambridge using innovative gas and liquid analysis demonstrate that anaerobic decomposition of the large amount of organic matter had led to the formation of toxic concentrations of ammonium in the landfill leachate. This leachate was leaking outwards into the more aerobic environment of the surrounding chalk. There was therefore a high possibility that oxidation of the ammonium by bacterial nitrification would lead to nitrate pollution of the chalk aquifer. When chemical data were combined with N isotope information, however, the data displayed a log-linear relationship between ammonium concentrations and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values which could only be explained by 'Rayleigh' type isotope fractionation accompanying nitrification. The data also showed that bacterial conversion of nitrate to N_2 gas - was also occurring, as detected in dissolved gases. This unexpected discovery suggests that pollution by landfill ammonium can, in some environments, be attenuated by a series of natural processes which convert it to harmless N_2 gas. (BGS and Environment Agency)

Zn isotopes by MC-ICPMS – a possible tracer for industrial pollution processes. NIGL has used a CASE studentship to investigate the potential of Zn isotopes as a monitor for the source of industrial pollution. Experiments using rice, lettuce and tomato plants grown in soils doped with Zn, showed subtle levels of isotopic fractionation from the roots to the shoots of the plants. The level of fractionation (± 0.2 - 0.4 permil) was however, tiny in comparison to the levels of fractionation (-9.0 permil) recorded from samples of refined and purified Zn commercial standards whose isotopic fractionation took place during metal refinement. This establishes the feasibility of using Zn isotopes to fingerprint industrial processes and related anthropogenic Zn pollution. (With T Mason, Imperial College)

Method Development

In-situ U-Th-Pb dating of accessory minerals. Additional methodological development has allowed in situ dating to sample small regions within crystals, even irregular growth zones. The precision achieved has reached Spatial resolution protocols allow both rasters and curve line segments of crystals to sample small and 2-3 % (2σ) for the U/Pb ratio in monazites and xenotime, and slightly higher in zircons. A manuscript setting out the full analytical methodology, including an accurate and precise correction for Hg and common Pb was completed, and was submitted in spring 2003.

Geochronology

Prograde metamorphism at the Nanga Parbat Haramosh Massif, Pakistan. The timing of metamorphism at this enigmatic feature of the Himalayan orogen is contentious. By analysing monazites *in-situ* using LA-MC-ICPMS it was determined that high-grade metamorphism occurred at ~ 1860 Ma, and fluid induced retrogression at greenschist grade occurred at ~ 4 - 8 Ma. By rastering the laser across the sample of monazite occluded in garnet, a high precision ($\pm 4\%$) age was derived in spite of huge variations in signal intensity arising from differential mixtures of garnet and monazite. (Dr G Foster, NERC PDRA)

Dating of Eclogite UHP metamorphism. The dating of high pressure metamorphism has been achieved using the U-Th-Pb system by analysis of accessory minerals in eclogite in conjunction with petrographic and detailed chemical maps of accessory minerals. During India-Asia continental collision in Pakistan, coesite-bearing (c. 100km deep) eclogite grew prograde allanite prior to highest pressure, then crystallised coesite and zircon accompanied by further growth of allanite and rutile, and was followed by retrograde growth of epidote and conversion of clinopyroxene to hornblende. Zircon and allanite record dates of 47-46 Ma, defining the prograde to peak pressure portion, while rutile returned an age of 44 Ma that likely defines the cooling of the rock to temperatures less than 500-550C. These data allow a calculated rate of exhumation of more than 50 km/Ma, amongst the fastest ever documented. These data allow better quantification of rapid rates of exhumation of subducted continental crust in collisional orogens. (NERC PhD student S Gough, Oxford)

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

SRG2003 approved in principle the renewal proposal that included in 2003/4 and 2004/5 a new stable isotope palaeoclimate scientist and a new isotope mass spectrometer for palaeoclimate studies, the latter's funding mechanism to be decided. Analytical developments have focussed on (1) the extraction of nitrate from arctic snow and its N isotopic measurement; (2) Zn, Cu and Cd isotopes and mass fractionation refinements using PIMMS instrumentation, (3) rapid zircon dating by LA-PIMMS for provenance studies and (4) high precision uranium isotope measurements on a variety of matrices including soils, urine, and bone. These will continue to see development refinements, but we will also pursue the analysis of silicon isotopes for palaeoclimate applications and the improvement in the analysis of phosphate oxygen by continuous flow temperature controlled reduction analysis. Considerable effort will be spent training PhD students and new staff members in analytical methods, installation of new TIMS and CF stable isotope mass spectrometers, upgrading to the laboratories water, air, and power supplies (with infrastructure funds) and tendering for a new stable isotope mass spectrometer for oxygen isotopic measurements on diatom silica. Short courses in 'Stable isotope applications to palaeoclimate studies' and U-Th-Pb geochronology will be given in the year ahead.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

Our reference

Your reference

Direct line/e-mail

J.Laybourn-Parry@nottingham.ac.uk

**School of Life and
Environmental Sciences**

3rd July 2003

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Dr D. Lin,
Natural Environmental Research Council,
Polaris House,
North Star Avenue,
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SN2 1EU

NERC LIFE SCIENCES MASS SPECTROMETRY FACILITY

Dear Dr Lin,

The annual reports of the three nodes of the Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility are testament to the continuing success of the Facility. Each of the nodes received consistent highest scores for need, uniqueness, quality of service and quality of science and training in the review for the financial year 2002-2003. The combined nodes of LSMSF supported 38 projects during 2002/2003. A significant number of these projects contributed the NERC thematic programmes (GANE, Soil Biodiversity), as well as to responsive mode funded projects and Ph.D. projects. During 2002 the Facility achieved an excellent output of 35 peer reviewed publications, many of which included facility staff as authors. The training of graduate students is an important activity undertaken by the staff of LSMSF, resulting in a number of Ph.D theses, most supported by NERC studentships.

During 2002/2003 the Organic Mass Spectrometry node of LSMSF received a significant level of refurbishment and additional instrumentation that was supported by funds secured from SRIF. While this will strengthen the excellent reputation and capability of the node, it did cause very considerable disruption during the year, with equipment 'down time'. Nonetheless the node sustained a good performance for which the staff must be congratulated. The ¹⁵N SIF node is preparing for its imminent move to Lancaster University, which is likely to impose some disruption during 2003/2004.

While the three elements of LSMSF have operated in a complementary fashion for many years, we are always seeking ways to maximise operational efficiency and to deliver a more streamlined service to NERC users. Together the three nodes provide

Head of School: Professor J Laybourn-Parry
Professor D Archer, Professor C J Barnard, Professor J M Behnke, Professor J Bradley,
Professor J F Peberdy.

THE QUEEN'S ARMS
FOR ENTERPRISE
INTERNATIONAL TRADE
2001

THE QUEEN'S
ANNIVERSARY PRIZES
FOR HIGHER AND FURTHER EDUCATION
2000

support for virtually all applications of organic and light stable isotope mass spectrometry, however, there are potential problems with respect to new applicants and their understanding of the services available from each node. Applicants may make a number of applications to the different nodes, which results in confusion and an inefficient use of Facility staff time. In future the LSMSF will operate a single entity. Not only will this increase the efficiency of service, it will enable synergistic operation of the three nodes by facilitating sharing of knowledge, expertise and analytical capabilities. Moreover, it provides a level of insurance in the event of serious instrument failure. In future applicants will make a single electronic application – effectively a one-stop-shop. The advantage of this is that it enables LSMSF to direct an application to the appropriate node(s). The current Directors of each node will undertake the role of LSMSF Director in rotation.

In summary the LSMSF has sustained a strong performance during 2002/2003 and has implemented measures to enhance the quality of its service to the NERC community.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Johanna Laybourn-Parry". The signature is written in a cursive style with a long horizontal flourish at the end.

Johanna Laybourn-Parry
Chairman NERC LSMSF

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Life Sciences Mass Spectrometry Facility (LSMSF), [Organic Mass Spectrometry (OMS) node]	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT F14/G6/13/01	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1992	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The OMS node of LSMSF provides a specialist service enabling the separation and mass spectrometric characterisation of organic compounds derived from biological and environmental matrices. The strength of the node is evident in the expertise and instrumental capabilities for the analysis of complex mixtures particularly through combined chromatography (i.e. GC and HPLC) coupled to either organic or light stable isotope mass spectrometry (current technological limitations prevent the use of HPLC with the latter). Typical information that may be provided includes compound structures inferred from mass spectra, 'fingerprint' distributions using GC/MS or HPLC/MS and compound specific stable isotope (C, H, N and O) compositions. The techniques and breadth of expertise possessed by the Facility make it unique certainly within the UK and matched by only a possible few laboratories internationally. It is probably the most experienced anywhere in the world in the application of compound specific stable carbon isotope analysis methodologies to environmental science. Prospective outside users submit applications to use specialist instrumentation or techniques not in their own institutions, thereby emphasising the unique position of the Facility. Successful applicants are encouraged to visit and become directly involved in the analysis of samples and subsequent processing of complex mass spectrometric and/or stable isotope data. The activities of the node are overseen by a steering committee (NILSSC) which is also responsible for reviewing the activities of the other two nodes, namely: ¹⁵N Stable Isotope (¹⁵NSI) node and the Life Sciences Community Stable Isotope (LSCSI) node.

Key advantages of the OMS node:

- Enables the UK life sciences community to undertake biomolecular and stable isotope analyses largely unavailable elsewhere in the UK, e.g. compound specific δD measurements, and insures continued access to new 'cutting edge technologies.
- Provides expertise in the analysis of organic compounds backed by a world-class research group operating within the area of biogeochemical analysis for over 30 years. Situated within a Grade 5* chemistry department the node has the necessary background for providing analytical chemical support for its users and environment for the development of new technologies.
- On-site guidance and training in sample preparation, instrumental operation and data interpretation is available, as are facilities for 'wet chemical' treatment of samples prior to analysis.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: 28/01/03		
Need α5	Uniqueness α5	Quality of Service α5	Quality of Science & Training α5	Average α5

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 13 %	Staff & Status Dr Ian D Bull PDRA 100% S&F Funded Fixed term appointment	Next Review (January) 2008	Contract Ends (31 March) 2004
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k 55.83	Unit Cost £k		Capital Expend £k 21.8	Income £k 0	Full cash cost £k 79.13	
	1 GC/MS, GC/C/IRMS, Py/GC/MS or LC/MS analysis 0.18					
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2002-03	77,630	2003-04	75,880	2004-05	2004-06	2006-07

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NILSSC	8 (Chair: Professor Layhourn-Parry, University of Nottingham)	1(2)	¹⁵ NSI node, LSCSI node

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		1	1					
Other academic								
Students		2	3					
Pilot								
TOTAL								

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	0.2	0.87	0.7				0.2	
Other Academic	0.7	2.2	1.1				0.3	
Students	0.5	1.3	0.5				0.3	
Pilot			0.5				0.2	
TOTAL								

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects		2						
Other Academic								
Students			1					
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
23	5	13	7	0	5	0	0	0	0	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
35.7	5.3	21	10	1	7.5	0	0	0	0	0

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
10	0	0	13	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
15.2	0	0	21	0

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
11	1	2	0	3	0	0	17	11	0	6

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
65%	5%	12%	0%	18%	0%	0%

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
20.2	9.2	11.2	0	15.1	0	1.1	56.8	23.6	27.3	5.9

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
36%	16%	20%	0%	26%	0%	2%

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

The 2002/2003 financial period has been one of challenges with a significant amount of disruption originating from building refurbishments made using funds secured through the Science Research Infrastructure Fund (SRIF). At the beginning of June 2002 all instrumentation was temporarily shut-down and relocated on-site so that the laboratories housing OMSF could be completely renovated. As well as general modernization and decoration, renovations included the stripping out of redundant services, the replacement of existing gas-lines, electrical supplies, exhaust extraction systems and flood protection and the installation of a new computer sub-node. Additionally, extensive air conditioning was installed to accommodate the increased heat-load of the laboratory resulting from the larger inventory of analytical instrumentation. Existing instrumentation was reinstalled during September 2002 and additional instrumentation, also acquired using funds secured through SRIF, was installed over a period lasting from December 2002 to February 2003 (see ANNEX 3 for a comprehensive list of instrumentation and capabilities). To date full operational capacity of the laboratory has been hindered by a series of snagging issues, however, despite these problems the OMS node has been able to meet the agreed capacity (13%, 330 units; actually provided 431 units) for successful applicants to NERC S&F. The recent refurbishments and instrument purchases (and hence increased service capabilities), combined with specific expertise tailored to NERC science, make the OMSF an internationally unique facility, its analytical portfolio probably unmatched by any similar laboratory worldwide.

More recently the OMS node has acted as a central component in the organisation and execution of the 2003 Stable Isotope Mass Spectrometry Users Group (SIMSUG) meeting hosted by the School of Chemistry, University of Bristol. The meeting provided an ideal opportunity to advertise the newly created LSMSF to a large number of potential users and the OMS node fully capitalised on the presence of a captive audience to advertise the Facility. Moreover, attendees were given the opportunity to view first-hand the facilities provided by the node through a series of guided tours conducted throughout the course of the meeting. A short course on compound-specific stable isotope mass spectrometry, arranged by the OMS node and associated staff, preceded the main SIMSUG meeting and was deemed both useful and interesting by attendees again the majority of whom represented potential users of services provided through LSMSF.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Investigation of methane oxidising bacteria using $^{13}\text{C}_4$ labelling of phospholipid fatty acids

This research was performed as part of a NERC funded CASE studentship in collaboration with the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Merlewood. Although some low affinity methanotrophs have been cultured the majority of methane oxidising bacteria are not amenable to currently available methods of culturing resulting in the need for a culture independent method of analysis. One such method is the combination of stable isotopic labelling and phospholipid fatty acid (PLFAs) analysis. An example of the use of this technique is in the investigation of the methane oxidising community in the cover of a clay-capped landfill site. Soil samples were taken from four sections of the depth profile of the cap and incubated with 10,000 ppm methane of which either 1% was $^{13}\text{C}_4$ or all was unlabelled methane. Following incubation the PLFAs were extracted from the soils and analysed by GC/C/IRMS. From the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values obtained it was possible to calculate the relative abundance of each of the labelled PLFAs produced over the course of the incubation. These PLFAs are effectively a chemical signature of the methane oxidising community in the soil samples. As PLFAs can be used for chemotaxonomic characterisation of certain groups of bacteria it was possible to observe a change in the methane oxidising community with depth through the landfill cap. Figure 1 shows the relative abundance distributions of labelled PLFAs for the four sections of the cap. The top section of the profile is dominated by labelled C_{16} fatty acids suggesting a population of type I methanotrophs are performing the majority of the methane oxidation. As the profile is descended, the deepest soil can be seen to have a different labelled PLFA distribution, dominant in C_{18} fatty acids, suggesting a high abundance of type II methanotrophs contributing to the methane oxidation. This method of microbial analysis can also be employed in the investigation of high affinity methanotrophic bacterial communities in forest soils by incubation with a lower concentration of labelled methane. Additionally, other labelled substrates may be utilised for the investigations of different functional groups of microbes involved in carbon cycling in soils or sediments.

Figure 1. Relative abundances of labelled PLFAs extracted from four sections of the profile a clay-capped landfill cap following incubation with 10,000 ppm methane containing 1% $^{13}\text{C}_4$.

Climate change recorded by biomarkers in modern to 2.6 MA old sediments underlying the Benguela Current System

This work represents an on going collaboration between Dr RD Pancost of the University of Bristol and Dr MA Maslin of the Environmental Change Research Centre, Department of Geography, University College London. The Benguela Current (BC) system is one of the major eastern boundary upwelling regions; consequently, underlying sediments are organic-rich and the system likely played a significant role in the global carbon cycle. In addition, by contributing to cross-equatorial heat transport, the BC could have influenced the moisture supply available for the build-up of ice-sheets. Samples were collected from sites 1083 and 1084a recovered during Leg 175 of the ODP. Both are hemipelagic settings on the continental shelf, with site 1083 being located slightly to the North of site 1084 and, thus, more centrally located in the zone of most intense upwelling. Because of the upwelling and associated high productivity, Benguela sediments at both sites are organic-rich with TOC contents varying from 2 to 20%. Consequently, shallow sediments are associated with dramatic redox gradients in which O_2 and then SO_4^{2-} are rapidly consumed and methanogenesis begins at relatively shallow depths (<10m). Thus, we have focused on three stratigraphic intervals in addition to a low-resolution long-term record: the upper 4 m (modern to last glacial maximum); two TOC cycles (ca. 4-17%) at 0.7 and 1.1 Ma; and 2.6 to 2.4 Ma spanning the intensification of NHG.

Specific attention has been devoted to a high-resolution reconstruction of climate change from 2.6 to 2.4 Ma, spanning the intensification of Northern Hemisphere Glaciation. In this interval, we have determined alkenone unsaturation indices and abundances as proxies for sea surface temperature and algal productivity, respectively. Alkenone unsaturation indices closely parallel obliquity-based insolation curves and, thus, glacial-interglacial cycles. Estimated palaeo-sea surface temperatures range from ca 18°C during the glacial period to 23°C during the interglacial (Fig. 2a), likely recording intensification of upwelling during the former. In contrast, alkenone and TOC accumulation rates maximize during the transition from interglacial to glacial states (Fig. 2b,c). This likely reflects the influence of two competing processes: upwelling intensity, which is greatest during glacial periods, and the nutrient richness of upwelled waters, which is greatest during interglacial periods.

We also determined *n*-alkane $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, abundances, and average chain lengths (ACL) as proxies for aspects of terrestrial ecosystems and climate. In contrast to the alkenone records, *n*-alkane $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and ACL exhibit periodicity consistent with precessional (ca. 20 ka) climate forcing (Figure 2d,e). Specifically, when insolation is high, *n*-alkane $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values shift to lower values (from -26 to -28‰). We suggest that this reflects southward movement of the Intertropical Convergence Zone during periods of high latitude insolation and associated increases in precipitation. This could have resulted in somewhat higher proportional abundances of C_3 plants as reflected by the lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values.

Ongoing and future work will focus on expanding the range of biomarker isotopic records from these sediments. Of particular interest are bacterial and archaeal biomarkers for sedimentary carbon cycling and algal biomarkers from which records of primary productivity and $[\text{CO}_2(\text{atm})]$ can be reconstructed.

Figure 2. Depth profiles of organic geochemical parameters across the intensification of Northern Hemisphere Glaciation

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Following the refurbishment of infrastructure and instrument acquisitions that have occurred over the past twelve months the 2003-2004 period is envisaged to be a time of consolidation for the OMS node. Whilst the commitment to NERC S&F under the current SLA was met instrument time for several projects was held in abeyance pending instrument (re)installation and as such provision for these projects has been made over the ensuing period.

The end of the 2002-2003 academic year will herald the departure of Dr JF Carter who is leaving the employ of the University of Bristol after fifteen years of service. Dr Carter has been both an integral and crucial part of the OMS node from its inception as an S&F facility in 1992 and his contribution and hard work in support of the facility cannot be overstated. Whilst Dr Carter's level of employment with the University will decrease on a sliding scale, thereby making the impact of this change in personnel minimal, the requirement to maintain the necessary levels of staffing and expertise is an immediate goal for the OMS node that shall be realised by autumn 2003. It is envisaged that this change in personnel will have no effect on the OMS node contractual commitment to S&F. Moreover, provision has been made with ThermoFinnigan for extensive training of OMS node (Dr ID Bull) and related staff in the operation of all the new instrumentation recently purchased using funds secured through SRIF. Such training is also transferable to older generation instrumentation housed by the node ensuring the base of expertise from which a continued successful operation of the OMS node will propagate.

The OMS node under the auspices of the University of Bristol will continue its collaboration with ThermoFinnigan in the development and application of new GC/C/IRMS technologies and it is hoped that significant advancements in this project will be realised over the coming period. The node will be the test-base and therefore the first facility worldwide to exploit any new technologies derived from this promising collaboration.

The 2003-2004 period is also a time of restructuring and consolidation for the newly formed LSMSF as a whole. Whilst initial steps towards an acceptable level of unification of the three former Facilities (LSCIF, ^{15}N SIF and OMSF) have already been made (e.g. standardisation of application forms, advertising of LSMSF) there is still some progress to be made before a viable, coherent, operational entity is realised. Whilst initial promotional overtures for LSMSF have been made to the UK user community through the recent SIMSUG conference, hosted by the University of Bristol, it is essential that further promotional activities be undertaken in order to increase the exposure of LSMSF. Such activities in the 2003-2004 period will utilize both NERC (NERC News) and non-NERC (e.g. mailshots) promotional routes as well see the creation of a single LSMSF webpage to facilitate access for potential applicants. Furthermore, the webpage should be utilised as a resource to aid applicants, users and node staff alike through the inclusion of useful information available for download, e.g. application notes and methodologies. By making such information readily available knowledge transfer between nodes will be increased as will be the quality of applications originating from a more informed user base. It is the intention of the OMS node to be fully participative in the development of LSMSF into a fully unified flagship Facility within the S&F portfolio.

13 January 2004

Our ref:

Dr David Lynn
Director, Science and Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU

Dear Dr Lynn

As Chairman of the Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service (ORADS) Steering Committee I am writing to endorse and commend to you the Services Review Group 2004 application produced on behalf of ORADS by Drs Ramsey and Higham. ORADS continues to operate entirely successfully and cost-effectively at the highest international level, providing an outstanding asset, which reflects well on NERC and British science in general.

You will see from the appendices to the application that exciting research projects involving very high-quality science by the British archaeological and palaeoenvironmental communities are being supported by NERC through ORADS, with consequent wider educational benefit through resultant publication. I would also draw your attention to the very sensible proposals in Appendix 9 for closer collaboration between the two NERC service radiocarbon laboratories.

I am personally extremely pleased with the operation of ORADS and believe the present application and appendices are a true reflection of the current position and future potential of the service. Renewal of facility support by NERC will be warmly welcomed by every researcher and organization involved directly or indirectly with radiocarbon dating.

Yours sincerely

Alan Saville
Curator, Archaeology
(E-mail: a.saville@nms.ac.uk)

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE <i>ORADS</i>	FUNDING	AGREEMENT	ESTABLISHED as S&F	TERM
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

ORADS (the Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Dating Service) carries out dating for projects approved by NERC, as a part of the operation of the Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Unit (ORAU). The area in which ORAU offers particular specialisation is in archaeological dating. This involves the analysis of a range of issues, such as different materials and burial environments, and complex relationships between the dateable event and the archaeologically significant date.

Radiocarbon dating is applicable to organic material that has survived over the last 50,000 years. The use of accelerator mass spectrometry (the AMS method) permits samples containing 1 mg of carbon and smaller to be dated to an accuracy of about ± 40 years. Choice of each sample is critical, necessitating selection at archaeological, biostratigraphic and chemical levels. In particular, chemical purification methods must be employed to minimise the effect of environmental contamination on the measured date. ORAU has developed over 20 different procedures for this.

Most ORADS projects are for science-based archaeology, but include some environmental projects using ORAU's expertise in the chemistry of bone dating - such as dating the occupation of identified species of frogs and newts in caves after the last Ice Age. The archaeological projects vary enormously, from establishing the earliest occurrence of "anatomically-modern Man" in Europe to providing a statistically validated detailed chronology for the phases of a Saxon settlement.

Dating information is vital to the building of archaeological and environmental historical knowledge, and therefore to most of the research in these subjects in the HEIs supportable by NERC. For the most part, ORADS manages numerous proposed individual projects judged worthy of support. An additional, usually lesser, source of projects is as part of Research Grant Awards. ORADS is able to co-ordinate projects, so that the chronological framework of the whole is greater than all the parts. A recent example of this, which is almost underway, is the EFCHED programme, in which ORAU is centrally involved.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review:		
Need	Uniqueness	Quality of Service	Quality of Science & Training	Average
5	4	3.5	4	4.13

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F	Staff & Status Current contract for c. 250 dates per annum, plus supplemental projects as agreed	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March)
20%		2005	31/3/05

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY							
Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k	
	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3				
	0.494			6.707	0	130.08	
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)							
2002-03	138k	2003-04	196.7	2004-05	152.6	2004-06	2006-07

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
ORADS	5-6	2/3	Joint meeting with RCLSC at Swindon May 2003

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects								
Other academic	3	9	1	1			1	1
Students	1	4	1	1			1	1
Pilot								
TOTAL	4	8	2	2			2	2
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		4						
Other Academic	2.7	7.3	2.7	2.7	0.3		4.7	4.3
Students	1	4	1	1			1	1
Pilot								
TOTAL	3.7	13.3	3.7	3.7	0.3		5.7	5.3

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects								
Other Academic	3	4	5					1
Students	2							
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
41	32	5		0	0	4	0	0	0	0

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
48	35	7	1	0	0	5	0	0	0	0

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic 32	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD 11	Commercial
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic 35	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
17							17			
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
17										
OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
28							28			
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
35										

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OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

New AMS system

The new AMS system supported by the JIF fund (through NERC) is now installed, tested and now dating archaeological samples. The instrument is producing significant improvements in precision, throughput and in background. The old AMS system is no longer operational, it has been decommissioned. New laboratory space is in the final stages of planning and construction will commence within the next 3 months.

New mass spectrometer

A new Europa mass spectrometer has recently been ordered. This will be situated in a new purpose-built mass spectrometer laboratory in the space made vacant by the old AMS. A new gas collection system will enable this MS instrument and the older Europa instrument to be equipped with collection units which will enable greater throughput and flexibility in AMS.

Developments in methodology

With the arrival of the new AMS system, we are now working on commissioning the already planned methodological improvements for handling compound-specific samples. As planned earlier, this includes the commissioning of a new GCCIRMS instrument which is also aimed at providing a GCC-AMS capability.

Developments in sample methodologies are ongoing, including investigations into the isolate of chitin from insects, which is yielding exciting preliminary results, the development of efforts to date single amino acids, the dating of iron, the pretreatment and dating of cremated bone and improvements in the handling of carbonate samples.

Quality system

Following accreditation to the ISO-9002 standard last year we have received complimentary audits from the BSI. We are now developing the system towards compliance with ISO-9001:2000, the latest version of the standard. There have been several enhancements to our Quality Assurance system.

For comments about reproducibility see Optional Annex 9.

QRA meeting and ¹⁴C and Archaeology Conference

The publication of the proceedings of the QRA conference and the 4th meeting of the ¹⁴C and Archaeology symposium are well advanced. Staff will be attending the UK Archaeological Science conference in Oxford in 2003 and chairing or co-chairing sessions as well as presenting papers.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

1. DNA of bison in north America/Siberia (University of Oxford)

This project is ongoing, with further ORADS-NERC support this year for an additional 15 determinations. This work has been undertaken in collaboration with Alan Cooper and colleagues at the Ancient Biomolecules Centre in Oxford. Key publications in *Science* or *Nature* are anticipated in the next year as the results are published. Further collaborative research into the phylogenetic histories of extinct large cats, hair of various species and wolves and dogs are planned in the near future.

2. Dating the evidence for early treponemal diseases in Europe (University of Durham)

The question of whether treponemal diseases such as syphilis originated in the Old World and introduced with European explorers in to the New World or vice versa is a crucial one. Archaeologists at Durham University obtained support for a series of measurements of skeletal remains from the Hull Magistrates Court site in Hull which have evidence for syphilitic condition. The results could show definitively the origin of the disease.

3. Dating the Niah Great Cave (University of Leicester)

The second largest cave in the world, Niah is located in Borneo (Sarawak) and is probably most famous for the discovery of the so-called 'Deep Skull', a 40 000 BP modern human which constitutes the earliest evidence for human presence in this region. Unfortunately, the early excavations, undertaken largely privately, were never comprehensively written up. ORAU is collaborating with Prof. G. Barker of Leicester in an extensive ORADS dating programme to place some of the key archaeological contexts within a proper chronological framework. Central to this is major experimental programme designed to test the dating of samples close to the radiocarbon background and provide replicated and accurate dates for sediments within and below the 'Deep Skull'.

4. Extinction of Megafauna in Europe (University College London)

This large project (350 dates over three years, NERC ref. GR3/12599; dates funded as supplement to facility block-allocation) is nearing completion. It aims to document the latest reported occurrences of now extinct large mammals (mammoths, rhinos, giant deer, etc) in Europe during Oxygen Isotope Stages 3 and 2.

The project is challenging because the samples are small, from museums and often conserved, often contain little collagen, and can be at the date range limit for radiocarbon.

Results so far are extremely significant, with strong evidence for the late survival of *Megaloceros* and firmer chronologies being developed for the latest mammoths populations in northwest Europe. Publications are expected in major scientific journals.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

The new AMS system is operational and producing, as expected, significant improvements in the following areas:

- Improved efficiency (reduced turn-around times and higher throughput)
- Improved precision (allowing us to work towards higher precision dating - as the pre-treatment techniques develop)
- Improved background (allowing the reliable dating of older material, and perhaps more importantly the enhanced ability to study methodological issues arising with very old samples).

New research collaborations are now developing on a number of fronts. For example, the development of preparation and pre-treatment work on chitin dating from insects has yielded promising initial results (being presented at ACS conference, New Orleans 2003) and the analysis of single amino acids is developing using the new HPLC system recently purchased as well as the efforts of a recently arrived PDRA from Berkeley (Dr J. Tripp). In addition, the development of compound specific dating of lipids, atmospheric pollutant and tracer work is ongoing aided through the service provision of ORADS.

Compound specific work is still seen as a key area in further development of the AMS methodology bringing, as it does, the ability to efficiently deal with samples right down to the microgram level. An on-line gas feed to the ion source for the measurement of extremely small samples coupled with a system for collecting CO₂ samples resulting from GC-combustion systems (as used in GC-C-IRMS) are currently being constructed.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

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8 July 2003

Mr David Lin
Science Programmes Directorate
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wilts SN2 1EU

Dear David,

NERC Isotope Geoscience Facilities: Annual Reports

On behalf of the Steering Committee I write to approve the annual reports from the facility managers of:

NERC Isotope Geoscience Laboratory (NIGL) at BGS;
NERC Isotope Community support Facility (ICSF) at SUERC;
NERC Argon Isotope Facility (AIF) SUERC; and
NERC Uranium Series Facility at the Open University (OUUSF)

Over the past 12 months all four facilities have continued to respond positively to the increasingly competitive scientific criteria imposed by the committee and we endorse the progress made in both the range and quality of science that they have undertaken. For 3 of the facilities, recent months have been dominated by the Review, the results of which, relative to previous reviews, I enclose. The committee was pleased to see upward movement by all 3 facilities, virtually across the board. It is interesting to note that the Review identified a marked increase in 'uniqueness', emphasizing that the skills and resources that are offered cannot be found elsewhere in the U.K. The most outstanding progress however, was made by NERC Isotope Geochemistry Laboratory increasing its average grade from 3.8 to 4.25. In my view this success reflects the sustained high level of work approved by the committee, the innovative science now being undertaken, the strong publication record and the effective management of the Facility by Prof. Parrish.

Yours sincerely,

Prof. N.B.W. Harris
Encl:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Nigel Harris', written over the typed name and 'Encl:'.

**SRG 2003 Facility Review Scoring
(previous review in parentheses)**

	NEED	Uniqueness	Quality of service	Quality of science and training	Average
ICSF	4.0 (4.0)	5.0 (4.5)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
OU USF	4.0 (4.0)	4.5 (3.0)	4.5 (4.5)	4.5 (4.5)	4.38 (4.25)
NERC IGL	4.5 (4.4)	4.0 (3.4)	4.5 (4.0)	4.0 (3.6)	4.25 (3.8)
AIF	(4.5)	(5.0)	(4.0)	(5.0)	(4.63)

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE: OUUSF Open University Uranium Series Facility NERC/IF/209	FUNDING: Contract F14/G6/47	AGREEMENT	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1998	TERM 3 year
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:
 U-series analyses are an essential component of research projects in Earth and environmental science and science-based archaeology. Topics include magma chamber evolution and volcanic hazard prediction, global climatic change through dating of authigenic carbonate deposits, and human evolution through dating of bone, and potentially the study of groundwater evolution

OUUSF provides state-of-the-art U-series isotope preparation labs, a high abundance sensitivity Finnigan MAT 262 solid source mass spectrometer, a Nu Instruments plasma ionisation mass spectrometer and a New Wave Excimer laser ablation system. Access to all U-series systems is subject to availability, as determined by the Manager of the OUUSF and the Open University Isotope Geochemistry Laboratory (OUIGL).

The normal basis of operation is collaborative research via U-series measurements. OUUSF provides access for training and research in the application of U-series systems to NERC-related research, in particular geochemistry, Quaternary science, archaeology and hydrogeology. OUUSF provides the equivalent of one user-year of training and analyses per annum, which represents 25% of OUIGL capacity and corresponds to circa 165 project samples. Quality Assurance is maintained through the repeated analysis of internal standards and Certified Reference Materials, reagent and total-procedure blanks and calibrations, performed by staff and users, equivalent to some 60 samples per year.

Users should have, or be prepared to learn at the OUUSF, the analytical skills necessary for successful processing of samples in a clean room, for working with radioactive materials, and for using isotope ratio mass spectrometers. OUIGL and OUUSF staff are primarily involved in supervision of post-graduates and have limited capacity to perform analyses for collaborators.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: 2003	
Need	Uniqueness	Quality of Service	Quality of Science & Training	Average
4	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.38

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F	Staff & Status Dr P. van Calsteren Senior Research Fellow 0% Dr M.A. Gilmour Project Officer 70% Dr L.E. Thomas Research Fellow 0% J. Rhodes Technician Grade E 100%,	Next Review (January)	Contract Ends (31 March)
25 %		2006	2004

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY						
Recurrent Allocation £k 82.66	Unit Cost £k			Capital Expend £k 0.00	Income £k 0.00	Full cash cost £k 82.66
	Unit 1 0.500	Unit 2	Unit 3			
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)						
2003-04 90	2004-05 85	2005-06 88	2006-07 91	2007-08		

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
Isotope Geoscience Facilities	15 (Chair, Prof N Harris OU)	2	NIGL, AIF, ICSF

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects			1					
Other academic		1	1					
Students								
Pilot								
TOTAL								
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 - 2000/2001 & 2002/2003)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		.33	2.67					
Other Academic		1	1.33					
Students								
Pilot		.33						
TOTAL								

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	
NERC Grant projects		.33	1.67					
Other Academic		.33	.67					
Students								
Pilot			.33					

USER PROFILE (current FY)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	
3	1	2			2					

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total		NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total		NERC C/S	
5.33	3	1	0.33		2.33					

USER PROFILE (current FY)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
3			2	
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
5	0.33		1.33	

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
	4						4	6	9	
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
	3									

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
1.67	2						3.67	3.33	3.33	.33
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
.67	3.67									

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2001/02):

During this report year 12 projects graded $\alpha 3$ high to $\alpha 4$, on average, were active. Two projects form part of a PhD project and these received extensive training at the OUUSF. Three papers involving OUUSF staff were published in peer-reviewed, and another 14 manuscripts are 'in press' or 'submitted'.

The MAT 262 mass spectrometer has been out of action for two months of this report year due to the HEFCE/OU funded refurbishment project. The Nu-instruments Multi-Collector Plasma Ionisation Mass Spectrometer has been available for OUUSF work throughout and the New Wave Excimer laser ablation system has been commissioned in March. Chemical dissolutions and separations have been carried out in custom-designed perspex containment boxes, since July. Thanks to the forward planning, hard work and determination of staff and post-graduates, the full complement of contracted samples has been analysed in this report year.

Scientific highlights this year include:

Precise dating of Dansgaard-Oeschger climate oscillations in western Europe from speleothem data.

A better understanding of the millennial scale Dansgaard-Oeschger (DO) events, rapid temperature fluctuations of several degrees over 100's to 1000's of years, is highly relevant because the rate of temperature change into and out of DO events is comparable to the rate at present. Some twenty DO events have occurred in the last 80 ky and they are evident in both ocean sediment and ice-core records. Heinrich events have a similar temperature effect but are associated with clearly identified sediment layers that are rich in clastic material, probably caused by ice rafting. DO events are a probable consequence of stagnation of the Gulf Stream and the formation of North Atlantic Deep Water but the underlying cause is as yet, unclear. Evaluation of the effects of DO events on continental climate and vegetation is closely linked to the gathering of additional data and to better absolute chronologies. This is particularly important for the period beyond the ^{14}C dating limit for marine and lake records and beyond the limit of annual layer counting in ice cores.

Genty et al., (Nature 2003), have analysed carbon and oxygen stable isotope profiles on a stalagmite, collected from Grotte de Villars, in southern France less than 200 km from the Atlantic Ocean which very clearly shows DO events. OUUSF has dated 28 points along this stalagmite, between 83 and 32 ka with uncertainties less than 2% 2σ using the Uranium-series method and making this the best-dated climate archive for this period. Linkage of the DO events in the Villars record with ice-core and deep-sea sediment records provides improved further time constrains for those records.

The main climatic feature of the Villars record is the confirmation of the rapidity of onset and amelioration of the DO events with rates of change up to ten Celcius per century. Most DO events last for about one millenium. Drastic and rapid vegetation changes were associated with DO events in this area of Western Europe where many prehistoric cultures have been recognised. If the present global temperature increase also results in the interruption of the Gulf Stream then the climate during DO events may well be a guide to what can be expected in the future.

Corals to estimate earthquake frequencies

Marine terraces that have been raised by fault activity in central Greece have been dated using corals. In the study area 10 (magnitude 6.0) earthquakes have occurred in the last century, but the frequency of earthquakes is poorly constrained due to the lack of data on rates of fault-slip. Initial U-series ages showed unexpected complexity and several ages did not match the presumed tectonic history of the region. Further fieldwork to resolve this issue showed that, in fact, the dates were a guide to previously unknown complexity of terrace formation. Unrecognised hiatus surfaces marked by thin calcretes allowed multiple terraces to be identified in vertical section. Once identified, and the sedimentological expression of terrace superposition recognised, the terraces were found to be compound, thereby validating the coral U-series ages. This result allows a considerable refinement to be made in the estimation of rates of fault slip. Multiple and accurate dates on terraces from central Greece are of great significance in the evaluation of deformation rates both locally and regionally and for assessing the changing intensity of differential uplift throughout the region. They are pivotal in testing the hypothesis of Morewood and Roberts (1999) concerning styles and rates of fault slip.

Lake marls

U-series disequilibrium dating of lake sediments is often complicated due to the presence of detrital ^{230}Th within the sample matrix. The analysis of bulk sample thus provides a ^{230}Th signature that is comprised of detrital and authigenic ^{230}Th , and yields an apparent age much older than reality. Many attempts at leaching such samples have yielded non-reproducible results. However, exciting results from lacustrine sediments from Hawes Water (NW Lancashire, UK) indicate that this particular lake has marls that are less affected by detrital thorium input than many other lakes. Hawes Water, a small shallow lake, is much more responsive to climatic and hydrological change than large deep-water lakes. U-series ages match rather well with a proxy chronology based on pollen horizons and stable isotopic data. Trace element and stable isotope data for the Holocene sequence at Hawes Water indicate considerable climatic change during the last 10 ky contrary to popular belief that the Holocene in NW Europe since the Younger Dryas as been a climatologically quiet period. This is the first attempt to combine high-resolution stable isotopic and geochemical data with an absolute chronology of a NW European shallow lake.

In a multi-user, multi-project laboratory it is essential to maintain high levels of Quality Control and 130 analyses (18.4 sample equivalent for OUUSF) have been carried out on shelf standards and Certified Reference Materials, reagent and procedure blanks and instrument performance standards.

OUUSF has a Website at <http://www2.open.ac.uk/ri/nssindex.htm> with 'Science Highlights', it also features images of the recent refurbishment work.

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2001/02): Full projects approved by the NIGF Steering Committee are:

PHILIP L. GIBBARD, Geography, Cambridge: *Quaternary Glaciations in the Pindus Mountains, Northwest Greece*. U-Series dating of post-depositional calcite deposits (calcretes) that are present within limestone-derived till sediments in the glaciated headwaters of the Voidomatis River Basin. The data will provide minimum ages for the glacial sediments and strategic sampling and detailed geomorphological mapping will allow a robust geochronology to be established and will establish local, regional and Mediterranean-wide correlations with the glacial sequences.

The field area is one of the most southerly examples of Pleistocene glaciation in Europe (40°N), the glacial sediments and landforms represent an important source of information on the nature of the Mediterranean climate during cold stages of the Pleistocene. This project will also test whether phases of ice build-up and decay in the Mediterranean mountains were in phase with the various proxy records that have been produced for the North Atlantic Region and with the records of glacier and ice-sheet dynamics developed for central and northwest Europe.

JOHN MCARTHUR, Geology, UCL: *Earthquake hazards calibrated using U-series dating*.

This is to complete the highly promising project on dating of Cladocora corals on uplifted marine terraces at the Perachora Peninsula, Greece. See Scientific Highlights above.

ANDY BAKER, Newcastle: *A 450 year annually resolved stalagmite record of Ethiopian climate*.

Drought and associated problems of famine affect Ethiopia, due to the dependence of its population on subsistence agriculture, such that if either one of the two seasonal rains fail, famine can result. Historical climate data (instrumental rainfall and Nile discharge) for the region suggest possible correlation of rain failure with ~5 yr, cyclicity in sea surface temperatures, and possible decadal variations in Nile discharge. Long high-resolution climate records are required to investigate the frequency of the failure of rains and the presence of decadal periodicity's in climate. Stalagmites can provide such high-resolution climate archives and a continuously laminated (451 laminae) Holocene sample has been analysed for lamina width variations. Spectral analysis demonstrates statistically significant peaks; using a wide range of spectral windows. Replicable peaks are observed at periodicity's that include the ~5 year period observed in historical rainfall records in the region and those similar to the decadal periods in Nile flood discharge. High-precision U-series dating on this lamina width series will constrain the time frame and confirm that laminae are annual.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

Analytical developments

The sensitivity of our new plasma ionisation mass spectrometer is such that it should be possible, in favourable circumstances, to measure ($^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$) and ($^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$) *in situ* using our new UV Excimer laser ablation system. This technique has important applications for stalagmite and bone samples but also for individual minerals, including zircons. However, laser ablation adds another process by which mass and element fractionation takes place and it is essential to develop and calibrate sophisticated data reduction protocols.

Expanding OUSF capability

A potential area of development is likely to be the mass spectrometric analysis of ^{231}Pa , the daughter of ^{235}U . ^{231}Pa has a half-life of ~35,000 y and is particularly useful as, in principle, it can provide confirmation of ages obtained by ^{230}Th dating. Two independent estimates of the age from the same sample would be of much use in the dating of speleothem carbonate and particularly in archaeological bone using the Oxford U-uptake model (Millard and Hedges, 1996), recently further developed for U-series (see Pike *et al.*, 2003).

Hydrogeology

- Oxygenated recharge waters have extremely high U/Th and high $^{230}\text{Th}/^{232}\text{Th}$, and both decrease with time under reducing conditions. Combined with other trace element characteristics and data from flow models, U-series isotopes may be used to determine residence times in aquifers (Osmond and Cowart, 1992). This approach has potentially important applications for drinking water extraction, and elsewhere for understanding the likely effects of discharges from the nuclear and other industries.
- A study of the Great Artesian Basin to evaluate the utility of U-series nuclides for the study of groundwater systems has been funded by NERC. U-series data (including Th, U, Ra and Rn), will be combined with noble gas data (Ar and He). This study is a test-bed for the combined application of these isotopes, and will potentially provide information on the climatic conditions at recharge (noble gas palaeotemperature) and the mobility and retention of U-series nuclides in the subsurface environment. Furthermore, it should be possible to calculate time-scales of nuclide fractionation, erosion rates in continental interiors and their effect on climate, and possibly the impact of deep crustal fluid inputs.
- U-series data (together with $\delta^6\text{Li}$) have been used successfully to assess silicate weathering rates in a few climate zones and there is great scope for extension. Moreover, there is no consensus on the palaeo-variations of the controlling factors of silicate weathering rates.

Hydrothermal systems and possible analogues for radioactive waste

Another area of where U-series isotope analyses have significant potential is in the investigation of natural hydrothermal systems. High temperature geothermal fields are found at a number of localities in volcanically and seismically active areas on the Earth's surface, and represent 'natural laboratories' where the reactions which take place between high temperature fluids and silicate rock may be investigated at first hand. The behaviour of naturally occurring radioactive elements in high-temperature fluids may provide an analogue for radioactive waste studies, and the measurement of natural short-lived isotopes such as ^{234}U , ^{230}Th , ^{228}Ra and ^{226}Ra allows constraints to be placed on the time scales of fluid movement.

Resource requirements:

It is not anticipated that major capital investment will be required in the next three years.

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**Dr David Lynn,
Director, Science and Innovation,
NERC
Polaris House,
North star Avenue,
Swindon SN2 1EU**

Our reference

Your reference

Date

17th June 2003

Dear Dr Lynn,

I write this covering letter to accompany the Annual Report of the NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory, and to formally transmit it to you in my capacity as Chairman of the NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory Steering Committee. The report was seen in draft and considered by the Steering Committee at its meeting in Swindon, 14-15th May 2003. The draft has been modified in line with comments made at that meeting.

As with previous years the report describes a further twelve months of achievement at the highest scientific level. Perhaps particularly noteworthy are the statistics for projects supported by the laboratory during the year (63 – up 14 on last year), and the number of dates reported (1206 from a total theoretical capacity of 1300). The JIF-funded AMS at East Kilbride is now in commission and awaiting its final acceptance tests, a singular milestone for UK radiocarbon science. The very well attended launch ceremony for the AMS last year is also a measure of the esteem in which the East Kilbride facility is held among the Quaternary and radiocarbon communities.

The participation of Dr S. Moreton in the South Georgia expedition underlines key the role of the laboratory in Antarctic science and also gave considerable publicity for the laboratories' activities in the media.

On a personal note, this is my last year as chair of the RCL-SC, and I would like to put on formal record my admiration for the work of the laboratory in supporting UK science. The standards improve every year and the RCL-SC continues to be a world-class facility of which NERC can be very proud.

I commend the report for 2002-2003 to you and would be pleased if it could be circulated as appropriate in NERC.

Yours sincerely,

Professor David H. Keen

**C O V E N T R Y
U N I V E R S I T Y**

INVESTOR IN PEOPLE

School of Science and the Environment

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT F14/6/3/01	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1975	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

Precise dating is fundamental to the timing of events and rates of processes. For timescales up to 50,000 years the most versatile technique is radiocarbon. Radiocarbon is also a useful tool for studying carbon dynamics in the natural environment. The Radiocarbon Laboratory (RCL) provides natural abundance ¹⁴C analyses (Radiometric and Accelerator Mass Spectrometric) for Earth and Environmental Scientists. Together with scientific advice and collaborative involvement by RCL, projects underpin priority areas identified by NERC as major issues on the environmental and natural resource agenda, currently covering all five ENRIs.

RCL is a NERC Strategic Facility hosted by the Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre (SUERC). The majority of RCL's resources are dedicated to projects approved by the RCLSC. Income earned via commissioned research (collaborative with NERC Centres and Surveys or with international collaborators) and a limited amount of commercial work is either reinvested in the facility or returned to NERC S&F budget.

The four scientific staff provide a breadth of expertise to provide advice at all stages of projects to maximise scientific return. In-house specialists cover areas as diverse as: **climate change** (e.g. Late Quaternary environments, palaeoecological studies of peatlands, proxy records of past climate, **human influences** and chronological indicators); **carbon dynamics** (e.g. in forests, peats and soils, stream and lake systems) and the impact of **land-use change** on different carbon components (dissolved organic carbon, the **greenhouse gases** carbon dioxide and methane, chemical fractions including compound-specific components); **marine and freshwater systems** (including Antarctic and Arctic marine and freshwater sediments). Close communication and collaborative links with the user community are fundamental to achieving high quality science and maximising value for money. RCL promotes this by:- laboratory residences; collaboration on projects from conception onwards; optimising sampling strategies and adapting quality control procedures; interpreting results, and redaction of publications. We outreach through staff visits and seminars, and workshop participation, and we represent UK science at international conferences. There are strong programmes in thematic, EU and non-thematic research in NERC Centres and Surveys, as well as collaboration with international scientists. As part of RCL's commitment to providing reliable radiocarbon data via in-house quality control procedures, RCL continues both as participant and co-organiser in International Radiocarbon Intercomparison programmes. The broad range of scientific expertise ensures that RCL is poised to adapt as new research agendas are raised. Development work in a variety of areas continues to stimulate innovative research applications, many of which are collaborative.

Training of students and visiting researchers and the promotion of good practice in radiocarbon analytical procedures is an important facet of RCL contributing to NERC's remit to provide the UK with a cadre of trained personnel. On-site training now incorporates the JIF-funded SUERC Accelerator Mass Spectrometer.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: 30/01/02		
Need 5.0	Uniqueness 4.5	Quality of Service 4.5	Quality of Science & Training 5.0	Average 4.75

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 97%	Staff & Status Est=established FT=fixed term; All 100% Scientific: NERC: Head of RCL, Band 5s (Est, part time); Glasgow Univ.: 2x PDRA 1A (2FT, 1 part time) 1xPDRA 2A (FT); Technical: 3 x Grade E (2FT, 1Est); 1 x Grade F (Est); Administrative: 1 x Grade 4 (Est);	Next Review (January) 2007	Contract Ends (31 March) 2008
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY

Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k		Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	AMS ¹⁴ C analysis	Radiometric ¹⁴ C analysis			
413.62 (spent)	0.450	0.450	11.00	24.95	578.41

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)

2003-04	485	2004-05	500	2005-06	500	2006-07	500	2007-08	500
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STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
RCL-SC	7 (Chair: Prof D Keen, Univ Coventry)	2	One joint meeting with ORADS-SC

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		5						1
Other academic		6	2	2			10	3
Students		10	8		1	1	6	3
TOTAL		21	10	2	1	1	16	7

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1.33	4.00	4.00	0.33	0.00	0.33	1.33	1.00
Other Academic	1.67	2.67	8.33	0.33	1.00	0.67	4.67	5.33
Students	1.00	4.33	9.00	1.33	0.00	0.00	4.67	1.00
TOTAL	4.00	11.00	21.33	2.00	1.00	1.00	11.33	7.67

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY) Projects in which <u>all</u> approved analyses have been completed							
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	Pilot/ rangefinder
NERC Grant projects		4	2				
Other Academic	1		3				2
Students		9	3				6

USER PROFILE (current FY) Projects in which some or all analyses completed						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
51	13	23	7	1	7	0	1	0	3	3

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)						<i>*Combined non-Thematic and Thematic</i>				
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
40.67	7.00	11.33	5.00	3.33	13.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	5.00

USER PROFILE (current FY) Projects in which some or all analyses completed in FY				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
20	1	0	23	7

USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
20.00	3.33	0.00	11.33	6.00

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0	8	4	0	13	0	0	25	18	0	7

Distribution of Projects (by science areas) of approved projects, whether completed or not						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
1	13	14	0	17	0	3

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
0.00	8.00	11.00	0.00	46.67	0.00	4.00	69.67	34.67	26.00	9.00

Distribution of Projects (by science areas) of projects approved, whether completed or not						
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
3.33	8.67	6.33	0.00	19.67	0.00	2.67

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

A busy year with 63 projects approved by RCL-SC, 1137 samples accepted for AMS analysis during the year (94% of which were for RCL-SC approved projects) and 172 samples were accepted for radiometric analysis. RCL staff contributed collaboratively to 25 RCL-SC-approved projects and a further 3 commissioned projects with international collaborators and/or NERC Centre/Surveys.

Analytical Programmes: Turn-round time for radiometric analyses was 4.6 months and for AMS analyses between 1 and 9 months, average 6 months. The total number of samples and standards analysed (radiometric and AMS) was 1206 of an overall capacity of 1300 (1050 for AMS, capacity exceeded; 250 for radiometric, below capacity). Several projects involved a significant amount of development work so the resource implications of preparing these samples for analysis, was greater than for samples prepared using established techniques.

Progress on the East Kilbride AMS Facility: The final acceptance tests for the NEC-manufactured AMS are imminent and results for ^{14}C analyses of standards and backgrounds have already shown that machine operation for ^{14}C is running well. However the focus of current work by NEC and AMS staff is on obtaining machine stability at the high energy required for resolving ^{36}Cl . Graphites from international standards produced by RCL and the Glasgow University (GU) ^{14}C lab are to be run as soon as acceptance tests have been completed. Quantification of background ^{14}C for different pre-treatment methods and sample sizes, together with strong collaboration with Prof Marian Scott (Statistics Department, GU and co-ordinator of International Radiocarbon Intercomparisons) and the AMS team will ensure that the RCL user community continues to receive reliable, high quality radiocarbon data once the AMS is routinely operational for ^{14}C (anticipated Summer 2003).

Health and Safety: Following a thorough review of H&S procedures last year, particularly of emergency drills, we have continued to optimise H&S procedures and develop new procedures as required. RCL's approach to H&S was described as 'exemplary' during a visit by NERC's H&S Adviser, Mr Stuart Dobson. Following discussions with the PI and a visit from the GU Biological Safety Officer, we have designed a safe working procedure for one RCL-SC approved project, which poses potential health hazards. This will ensure safe practices are adopted whilst maintaining the scientific integrity of the samples. Once procedures have been approved by GU Biological Safety Officer, the project will proceed and the investment of time in developing this will benefit similar future projects.

Meetings and workshops

Drs Garnett, Moreton and Bryant (RCL) attended the BGS-hosted meeting on Isotopes in Palaeoclimate Research. Dr Bryant presented an overview of problems inherent in ^{14}C dating, such as hard water effects, marine reservoir effects and mobility of carbon in soil systems. Optimising sampling strategies and interpretation of the accuracy and precision of results e.g. age-depth models were discussed. A seminar on Constructing Late Quaternary chronologies and carbon cycling studies was given jointly by Drs Garnett and Bryant at the Department of Geography, University of Plymouth. This was followed by useful discussions with staff involved in a range of RCL-SC approved projects.

Field Research Dr S Moreton participated in an expedition to South Georgia, Antarctica to mark the centenary year of the Scottish National Antarctic Expedition (1902-04). The study, funded largely by the Royal Scottish Geographical Society, focuses on the environmental changes that have affected the region since the end of the Last Glacial Maximum approximately 20,000 years ago. The expedition will integrate geomorphology, glaciology, sea level change, peat core and lake sediment records and glacier-climate modelling, to establish north-south environmental gradients in climate and palaeoclimate reconstructions over a critical area of the Southern Ocean. Dr Moreton was also involved in a Scottish Association for Marine Science led 'Northern Seas Programme' research cruise to the Arctic. The aim of the programme is to investigate the sensitivity of marine ecosystems to natural and anthropogenic perturbations along a latitudinal gradient from the Irish Sea to the Arctic pack ice zone. The establishment of ^{14}C and ^{210}Pb chronologies will be essential for determining the timing and rate of ecosystem changes. Applications for analytical support for work arising from both cruises have been submitted to RCL-SC.

Student training Dating support was provided for 23 projects involving PhD students. Five PhD students visited RCL to discuss approved projects and receive training in laboratory techniques. A joint NERC studentship commenced October 2002, between Dr B Horton (Durham University), Prof C Anderson (Sheffield University) and Dr Bryant. Ms Sarah Woodroffe will study Holocene sea-level change and coastal evolution in the Central Great Barrier Reef coastline, Australia, a far-field site ie distant from the Last Glacial Maximum ice sheets.

Public Understanding of Science Dr S Moreton contributed to media coverage of the S Georgia expedition:

The Scotsman "For Science and Scotland", "The piper at the pole", Edinburgh Evening News "The iceman cometh...100 years on", The Herald Magazine "Extreme Reaction" and Literary Review "Letter from the Antarctic".

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

RCL-SC APPROVED ANALYSES: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (FY 2002-2003)	$\alpha 5$	$\alpha 4$	$\alpha 3$	$\alpha 2$	$\alpha 1$	β	Ungraded		
							Range-finder	Pilot	Check date
NO. OF ANALYSES (ALL PROJECTS)	0	430	84	0	0	0	30	22	10

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Examples of science addressing some 'fundamental research questions' posed in NERC's scientific plan 2002-2007.

Earth's life support systems

What are the sources, sinks and transportation processes of carbon within the Earth system?

Several collaborative projects have used the documented change in atmospheric ^{14}C due to nuclear weapons testing in the 1960s to elucidate sources and rates of transfer of carbon in a variety of environments: 1. Modelling streamwater organic carbon in two upland catchments with Prof E Tipping, CEH Windermere. The successful ^{14}C -based model of carbon transfer (publication in press), developed by Prof Tipping in previous work with RCL, will be applied to ^{14}C data from particulate and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) in streamwater, collected during high, medium and low flow conditions as well as bulk peat samples and humic, fulvic acids and humin extracts from the soils. 2. Two collaborative commissioned projects with Prof D Berggren, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, and Dr N Clarke, Norwegian Forest Research Institute, will also apply the ^{14}C -based DOC modelling to quantify sources and rates of carbon transfer in forest soils. ^{14}C data from bulk soils, soil extracts and DOC are being obtained. 3. ^{14}C signatures in soil and DOC samples collected from a chronosequence of forests planted on agricultural land (commissioned collaborative work with Dr A Harrison, CEH Merlewood and Prof E Karlun Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences) showed that organic matter mean residence time in the organic soil horizon increases with forest stand age following afforestation. For the top mineral soil, the opposite effect was observed. 4. RCL designed molecular sieve containers were used to collect CO_2 emitted from peaty gley soils under a spruce forest chronosequence and a grassland site. ^{14}C analyses of the CO_2 and of different soil fractions form part of a project quantifying the greenhouse gas balance resulting from afforestation of peat gley soils (Prof K Smith, Edinburgh University).

Dr P Gulliver (RCL) is working with Dr G Darling, CEH Wallingford, and Dr C Cook (GU) on improving preparation methods for ^{14}C analysis of groundwater dissolved organic carbon. Obtaining reliable DOC will improve modelling of groundwater transport, for example to understand biogeochemical processes between surface and groundwater.

Biodiversity & ecosystem evolution: ^{14}C is being used to establish the timing and sources of soil organic matter development in a glacier foreland (Prof Bardgett, Lancaster Univ. collaborative with Dr M Garnett). Results show that as the glacier retreated, old carbon (>10 ka) was initially deposited in the developing soil, but as plants colonise, the ^{14}C signature of the soil beneath them increases and the progressive incorporation of carbon from recently established plants can be quantified.

Climate change

How has the climate changed in the past?

Where pollen assemblages are used to reconstruct palaeoenvironmental conditions for inferring climate changes, chronologies based on ^{14}C analysis of terrestrial pollen concentrates, rather than bulk organic matter, should be more reliable. Drs R Newnham and M Vandergoes, Plymouth University and Dr M Garnett, RCL have analysed bulk material and pollen concentrates from above and below a relatively well-constrained tephra horizon at a high rainfall site in New Zealand. The high rainfall increases the possibility for younger material to be moved down the profile and incorporated into bulk organic matter. Initial results show that the pollen concentrates ages are older than the organic residue fractions, and closer to the 'accepted' age of the tephra, supporting the hypothesis that the pollen provide ^{14}C results which are closer to the age of the horizon under investigation.

Tephrochronology offers the potential to correlate precisely between palaeoenvironmental records (as proxies for climatic conditions) from peat and lake sediments, and other proxy data such as ice core records and tree rings. It can reduce the need for ^{14}C analyses for archaeological and palaeoenvironmental studies. The potential for this depends on accurate and precise dating of the tephra markers. Prof K Barber, Southampton University, is currently using ^{14}C to determine the age and synchronicity of the Glen Garry tephra, an Icelandic volcanic ash layer, which is widespread and distinct in peat bogs of northern England and Scotland. The Glen Garry tephra lies between the well-known Hekla-4 tephra at 3800BP and the historic 'AD 860 tephra layer' an important period during which to study relative impacts of humans and climate on the environment.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

- The second graphitisation line should be operational by the end of summer of 2003. This will improve turn-round times, especially if a large number of samples are submitted during a short time, as experienced during summer 2002.
- Refurbishment of laboratory space to improve efficiency and turn-round times for the AMS programme commences during summer 2003. Maintaining radiometric capability (using less lab space) remains relevant, especially for large soil samples, which are often required for commissioned projects on carbon dynamics.
- Appointment of a two year post-doctoral research assistant to commission and refine procedures for preparation and analysis of small samples and become collaboratively involved with relevant projects. This will involve collaboration with the AMS team to commission the AMS CO_2 source, enabling RCL to provide ^{14}C analyses on tens of microgram quantities of carbon and opportunities for compound-specific ^{14}C dating.
- Approximately 300 ^{14}C analyses are required for the NERC thematic programme 'Rapid Climate Change'.

INTER-AGENCY COMMITTEE ON MARINE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

THG/1.1

1 December 2003

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Dear David

Annual Report of Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service 2002/2003

Please find enclosed the report for 2002/2003 which was considered at the meeting of the Steering Committee held in London on 9 June 2003. The Committee was extremely pleased with the report of the year's achievements.

I would like to draw attention to one or two aspects of the Annual Report and Forward Look.

- 1) The highest ever total for refereed papers had been recorded. This was largely due to the high level of SeaWiFS-related papers now being published. The majority of papers still used Dundee data, but an increasing number used data from other sources.
- 2) The Steering Committee noted with considerable concern the issue of access to SeaWiFS data. Until now this has been provided through a NASA contract with ORBIMAGE, but the contract ends in December 2003 and is unlikely to be renewed. NASA had advised users to contact ORBIMAGE directly regarding access beyond December 2003.

There was general agreement on the need for continued access to SeaWiFS, at least until there is an established MODIS ocean colour service. The Committee agreed that DSRS/RSDAS should continue negotiations with ORBIMAGE to establish the terms for future access. As a member of the UK Delegation I also raised this issue at the IOC (Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission) Assembly in June 2003 and found wide support from other Member States. As a result, the IOC Executive Secretary has been instructed to raise this matter with NASA.

- 3) A total of 16 research cruises had been supported, which was also a record and continued the upward trend. The total number of cruise support days was approximately 40% increase on the previous year partly due to support provided for the NERC Marine Productivity thematic programme, which funded RSDAS for approximately 100 days of cruise support. For the first time BAS had requested RSDAS support (for the RRS James Clark Ross cruise to the Scotia Sea).

With regards

Trevor Guymer
Chair DSRS Steering Committee

enclosure

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service	FUNDING Block	AGREEMENT CONTRACT	ESTABLISHED as S&F April 1995	TERM 5 Years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

The RSDAS mission is to research, develop and operate systems for cost-effective processing and analysis of remote sensing data on behalf of NERC and UK academic communities, delivering high-quality products in a timely fashion to support peer-reviewed applications.

RSDAS provides value-added remote sensing data, supplied in near-real time or from the archive, derived primarily from imagery received at the Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS). Products include geo-referenced sea-surface temperature, land brightness temperature and vegetation index from AVHRR, chlorophyll and other ocean colour properties from SeaWiFS and cloud products from MODIS. A separate NERC grant supports development of MODIS ocean colour products. Most products are supplied as high-resolution regional data to complement lower-resolution global data sets provided by NASA and ESA. A flexible approach to each request allows user-driven products and analyses, including compositing, extraction of positional data, and time-series studies. Additional sources of satellite data on the Internet are exploited if a region is requested outside the coverage of DSRS.

The user community is mainly marine with a growing number of atmospheric, terrestrial and earth science users. Applications can be submitted at any time and are peer-reviewed by the DSRS Steering Committee. Requests are often made to complement measurements taken on field studies or cruises, either to provide a wider spatial or temporal context. An important and unique aspect of the service is the ability to process satellite data on the same day as acquisition to provide guidance to research cruises and ensure cost-effective use of expensive ship time.

RSDAS also fulfils an important training role for future environmental scientists by supporting PhD and MSc projects, even if such applications obtain mid-alpha grading. Imagery processed for RSDAS users is made available to the wider community on a web site to promote scientific communication, attracting further research users and inspiring school projects world-wide.

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)		Date of Last Review: January 1999		
Need 5	Uniqueness 4.5	Quality of Service 5	Quality of Science & Training 4	Average 4.63

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 100 %	Staff & Status FY 2002-3 Steve Groom, Head of Service (15 % PML funded, B4)	Next Review (January) 2004	Contract Ends (31 March) 2005
	Dr Pete Miller, RSDAS manager (33%, B6) Dr Tim Smyth, MODIS Development (25%, B6) Dr Peter Land, ARSF/MODIS Development (60%, B6) Dr Kate Evans-Jones, Development (100%,B6) Mr Gareth Mottram, Data Analysis (80%,B7) (2.98 Full-Time Equivalent)		

FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY									
Recurrent Allocation £k	Unit Cost £k						Capital Expend £k	Income £k	Full cash cost £k
	HSO hours	SO hours	Routine images	Archive images	Composite images	Real-time support			
107 + 29 for MODIS	28	18	3	5	13	100	30	-	151

FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement)		
2003-04	£115k	2004-05 £121k
		2005-06 -

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
DSRSSC	6	1	DSRS, NEODC
ARSFSC (report for info)	7	2	ARSF, NEODC

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Received during current FY only — 2002/03)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		4						
Other academic		6	3					
Students		1	4					
Pilot								
TOTAL: 18		11	7					
APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (per annum average previous 3 years — 1999/2000 2000/2001 & 2001/2002)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects	1.33	4.67	2.33					
Other Academic	0.33	8.00	5.33					
Students	0.33	1.33	5.33					
Pilot								
TOTAL	2.00	14.00	13.00					

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)								
	α5	α4	α3	α2	α1	β	R*/Pilot	Reject
NERC Grant projects		3						
Other Academic		7	3					
Students		1	5					
Pilot								

USER PROFILE (current FY, including requests related to applications from previous years) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
36	6	10	4	9	11					
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years) *Combined non-Thematic and Thematic										
Grand Total	Infrastructure					PAYG				
	Supplement to NERC Grant *	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other	NERC Grant*	Student Total	NERC	NERC C/S	Other
30.67	8.33	9.00	4.50	6.00	10.33					

USER PROFILE (current FY, including requests related to applications from previous years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
16	11	1	8	-
USER PROFILE (per annum average previous 3 years)				
Academic	Centre/Survey	NERC Fellows	PhD	Commercial
17.67	8.67	1.67	2.67	-

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SB A	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
-	2	56	6	-	6	-	65 70	32	34	3
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
-	1	24	1	2	8	-				
OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average previous 3 years)										
Publications (by science area & type)										
SB A	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Grand Total	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses
-	1.00	47.33	0.67	0.00	4.33	-	53.33	18.67	31.33	3.33
Distribution of Projects (by science areas)										
SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar				
-	1.33	24.00	0.33	0.67	4.44	-				

OVERVIEW & ACTIVITIES IN FINANCIAL YEAR (2002/03):

Output and performance measures

- In 2002/3 RSDAS supported 16 cruises with near real time images, the highest of any year, continuing the upward trend in 2001 (figure 1). Notably, support was requested by BAS on James Clark Ross in the Antarctic (see below). The length of many cruises was higher and the number of cruise days supported (313) was an increase of 40% over the previous year. A major customer was the NERC Marine Productivity thematic that funded RSDAS for ~100 days cruise support.
- Peer-reviewed publication was also the highest ever, totalling 32 in 2002, exceeding the 31 in 2001 and much higher than 13 for 2000. One reason was the publication of the DISCO cruise special issue that utilised RSDAS images of coccolithophores. Nine papers included RSDAS co-authors. An increasing number of papers use data derived from sources other than the Dundee Receiving Station.
- Facility utilisation was similar to last year, with 36 projects supported, and 18 new applications (including 5 student projects). Science quality was high with 77% of new (non student) applications graded over $\alpha 4$. Staff effort was biased towards the highest-graded projects. Staffing issues included the appointment of a new band 7 data analyst.

Hardware upgrades and processing status During the year the processing facilities were significantly upgraded with a new file server, backup server, two LTO tape stackers and ~6 Terabytes of RAID storage. Unfortunately problems with the RAID arrays caused the file server to crash repeatedly, and despite intensive efforts by PML and NERC IT support staff this has had a major impact on RSDAS processing since February 2003. This was not caused by any underfunding of RSDAS, and we now have contingency plans to reduce the risk of such situations.

Service/Software Developments MODIS Atmosphere As a result of European funding PML was able to develop and operate a near-real time service for MODIS atmospheric products. This service is available to RSDAS users and an example image was published in the Royal Meteorological Society magazine "Weather". Airborne Imagery Atmospheric Correction: further work was undertaken on development of atmospheric correction procedures for the marine imagery from the NERC CASI and ATM sensors. A presentation of results was given by Peter Land at the ARSF Workshop in Dec. 2002. An example raw and derived chlorophyll product is shown in fig. 2. Note results are still preliminary.

Science communication: Steve Groom was invited to give a presentation at SOC on RSDAS. Further eruptions on Mount Etna elicited more interest in the RSDAS Etna service. Finally, Peter Miller gave a number of interviews to radio and newspapers on algal blooms (inc. harmful blooms) around the UK.

Figure 1. Cruises supported

Figure 2: CASI raw and retrieved chl-a (mg/m^3) images for FISHERS cruise

SCIENCE SUPPORTED IN FY (2002/03):

Support of Cruise JR82 (BAS Core Programme) A new customer to RSDAS in 2002/3 was the British Antarctic Survey who requested remote sensing support of their JR82 cruise in early 2003. In support of the BAS core programme the cruise investigated how biological and physical factors affect krill distribution in the Scotia Sea. The cruise was designed to cross a number of significant physical fronts; the track was very flexible and utilised near-real time SST and chlorophyll to modify the plan whilst at sea.

Figure 3. Composite of all SeaWiFS images received during the cruise (07 Jan-24 Feb 2003), overlaid with the final cruise track. Note high chlorophyll concentrations around S. Georgia and S. Sandwich Islands.

Investigation of coccolithophore blooms in the Bering Sea (NERC Fellow and PhD student SOC). Approx. 4,500 AVHRR GAC (4-km) images from 1987 to 1996 were processed to reflectance maps by RSDAS to investigate the occurrence of coccolithophore blooms in the Bering Sea. A small, previously unreported, bloom was found in 1996 (see figure 4) preceding the enormous 1997 bloom, suggesting, contrary to previous work, that there was not a sudden change in the Bering Sea ecosystem in 1997. The results have been accepted for publication in *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, Merico, Tyrrell, Brown, Groom & Miller.

Figure 4: AVHRR image 18 Sept 1996 showing a coccolithophore bloom in the Bering Sea.

Novel Observations of Frontal Exchange and Recirculation (NERC Non-thematic grant, NER/M/S/2001/00091, SOS, UW-Bangor). This relatively small activity (for RSDAS) involved supplying sea-surface temperature images in support of field work in July 2002 at the Celtic Sea front (using ADCP, Scanfish undulating CTD, and patch dye labelling and following). It is included to show some examples of the SST products supplied by RSDAS. The image is an SST composite produced immediately prior to the cruise, showing the frontal positions.

Figure 5: SST composite for Celtic/Irish Seas showing presence of frontal boundaries. Note black area NW of Cornwall caused by diurnal surface heating masked by the RSDAS software.

12 13 14 15 16 17 1 °C

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS/STRATEGIC FORWARD LOOK

RSDAS is undertaking four development activities supported through the NERC funding. Due to the impending review of RSDAS by the next Services Review Group in January 2004 we aim to complete significant parts of each for inclusion with the paper submission in Nov. 2003. We sought advice from the ARSFSC and DSRSSC on their relative priorities, and they are ordered accordingly below.

1) MODIS Ocean Colour: RSDAS have received additional funding from NERC to enable development of ocean colour products from the NASA Moderate Resolution Spectroradiometer series of instruments. There are two MODIS instruments in orbit on-board Terra & Aqua. Data from both system are transmitted in near-real time and are received & archived at Dundee. MODIS is important since it is NASA's principal ocean colour, SST and medium resolution land observation instrument and will be followed by similar instruments over the next 12 years. Furthermore, SeaWiFS has a nominal lifetime of 5 years from launch in 1997 and so is now in "borrowed time". Up to Dec 2002 the University of Wisconsin level 1 (IMAPP) software had been implemented, but the NASA Level 1-2 ocean colour software was only provided in Jan 2003. Dr Land attended the MODIS users' meeting in Feb 03 at Boston, and was advised to use the NASA version of the level-1 software instead of IMAPP. The implementation to run with Dundee MODIS is ongoing and by June/July 2003 we expect to have a near real time MODIS service running.

Figure 6 MODIS level 2 chlorophyll-a image for 7 April 2002.

2) Airborne Remote Sensing Sensor Atmospheric Correction: the work detailed in the overview and activities section will be continued during 2003/4. The aim is to upgrade the case 1 AC and complete implementation of the case 2 algorithms.

3) PANORAMA re-write As reported last year a start has been made on re-writing much of PANORAMA, the automated processing system at the heart of RSDAS near-real time support, to take advantage of new equipment and new methods and to allow for addition of new sensors. The development will continue during the coming year with an aim of finishing the project during the financial year.

4) Upgrade of computing facilities: As noted above the RSDAS file, backup, and web servers have or will be upgraded along with addition of significant new disk storage.

RSDAS will be developing strong links this year with both the new NERC Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) Consortium and the new NERC EO Centre of Excellence: Centre for Observation of Air-Sea Interactions and Fluxes (CASIX).

PML will also undertake research and development funded externally to RSDAS but which will enable upgrades to the service perceived by NERC users. **Envisat Data:** the new ESA Envisat satellite has a number of new sensors that can support new and improved areas of science such as MERIS high quality 300m resolution ocean colour. Through EC funding PML will be investigating near-real time capabilities of MERIS. The results would be available as a possible additional RSDAS service. **Spatially enabled internet applications/e-Science:** funding from the EC will support the establishment of an Open GIS Consortium compliant MapServer based system to serve georeferenced images for use in coastal monitoring systems or models. **Marine Productivity:** NERC and EC funding has enabled development of methods for the production of phytoplankton primary production maps; during the year these will be made available through the standard RSDAS mechanisms. **Link with BADC:** RSDAS is pursuing joint funding with the NEODC to enable MODIS and other data to be made available through the data centre.

Non-Mandatory Facility-specific OPMs: utilisation, allocation of capacity etc

Cruises Supported During 2002/3			
Dates	Ship	Project	PI/Principal Scientist
07 Jan - 24 Feb 2003	James Clark Ross JR82	BAS Dynamics and Management of Ocean Ecosystems	Dr Angus Atkinson & Rebecca Korb, BAS
05 Nov - 19 Dec 2002	Discovery 267	NERC Marine Productivity thematic	Dr John Allen, SOC
23 Sep - 07 Oct 2002	Scotia	Mesoscale variability in the Faroe-Shetland Channel	Dr Bill Turrell & Ms Mary Robjant, Marine Lab. Abdn
25 Jul - 28 Aug 2002	Discovery 264	NERC Marine Productivity: Zooplankton demography and trophic interactions in the sub-arctic North Atlantic	Dr Andrew Brierley, St. Andrews
29 Jul - 12 Aug 2002	Japanese	Coccolithophores in the Bering Sea.	Mr Agostino Merico/ Dr Toby Tyrrell, SOC
22 Jul - 30 Jul 2002	Prince Madog	Novel Observations of Frontal Exchange and Recirculation (NOFEAR), at the Irish Sea front.	Dr Kevin Horsburgh, University of Wales, Bangor
12 Jul - 21 Jul 2002	Prince Madog	Inherent optical properties of marine particles in Southern Irish Sea	Dr Alex Cunningham and Ms Agnes Dudek, University of Strathclyde
01 Jun - 11 Jul 2002	Charles Darwin 141	Satellite Calibration and Interior Physics in the Indian Ocean Mascarene Ridge, Shoals of Capricorn project	Dr Jonathan Sharples, SOC
24 Jun - 07 Jul 2002	Prince Madog	Western Irish Sea and Clyde Sea	Dr Jonathan Sharples, SOC
25 Jun - 28 Jun 2002	EA Vigilance	Regional Validation of MERIS Products	Mr David Blondeau, PML/SOC
17 Jun - 21 Jun 2002	Belgica	Regional Validation of MERIS Products	Dr Gavin Tilstone, PML
13 Jun - 13 Jun 2002	Squilla	Regional Validation of MERIS Products	Dr Gavin Tilstone and Gerald Moore, PML
15 - 29 May 2002	Cirolana	Mesoscale variability in the Faroe-Shetland Channel	Dr Bill Turrell & Ms Mary Robjant, Marine Lab. Abdn
17 Apr - 27 May 2002	Discovery 262	NERC Marine Productivity	Dr Kelvin Richards, SOC
02 - 10 May 2002	Belgica 2002/11b	Coccolithophores in Celtic Sea	Dr Tim Smyth & Mr David Blondeau, PML
01 Apr - 14 Apr 2002	Discovery 261	PML-Microbially-Driven Biogeochemical Processes	Dr Carol Turley, PML

UNIVERSITY OF
NEWCASTLE

**School of Civil Engineering
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School Office · Cassie Building
University of Newcastle
Newcastle upon Tyne NE1 7RU

Head of School
David Parker
Professor of Geomatics

01 July 2003

Dr David Lin
Director, Science & Innovation
NERC
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
SN2 1EU

Dear Dr Lin

Please find attached the Services and Facilities Annual Report for the NERC Space Geodesy Facility (NSGF) for the financial year April 2002 to March 2003. The NSGF delivers accurate laser and microwave range measurements of selected Earth-orbiting satellites to global data banks, from where the data is freely available for research. The Satellite Laser Range (SLR) normal points are precise at the mm level, and accurate to better than 1 cm. In terms of quality and quantity of tracking data, the Facility is ranked in the top five of more than 30 stations worldwide. The GPS and GLONASS receivers operate autonomously and continuously. The Facility is registered with the International Laser Ranging Service (ILRS) as a Tracking Station and as an Associate Analysis Centre, and with the International GPS Service (IGS) as an IGS Tracking Site. Facility staff are involved in several ILRS Working Groups, and one member is currently serving on the ILRS Governing Board. At the last review in early 2003, the facility scored 5 in every category.

As in all previous reports it is important to stress that the NSGF does not have the usual output indicators of other Services and Facilities but is a crucial part of a global network of stations that send data to international centres from which scientists, both in the UK and abroad, extract data for their own usage. Thus, the NSGF data continues to underpin precise orbit determinations that are an essential component of the satellite altimetry data sets upon which much UK land altimetry, oceanography and ice sheet studies are based. The last year saw continuation of the four altimeter missions, with ENVISAT in tandem with ERS-2, and Jason-1 in tandem with TOPEX/Poseidon, prior to the latter being manoeuvred such that the ground-tracks bisect those of Jason-1. These missions supply UK scientists with altimetry, SAR and other data that requires precise orbit determination. NSGF is central to this task. NSGF SLR data is also used for UK research centred on maintenance of the terrestrial reference frame, polar motion studies, interferometric SAR studies and gravity field studies including the increasingly important time variability, to name just four applications.

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e-mail · ceg@ncl.ac.uk
<http://www.ceb.ncl.ac.uk/>

SLR has proven itself invaluable to the dedicated gravity field missions CHAMP and GRACE. Both have onboard GPS but the quality of the orbits can only be checked by comparison against independent tracking provided by the global SLR network. The LEO Pilot Project of the International GPS Service has striven to improve the quality of the GPS orbits of low Earth orbiters with SLR providing the strongest test data.

The GPS and GPS/GLONASS receivers at Herstmonceux are both official International GPS Service (IGS) sites with data from both used by the UK and international community for tectonic studies, ocean loading studies and for separating crustal and sea-level changes at tide gauges around the UK. Both receivers contribute data to BIGF (British Isles GPS archive Facility) in addition to the IGS. BIGF, the archiving and processing centre for GPS at IESSG, Nottingham, collects data from about 50 continuously operating GPS stations within the UK.

As chairman of the NERC Space Geodesy Steering Committee (NSGSC) I wish to record the committee's full support for the facility and our continued admiration for both the quality and quantity of data supplied to the geodetic community.

Yours sincerely

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "P. Moore". The letters are cursive and fluid.

Professor Philip Moore
Direct dial: 0191 222 5040
Email: philip.moore@ncl.ac.uk

SERVICES & FACILITIES ANNUAL REPORT - FY April 2002 to March 2003

SERVICE SPACE GEODESY FACILITY (SGF)	FUNDING Direct from 1999	AGREEMENT	ESTABLISHED as S&F 1994, operational from 1983	TERM 5 years
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TYPE OF SERVICE PROVIDED:

- **Output:** The NSGF delivers accurate laser and microwave range measurements of selected Earth-orbiting satellites to global data banks, from where they are freely available for research. The Satellite Laser Range (SLR) normal points are precise at the mm level, and accurate to better than 1 cm. In terms of quality and quantity of tracking data, the Facility is ranked in the top five of more than 30 stations worldwide. The GPS and GLONASS receivers operate autonomously and continuously. The Facility is registered with the International Laser Ranging Service (ILRS) as a Tracking Station and as an Associate Analysis Centre, and with the International GPS Service (IGS) as an IGS Tracking Site. Facility staff are involved in several ILRS Working Groups, and one member is currently serving on the ILRS Governing Board.
- **The Satellites.** The principal satellites that are tracked by SLR are the series of Earth Observation satellites (including ENVISAT, TOPEX/POSEIDON, JASON, GEOSAT-follow-on and ERS-2) that carry radar altimeters for measuring distances to sea, ice and land. Full exploitation of the altimetry information is achieved by observing the geodetic satellites (including LAGEOS) and gravity-field missions (GRACE, CHAMP, STELLA). SLR is also regularly used to observe two of the constellation of GPS satellites and the GLONASS satellites. Priorities for SGF tracking are set by the Steering Committee, taking account of recommendations from the ILRS.
- **The Science.** The work of the Space Geodesy Facility provides the raw material to underpin several areas of NERC science. Observations of the geodetic satellites by the SLR system, which is collocated with a continuously operating GPS receiver, contribute to the definition of a global geocentric reference frame: Herstmonceux is one of ten key worldwide reference stations that define the scale and origin of this frame. Observations of remote-sensing satellites allow accurate computation of their orbits within this same, well-defined reference frame. In turn, satellite altimetry and SAR measurements to the oceans, ice caps and land areas can be accurately calibrated using this precise knowledge of the positions of the satellites. Such data impacts upon ongoing UK studies into for example long-term variation in sea level (e.g., Newcastle), ocean circulation/anomaly dynamics (SOC, POL), polar ice mass-balance and response to climate change (e.g. UCL), improvement of global digital elevation models (De Montfort), forest vegetation dynamics (CEH). In addition, UK research is underway (Newcastle and SGF) to make rapid determinations of Earth centre-of-mass variations, using SLR observations of the geodetic satellites and by combining solutions from several ILRS analysis centres. Novel observations from Herstmonceux continue to be used to derive spin-vector information for the LAGEOS-2 satellite, which are being used to model non-conservative forces on the satellite (SGF, Communications Research Lab, Japan and DEOS, Delft, The Netherlands.)

SCORES AT LAST REVIEW (each out of 5)			Date of Last Review: 2003	
Need 5	Uniqueness 5	Quality of Service 5	Quality of Science & Training 5	Average 5

CAPACITY of HOST ENTITY FUNDED by S&F 53 %	Staff & Status (NERC Bands) 100% of 2 at Band 5, 4 at Band 6, 1 at Band 7	Next Review (January 2008)	Contract Ends (31 March 2009)
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FINANCIAL DETAILS: CURRENT FY							
Recurrent Allocation £k 248	Unit Cost £k - N/A			Capital Expend £k 220	Income £k 220	Full cash cost £k 468	
	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3				
FINANCIAL COMMITMENT (by year until end of current agreement) = FCC- Income. Numbers assume funding partners continue at current level. Excludes any per-annum Capital Bids.							
2002-03	£250k	2003-04	£250k	2004-05	£250k	2006-07	£250k

STEERING COMMITTEE	Independent Members	Meetings per annum	Other S&F Overseen
NERC Space Geodesy Steering Committee, NSGSC	7	1	BIGF

APPLICATIONS: DISTRIBUTION OF GRADES (Current FY)

Users do not normally apply *directly* to the Facility for any products or services. The raw data from SGF, namely accurate observations of satellite positions are made freely available in close-to-real-time as part of a commitment to three of the Services of the International Association of Geodesy (ILRS, IGS and IGLOS, respectively). From these raw observations both UK and international users and agencies derive the principal end products, which include accurate orbits of remote-sensing satellites, a global reference frame and measurements of the Earth's orientation in space. These products then underpin the scientific exploitation of the remote sensing data, such as altimetry and SAR, as well as being of scientific interest in their own right.

The laser ranging satellite tracking priorities are set by our steering committee (NSGSC) with UK users in mind, but again with a knowledge of ILRS priorities.

The UK user base in the field of space geodesy has been approximately quantified from direct knowledge of numbers of university departments, Centres/Surveys and National Agencies.

PROJECTS COMPLETED (Current FY)

NOT APPLICABLE – SEE ABOVE

USER PROFILE (current FY) No Users directly funded to use SGF data *combined non-Thematic and Thematic

Grand Total	PAYG				Infrastructure					
	NERC Grant *	Student		NERC C/S	Other	supplement to NERC Grant*	Student		NERC C/S	Other
		Total	NERC				Total	NERC		

USER PROFILE (per annum average last 3 years)

NOT DETERMINED, BUT LIKELY TO BE SIMILAR TO CURRENT YEAR

USER PROFILE (current FY) -

Academic 9	Centre/Survey 4	NERC Fellows	PhD 4	Commercial >3
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USER PROFILE (per annum average last 3 years)

NOT DETERMINED, BUT LIKELY TO BE SIMILAR TO CURRENT YEAR.

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (current FY)

Publications (by science area & type)

SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses	Grand Total
	3	3			2	2	5	5		10

Distribution of Projects (by science areas) - % from publications. Not all publications fit these categories

SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar
	27%	24%	2%	9%	9%	6%

OUTPUT & PERFORMANCE MEASURES (per annum average last 3 years)

Publications (by science area & type) NOT DETERMINED, BUT LIKELY TO BE SIMILAR TO CURRENT YEAR

SBA	ES	MS	AS	TFS	EO	Polar	Refereed	Non-Ref/ Conf Proc	PhD Theses	Grand Total

Distribution of Projects (by science areas)

NOT DETERMINED, BUT LIKELY TO BE SIMILAR TO CURRENT YEAR

SCHOOL OF BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES
Institute of Cell, Animal and Population Biology

The University of Edinburgh
Ashworth Laboratories
King's Buildings
West Mains Road
Edinburgh EH9 3JT
Telephone 0131 650 5505
Fax 0131 650 6564
E-mail J.Pemberton@ed.ac.uk

Vanessa Smallridge
Administration Officer
Science & Innovation Funding
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU

January 13, 2004

Dear Mrs Smallridge

Sheffield Molecular Genetics Facility

I am pleased to present the report for 2002-3 for the above facility. This was read and approved by the steering committee at its last meeting. I believe this facility performs an exceptionally useful function for a wide variety of NERC researchers.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. J.M. Pemberton
Chair of Steering Committee

